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Executive Summary

In 2019, a wide-ranging Landing Obligation (LO) is to be fully in place within the European Union, ensuring that all fish that is hauled on board fishing vessels operating in European waters is brought to shore (with few minor exceptions). To be able to fulfil these requirements, fishermen and stakeholders operating in various fishing industries will need to have viable solutions for what to do with the excess catch and that is the focus of this report.

The report focuses on four different fishing fleet sectors and two national examples that represent a good cross-section of European fisheries, varying in size and operation. The report is structured in such a way that each case is independent, which allows the reader to choose what case studies to read. This does however mean that there is some repetition when reading the report as a whole.

The six case studies presented in this document are small-scale coastal vessels, intermediate size bottom trawlers / Danish seiners, large-scale fresh fish bottom trawlers, and large factory bottom trawler; as well as national examples/analysis of how the Greek and the Irish fishing sectors could attempt to meet the requirements of the Landing Obligation.

The first four cases are presented with detailed 3D drawings of the vessels along with renders of images and videos on the DiscardLess webpage <http://www.discardless.eu> which enables stakeholders to see the results in a visual manner. Furthermore, a cost-benefit tool can be found on the website as well, which makes it possible to get raw estimates on return of investment based on the fleet type and gear chosen.

All the solutions presented are currently available on-board fishing vessels and are being used by several fleet segments and therefore the focus was on making them realistic and feasible to implement. The solutions focus largely on separating between the target catches and the unwanted catches and to provide alternatives for processing and storing under Minimum Conservation Reference Size catches as well as unwanted, unavoidable catches. These categories cannot be utilized for direct human consumption according to the Landing Obligation of the EU Common Fisheries Policy.

Given the current status of the EU fisheries and seafood sector and how it is adapting to the Landing Obligation, it is the opinion of the authors of this report that there is a need for implementing short-term simple solutions to meet the requirements of the Landing Obligation; but that strategies for long-term solutions need also to be drafted. The main emphasis of this report is on short-term solutions in the form of silage, fishmeal and fish oil production that can be implemented immediately. The report does though also identify and discuss more complicated long-term solutions that require significant investment and forward thinking of everyone in the value chain.

Abbreviations

CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CIF	Cost, Insurance and Freight
DCF	Data Collection Framework
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
EU	European Union
FPC	Fish Protein Concentrate
FPH	Fish Protein Hydrolysate
H&G	Headed and Gutted
Hp	Horse Power
IQF	Individually Quickly Frozen
ITQ	Individual Transferable Quota
LO	Landing Obligation
MCRS	Minimum conservational reference size
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MLS	Minimum Landing Size
OTB	Bottom Otter Trawl
PTB	Bottom Pair Trawl
PUFA	Polyunsaturated fatty acids
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RRM	Rest Raw Material
RSW	Refrigerated Sea Water
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement
STECF	EU Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UUC	Unwanted unavoidable catch

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1 Introduction

Discards have been a part of fishing practices in most fisheries around the world since fisheries began. Fishers have selected what fish to keep and what to release or throw back into the sea long before quotas and catch limits were invented. The introduction of catch limits has, however, created new incentives for discarding, as fishers try to maximise the value of their catches under quota regimes. Unwanted catches, such as low value bycatches, undersized fish, catches exceeding quotas and catches of target species that are unlikely to fetch premium prices are thrown back, and much of these catches are dead or dying. This has been the practice in European fisheries under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) of the European Union (EU). Based on EUROSTAT data it can be estimated that in European fisheries 1.7 million tonnes of all species have been discarded annually, corresponding to 23% of total catches (EC, 2011). This practice has been the subject of increasing levels of debate (Borges & Penas, 2019). As a result, the European Commission has introduced a Landing Obligation as a part of the 2013 reform of the CFP (EC, 2013). This means that all catches of species subject to catch limits, i.e. where total allowable catches (TAC) have been set and in the Mediterranean catches of species subject to minimum sizes, will have to be landed and will be counted against quotas. The obligation has been gradually implemented. The first fisheries were subject to this Landing Obligation in beginning of 2015 and by 2019 all EU fisheries are required to land the entire catch of all species subject to catch limits.

In recent years, the main focus of the EU authorities, researchers and the seafood industry working on the implementation of the Landing Obligation has been on how to avoid unwanted catches and how to facilitate efficient monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) of unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC). There has, however, been much less attention given to what to do with the unwanted catches which, prior to the implementation of the Landing Obligation, would have been discarded after being caught. Exceptions to the Landing Obligation and limits on permitted uses of the unwanted catches do have to be taken carefully into consideration when contemplating on board handling and stowage. Species not covered by catch limits, species where high survivability can be demonstrated and catches falling under the *de minimis* exceptions can still be discarded under the Landing Obligation; but everything else will need to be landed. In addition, catches under Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) need to be landed but cannot be used for direct human consumption. With all this in mind, it is clear that space for classification, proper handling and stowage will become an issue for much of the EU fishing fleet when the Landing Obligation is fully implemented. The available alternatives for addressing that challenge are scarce and are generally only applicable for larger vessels - but 85% of the EU fleet are under 12 meters long and 97% are under 24 meters (EU, 2018), which severely reduces available solutions.

Catches falling under the Landing Obligation can be broken into two basic groups i.e. catches under MCRS that cannot be used for direct human consumption and catches above MCRS that can be used for human consumption. By-catch of species not subject to catch limits (or minimum size in the Mediterranean) can still be discarded as before. The main challenges for on board handling are connected to catches under MCRS, as the larger fish destined for human consumption can, for the most part, simply be diverted to the traditional on-board handling processes that are already available. However, stowage of low value species with catch limits can have an effect on the

duration of fishing trips, as stowage space is limited. The MCRS catches have to be recorded and stowed separately from the catches intended for human consumption (EU 2015/812) and vessels greater than 12 meters length overall also have to place their catches in boxes, compartments or containers separately for each stock, just as with any other catches (EC 1224/2009). This basically means that any mixing of species during stowage on board is prohibited. Vessels will therefore need to have two separated compartments for stowage i.e. one for <MCRS catches and another for human consumption catches; vessels greater than 12 meters in length will need to sort everything into boxes, tubs or other such compartments. It is therefore evident that significantly more space will be required for on board classification, handling and stowage; in addition to added labour.

The Landing Obligation presents a number of challenges for the European seafood sector. Fishing strategies of individual fishers will have to be enhanced, selectivity of fishing gear will need to be improved, on board handling, sorting, storing and monitoring of compliance will need to be reconsidered, land-based processing will have to adjust to different supplies, and markets will be affected. The purpose of this report is to discuss challenges that the Landing Obligation presents to the on-board handling of unwanted catches and to demonstrate how vessel layout modifications and linked land-based facilities can be applied to meet with these challenges. The report focuses on four different fishing fleet sectors and two national examples that represent a good cross-section of European fisheries, varying in size and operation. The report is structured in such a way that each case is independent, which allows the reader to choose what case studies to read. This does however mean that there is some repetition when reading the report as a whole.

The six case studies presented in this report are small-scale coastal vessels, intermediate size Danish seiners/trawlers, large-scale fresh fish bottom trawlers, and large freezer trawler; as well as national examples/analysis of how the Greek and the Irish fishing sectors can attempt meet the requirements of the Landing Obligation.

The first four cases are presented with detailed 3D drawings of the vessels along with renders of images and videos on the DiscardLess webpage <http://www.discardless.eu> which enables stakeholders to see the results in a visual manner. Furthermore, a cost-benefit tool can be found on the website as well, which makes it possible to get raw estimates on return of investment based on the fleet type and gear chosen.

All the solutions presented are currently available on-board fishing vessels and are being used by several fleet segments around the world. The focus of this report is therefore to demonstrate how they can be applied and to make them realistic and feasible to implement in EU context. The solutions focus largely on separating between the target catches and the UUC and to provide alternatives for processing and storing under MCRS catches, as well as the by-catches.

The DiscardLess project was initiated by H2020 to contribute to a successful implementation of the Landing Obligation. The objectives of the project are to provide knowledge, tools and methods required to the successful reduction of discards in EU fisheries. To achieve this, DiscardLess has worked through collaborations between scientists, stakeholders and policy makers to support

and promote practical, achievable, acceptable and cost-efficient discard mitigation strategies, with the aim to make the EU Landing Obligation functional, credible and legitimate. The DiscardLess project is broken into nine work packages (WPs), which collectively are meant to reach the above-mentioned objectives. This report is the fifth and final deliverable of WP5, which is titled “From deck to first sale”, and like the title suggests is meant to focus on the part of the supply chain from capture to processing. The previous deliverables in this WP have identified and discussed current on-board discard practises and ongoing initiatives to reduce discards (D5.1), preliminary identifications and recommendations on on board solutions for handling unwanted catches (5.2), identifications and recommendations for MCS of discards (D5.3), and demonstrations on how vessel modifications can be applied to facilitate the successful implementation of the Landing Obligation in selected case studies (D5.4). This final deliverable (D5.5) builds on the previous work in the WP (along with input from other WPs; particularly WP6) by suggesting application of identified solutions in six “pilot case studies” that have been carefully selected to represent diverse and relevant cross-section of the EU fishing sector.

2 Small-scale coastal vessels

Highlights of chapter

- Approximately 85% of the EU fishing fleet consists of small coastal vessels below 12 meters in length.
- Main challenge for the fleet is limited space on board for handling and stowage of unwanted catches.
- Regulations allow for landing of mixed species, but catches intended for non-human consumption are to be separated from those intended for human consumption.
- Low volume of unwanted catches from each vessel creates challenges, as processors require significant volume to raise interested.
- Good practice on board handling for all catches is needed to facilitate utilisation in the right processing channels.
- Classification and allocation of catches into the right processing channels for this fleet type will for the most parts have to be done during or after landing.

The EU fleet consists of approximately 83 thousand vessels, where 85% are considered small coastal vessels below 12 meters in length (EU, 2018). This fleet is therefore highly variable with regards to target species, construction, engine power and design, with the state-of-the-art vessels being made from fiberglass and boasting the most technically advanced processing lines on board. Figure 1 shows the variability that can be between vessels in this fleet segment.

Figure 1. Small coastal vessels fishing in European waters. They can differ vastly in size and application, from traditional wooden jiggers to high-tech fiberglass vessel with state-of-the-art equipment (photos: Matís and Seigla).

The main challenge for this fleet sector, when it comes to the implementation of the Landing Obligation, is the extremely limited space on board available for handling and stowage. These vessels are, just like any other EU fishing vessels, required to recorded and stow MCRS catches

separately from the catches intended for human consumption (EU 2015/812). Vessels below 12 meters in length are however exempted from the requirement to place their catches in boxes, compartments or containers separately for each stock (EC 1224/2009) i.e. they can land their catches mixed for on-land classification.

The volumes of UUC caught by this small-scale fleet are expected to be relatively low, which is why the need for implementing a Landing Obligation for the sector has been debated (Veiga, et al., 2016). Especially since discard problems in the EU fleet have historically been associated with medium- to large-scale fleets. The small coastal vessels are more targeted in their catches and have higher incentives to land everything they catch.

Most of the EU small-scale coastal fleet consists of boats that are out at sea for less than 24 hours each trip, which means that if the UUC and fish under MCRS is treated like other catches and chilled properly, there should be little difficulties in utilising it once landed. Those catches must however ideally be sorted so they can be diverted to the appropriate production streams upon landing.

The solutions discussed below are focused on the advanced technical capabilities for these vessel types and therefore provide stakeholders operating in this fleet with an example of where to aim in order to maximize their product handling and quality. The solutions are presented in technical drawings rendered in 3D and animated videos that are available on the DiscardLess webpage; along with a cost-benefit analysis tool that allows for a rough estimation on the return of investment for these vessel types, given the equipment that is provided in the example.

2.1 On board handling

All catches need to go through the same on-board handling to maximise quality and extend shelf life. This applies to target catches as well as UUC, because making top quality products from second rate raw material is impossible. The main steps in the on-board handling of the catch are bleeding, gutting, cleaning, chilling, grading, storing and ensuring adequate traceability. There are a few exceptions when looking at UUC, as some of them are not intended for human consumption and do therefore not have to hold up to the same standards (Viðarsson, Iñarra, Pérez-Villarreal, & Larsen, 2016). Following is a short discussion on the main steps in on board handling of the catches on board these small coastal vessels.

Firstly, the catch must be brought on board the vessel in a manner that will not damage the fish or cause material deterioration of any kind. This includes gaffing the fish in the head instead of in the upper parts of the flesh, often damaging the more valuable parts of the fish e.g. fillet or loins.

Bleeding and gutting are essential to rid the fish of contamination bacteria which reduce the quality of the raw material (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). These bacteria start to grow at exponential rates post rigor mortis and therefore all mediums in which they linger, such as blood and intestines must be removed to slow the deterioration process of the fish muscles during storage. For most lean whitefish species such as cod and hake, given adequate cooling and proper bleeding and gutting, the shelf life cannot be extended much beyond two weeks; and for fatty species such as mackerel and herring this time is much shorter, or 1 ½ week at most. Another

factor to consider is the iron content of the blood, as iron acts as an oxidation agent when exposed to oxygen and therefore it can have severe impact on the quality of the fish fillets, most noticeably in colour and taste. This is especially noticeable for fatty species, but the fat is quick to lose the freshness and rancidity grows exponentially. If gutting is not possible or cannot be done properly on board after the fish has been bled, it is best to leave that part of the process out until the catch has been landed. Improper gutting of the fish can often result in worse material quality due to spoilage bacteria and enzymes from the intestines making their way into the fish muscle post-improper gutting.

Washing should be done in seawater, which may be also chilled to speed up the chilling process. Simply immersing the fish for a few seconds is not enough time for the blood to drain from the muscles. For best results, the heart should still be beating when the fish is bled, since then the heart acts as a pump which drains the fish quicker. Special bleeding tanks are advised for these applications, thus immersing the fish for a few minutes after bleeding until it is gutted and sent through cooling.

Chilling and maintaining of unbroken chill-chain is extremely important, as it is a deciding factor on quality and shelf life of the catch. Cooling is generally either done with ice or slurry in boxes/tubs in the hold of the vessels; or with pre-chilling in purpose-built cooling tanks on the processing deck. It is vital that the chilling process does not take too long time and ideally the muscle should be close to the initial freezing point of water from the time it enters storage in the hold. The cooling in pre-chilling tanks can take up to an hour should it be done sufficiently, depending on size of the fish, throughput and cooling media. The temperature in fish that is only chilled with ice in the hold can take many hours to reach the desired 0°C depending on the quality of the icing. Amongst the risks associated with inefficient cooling is that if the catch is not chilled properly from the beginning, it will have the effects that the fish will go earlier and faster through rigor mortis, which will result in gaping and shortening of shelf life. The effects of fish going fast through rigor mortis is intermuscular loosening and the fish becomes slimy and undesirable.

Equally vital to proper cooling of the catch is the maintenance of cold temperatures in the fish muscles. Vessels that use ice to cool down their products before storing are simply not cooling their fish as efficiently as possible. When fish at sea temperature enters a fishing tub or box full of ice, the ice starts to melt, leading to the fish being stored in water. Another factor to consider is that storage holds are not designed to cool products down, but to maintain even temperatures. If these things are misunderstood, temperature will rise in the storage hold. Research have shown that by pre-cooling products before going into temperature-controlled storage, their shelf life can be extended by 1-4 days (Martinsdóttir, et al., 2010).

Grading the catch according to species and size is important part of on board handling. In many fisheries it is a matter of legislation to keep species separate, but it is also important with regards to the processing to grade according to species and size. The correct species and sizes can then be transferred directly to the desired processing and production can be better planned. The grading is in most cases manual and can either be done by personnel on the processing deck during gutting or by the personnel in the hold during storing preparations. On board larger vessels it is common

to send only the target species directly to the hold and store by-catches in purpose-built boxes on the processing deck, until all target catches from the haul have been handled.

When it comes to grading of UUC it will depend upon what products are going to be made from the raw material and what requirements will be set by the authorities with for example separation between catches intended for human consumption and non-human consumption. There may also be potentials for grading all materials intended for non-human consumption in one lot, as far as catches can be registered adequately by species.

When fish is brought down to the hold, it should be placed in dedicated storage vessels. This can be in the form of specially made fish boxes, usually storing up to 50 kg of fish, or thermally insulated fish tubs of various sizes. As most vessels in Europe use fish boxes for storage of fish in the cargo hold, this will be used as an example in this chapter. An example of these boxes can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Typical fish boxes used for storage of fresh fish in cargo holds of the European fleet (GW Containers and Equipment, 2018).

Most by-products and materials for non-human consumption need to go through similar steps as the main product materials. There are however exceptions. This includes for example liver, roes, milt and other viscera (if the fish is gutted), as well as materials that are classified as unsuitable for human consumption. These are to be kept separate from other catches to avoid cross-contamination. There are different alternatives for on-shore handling of such materials, including freezing, fishmeal production, silage and more.

The materials intended for non-human consumption are going to represent the main challenges for the EU fleet operating under the Landing Obligation, as use of catches below Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) will be restricted to purposes other than direct human consumption. The MCRS is intended to ensure protection of juveniles, as fishermen will be in this way be motivated to avoid catching fish under MCRS. The MCRS replaces Minimum Landing Size (MLS), which prior to the implementation of the Landing Obligation was required to be discarded. When considering alternatives for on board handling of UUC, the size of the vessels, the length of each fishing trip and the species composition becomes a major deciding factor on what and how many alternatives are available.

2.2 The demonstration vessel

For demonstration of available solutions, the authors of this report have selected Cleopatra 38, which is a 11.3-metre long and 3.8-meter-wide fiberglass coastal vessel, seen in Figure 3. This is a boat that is quite common in the NE-Atlantic, North-Sea and adjacent areas. It is manufactured in Iceland, where it has proven itself under harsh conditions. Being manufactured in Iceland, where there is an active discard ban already in place and great emphasis is placed on maintaining quality of all catches, has contributed to significant efforts being awarded to development of solutions for improved on board handling of target and by-catches alike, for this vessel type.

Cleopatra 38 has an upper-deck where receiving and initial handling takes place, and a lower-deck where the storage hold, engine and cabins are located. Cleopatra 38 is available with wide range of engines, typically rendering 4-500 horsepower that give the boat a top speed of around 35 nm.

Figure 3. Cleopatra 38 coming to shore with load and another with no cargo running at full speed (Trefjar, 2018)

The upper deck is just about 3.5*6 meters, or 21.7 m², which is used for carrying and shooting the gear, receiving the catch, bleeding, gutting (if that is done on board) and cleaning. The hold is 13.5 m³ and can hold approximately 5 tonnes of catches.

These vessels either use nets or longlines to catch the fish and then the fish is sent to bleeding before being placed in a cooling medium and then boxes/tubs with ice. The main steps in the material handling can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The most common main steps in on board handling of catch on small coastal vessels (photo: Matís).

The catch is rarely gutted on board these small boats that are only out at sea for less than 24 hours. There is usually not enough space to properly gut and clean the fish on board these vessels, and improperly cleaned fish will spoil quickly as enzymes and bacteria from the viscera penetrates the flesh. The emphasis is therefore placed on chilling the catch as fast as possible and maintaining temperatures around freezing point until landed. Using ice slurry, that is made by mixing plate ice with seawater, has shown to chill catches faster under the most common circumstances (Þorvaldsson, Lauzon, Margeirsson, Martinsdóttir, & Arason, 2010), which is due to lower temperature of the solution because of the salt content of the seawater and because the slurry covers the fish better. The slurry also reduces damage on the fish due to falling into the tub, arranges better in the tubs and has better overall appearance.

In cases where gutting is necessary on board the vessel, for example if the fishing trip takes more than 24 hours, there is a need to have a bleeding- and cleaning tank/tub on the upper deck. The gutting is then usually done “in air” opposed to on a table, as there is rarely a space for a gutting table. This means that the gutting can be tricky and must be done carefully to avoid damaging the fish or allowing for cross-contamination of enzymes and bacteria from the viscera. Figure 5 shows a cod being gutted “in air” on board a small fishing vessel (photos: Matís).

Figure 5. Cod gutted "in air" on board a small fishing vessel.

Typically, these vessels haul on average 2-4 tons of catch in one fishing tour (when operating in the North Sea, N-Atlantic and adjacent waters), consisting mainly of cod. Annual catches in boats like Cleopatra 38 in Iceland average 500 tons or a value approximating 1.3 million EUR given current landing prices.

Estimating discard rates for this fleet segment is difficult, but the general consensus seems to be that small-scale coastal fisheries generate marginal discards (Veiga, et al., 2016) (Villasante, et al., 2015). The discard rate from longlining in Iceland is around 0.1% comprising mostly of juvenile fish and choke species (Pálsson, Björnsson, Guðmundsson, & Ottesen, 2015), but that should be a relatively good indicator on discard rates amongst small coastal vessels in those waters. There is no reason to expect very different numbers for discards from this vessel category in other NE-Atlantic waters (and adjacent waters) operating within a Landing Obligation.

There are very limited alternatives for making any special arrangements for UUC on board such small vessels, especially since the volume of UUC in each fishing trip is likely to be only a few kilos. What is possible to do is to handle the UUC as any other target catch, by bleeding, cleaning and chilling to maintain quality. The UUC can then be sorted into special tubs/boxes that are clearly labelled/coloured and can then be treated as necessary after landing. The MCRS needs to be clearly separated from other catches, but apart from that it is possible to land mixed batches. Good on-board classification of catches is however advice, as it makes it easier to divert catches to appropriate production streams upon landing.

There are "best practise" solutions available for this fleet segment for securing efficient bleeding, cleaning and chilling of all catches, including target species, by-catches and UUC. There are for example bleeding/cleaning tanks available that are specially designed for small coastal vessels. They have controllable throughput rate, so that each fish is in the tank for as long as needed. They also ensure first-in, first-out and are designed so they will not disturb the stability of these small

vessels too much. Sufficient time in a bleeding tank with good circulation and water replacement should be around 10-15 minutes (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). There are several solutions of this kind available for vessels of this size. They come in different sizes and can be purpose-built for each vessel. The systems showcased in the figures below would cost around 30 thousand EUR. These bleeding/cleaning tanks can also be turned into a pre-cooling tanks, by connecting them to an ice machine that can easily be fitted in the lower deck of the boat. There are several suppliers of such Ice machines available, one of which is ThorIce, but a slurry ice machine from them that can produce up to 1,5 ton/hour of 10% slurry ice, which is sufficient for pre-cooling on board Cleopatra 38. Such a system would cost around 30 thousand EUR. The machine does not take much space (120/30/60 cm) and there are already a few similar vessels that have fitted this machine in the engine room. If the crew would like to use the machine to also produce slurry ice to use in the hold, they would need to start production while steaming out and casting the lines, so that the tubs would be partly filled when they start hauling. For vessels using smaller boxes in the hold, it is more difficult to compile a buffer, so taking ice from land would be advised.

A recommended setup for ensuring best possible on-board handling, with respect to efficient bleeding, cleaning, chilling, storing and delicate overall handling is shown in Figure 6. The fish is brought on board by the person standing closest to the edge of the boat. It is then transferred to the bleeding station where the other person bleeds the catch and pushes it to the bleeding unit situated beside him.

Figure 6. Recommended setup of bleeding and cooling unit on board the vessel.

After the fish has been bled, it is passed into the cooling unit, where it stays for a fixed amount of time until it is transferred down to the hold. Once down to the reception tub in the cargo hold, where the third person is located, the target catch is sorted by species and size into fish boxes while the UUC and catch under MCRS are placed in mixed batches in dedicated larger tubs (blue tubs in Figure 7) to be sorted onshore. Ice is used to keep the catch cool post-cooling on the upper deck. This is further illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The lower deck of the vessel where sorting and storing of main species and bycatch is performed.

To chill the catch as shown in Figure 6, seawater is first used for producing ice slurry in the compressor units located on the lower deck shown in Figure 7. The slurry is then stored in a buffer tank; and if needed it can also produce ice buffer into a larger tub (red tub in Figure 7). The slurry is then pumped to the cooling unit on the upper deck. To further aid in the cooling process, ice can be taken at port and stored in larger tubs, as shown in Figure 7 (red tub).

Given that this setup is used, the UUC will be landed at best possible quality ready to be used for whatever processing chosen. The value of the UUC will, however, be marginal as the volume will be low along with the value of each kilogram of by-catch. The investment in the cooling unit along with the slurry ice maker machine suggested above is around 60 thousand EUR and installation cost, including hoses, valves and other miscellaneous is around 10 thousand EUR. The potential value adding derived from their instalment would solely be coming from higher prices for the target catch, due to improved quality. Estimating potential value adding is almost impossible. The catches are sold on an auction market, where supply and demand are the main price deciders, and the linkage between price and quality may not always be clear. A conservative estimate is though that quality improvements derived from improved bleeding, cleaning and chilling could render around 3% price premium. In the case of this vessel it would increase the annual landing value by approximately 40 thousand EUR. The payback time would therefore be around 2-3 years (not considering that the share of the crew can generally not be used for covering these kind of investments).

2.3 Summary

Approximately 85% of the EU fishing fleet consists of vessels under 12 meters in length (EU, 2018), this is a very important fleet segment, as it has been reported that the EU small-scale fisheries sector account for 25% of the revenues generated by EU fisheries (Villasante, et al., 2015). This sector has also high social, economic and cultural importance for coastal communities. These small-scale vessels have however very limited alternatives for handling UUC any differently from other catches, but because discard rates are for the most parts very low in this fleet category

the recommended “best practise” solutions suggested here are to simply handle the UUC as any other catches and then store them in specially labelled (coloured) boxes that can then be diverted to the proper production lines upon landing. It may not be strictly necessary to treat UUC the same as the target catches, as some of it will be used for non-human consumption, but the simplest way is to treat all catches the same to avoid cross-contamination and other possible problems. It is of particular concerns for this fleet sector that catches below MCRS landed after each fishing trip are so small that they do generally not create enough incentives for buyers to source them. Special solutions will therefore have to be implemented to aggregate these catches so that they become large enough to attract the attention of potential buyers.

3 Small and medium-sized bottom trawlers and Danish seiners

Highlights of chapter

- Approximately 12% of the EU fleet are small- and medium-sized vessels ranging between 12 and 24 meters in overall length.
- These small- and medium-sized vessels represent an important segment of the EU fleet.
- Small- and medium-sized bottom trawlers and Danish seiners are examples of vessels engaged in mixed fisheries where the Landing Obligation presents major challenges.
- Fishing vessels in this fleet category are required to stow separately each species and to clearly divide between catches intended for human and non-human consumption.
- There are limited alternatives available for handling and stowage of the catches on board these vessels, due to lack of space and human resources.
- Good practice on board handling for all catches is needed to facilitate utilisation in the right processing channels; meaning that all catches should ideally be handled and stowed in similar fashion. Further classification and allocation to appropriate processing channels can then be done during or after landing.
- Silage production is a simple solution that can be applicable for this fleet section but returning profits for that kind of processing can be a challenge.

Approximately 12% of the EU fleet are small- and medium-sized vessels ranging between 12 and 24 meters in overall length (EU, 2018). Significant part of the vessels within this size group (or similar) use bottom trawls and Danish seine as fishing gear. Bottom trawlers and Danish seiners ranging between 18 and 30 meters are particularly an important part of the EU fleet, especially in the NE-Atlantic, North-Sea and adjacent waters. These vessels typically target roundfish and flatfish species, as well as Nephrops. Figure 8 shows two vessels that represent this fleet type well (photos: Willem Harlaar to the left and Ally 1903 to the right)

Figure 8: Small bottom trawlers and Danish seiners represent an important part of EU fleet

The main challenge fishermen on these vessels face in connection with the implementation of the Landing Obligation is limited space for handling and stowage of the catches. The catch needs to be properly handled to maintain quality and then classified by species (and size where applicable) into boxes, compartments or containers in the hold (EC 1224/2009). Catches below MCRS must be recorded and stowed separately from the catches intended for human consumption (EU 2015/812).

Vessels within this category vary considerably in size and structure, which of course has significant effect on available alternatives for handling and stowing UUC. Some of the vessels have only two decks i.e. main (upper) deck where the bleeding, gutting and cleaning takes place, and the lower deck (cargo hold) where classification into boxes and stowage is. Other vessels have three decks i.e. the upper deck, the middle deck where the main handling is done and the lower deck (hold) where the catch is stowed.

The operation of the vessels does also differ in important way, as some are for example only out at sea for less than 24 hours; whilst others can be out at sea for up to one week. The vessels that land their catches within hours of capture can therefore land ungutted catches, whilst the others have to put efforts into gutting and cleaning the catch.

An example of a typical two decked Danish seiner can be seen in Figure 9, but it clearly shows how limited space there is on the upper deck for properly bleed, gut and clean the catch. There is then one person on the lower deck (in the hold) that has to classify the catch by species and size into boxes and arrange the boxes in the hold.

Figure 9. An example of a Danish seiner (Árni Sæberg, 2018).

To reach the highest possible material quality of the fish being brought to shore, it is of the utmost importance to bleed, gut and properly clean the catch as soon as possible after it is brought on board and use a combination of chilling and icing the catch during storage. If a dedicated processing method for chilling of the catch is not available on board the vessel, adequate amounts of ice should be used to cool the catch as effectively as possible and keep it chilled until it is landed on shore. This includes maintaining temperatures in the storage hold around 0°C.

UUC, such as by-catches of limited value and catches below MCRS, must be handled in accordance with requirements set by authorities and potential buyers. The following chapters identify and discuss good-practise on board handling of target catches and UUC in further detail.

3.1 On board handling

All catches should ideally go through the same on-board handling to maximise quality and extend shelf life. This applies to target catches as well as UUC, because making top quality products from second rate raw material is impossible. The main steps in the on-board handling of the catch are bleeding, gutting, cleaning, chilling, grading, storing and ensuring adequate traceability. There are a few exceptions when looking at UUC, as some of them are not intended for human consumption and do therefore not have to hold up to the same standards (Viðarsson, Iñarra, Pérez-Villarreal, & Larsen, 2016). Following is a short discussion on the main steps in on board handling of the catches on board small and medium-sized bottom trawlers and Danish seiners.

Firstly, the catch must be brought on board the vessel in a manner that will not damage the fish or cause material deterioration of any kind. In this regard, it is important not to haul too large quantities at the same time on board to limit the fish getting squashed at the bottom of the net when hauling on board deck.

After the fish is brought on board, the bleeding and gutting are essential to rid the fish of contamination bacteria which reduce the quality of the raw material (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). These bacteria start to grow at exponential rates post rigor mortis and therefore all mediums in which they linger, such as blood and intestines must be removed to slow the deterioration process of the fish muscles during storage. For most lean whitefish species such as cod and hake, given adequate cooling and proper bleeding and gutting, the shelf life can be extended to approximately 2 – 2 ½ weeks at most; and for fatty species such as mackerel and herring this time is 1 – 1 ½ week. Another factor to consider is the iron content of the blood, as iron acts as an oxidation agent when exposed to oxygen and therefore it can have severe impact on the quality of the fish fillets, most noticeably in colour and taste. This is especially noticeable for fatty species, but the fat is quick to lose the freshness and rancidity grows exponentially. If gutting is not possible or cannot be done properly on board after the fish has been bled, it is best to leave that part of the process out until the catch has been landed. Improper gutting of the fish can often result in worse material quality due to spoilage bacteria and enzymes from the intestines making their way into the fish muscle post-improper gutting.

Washing should be done in clean seawater, which may also be chilled to speed up the chilling process. Simply immersing the fish for a few seconds is not enough time for the blood to completely drain from the muscles. For best results, the heart should still be beating when the fish is bled since then the heart acts as a pump which drains the fish quicker. Special bleeding tanks are advised for these applications, thus immersing the fish for a few minutes after bleeding until it is gutted and sent through cooling.

Chilling and maintaining of an unbroken chill-chain is extremely important, as it is a deciding factor on quality and shelf life of the catch. Cooling is generally either done with ice or slurry in

boxes/tubs in the hold of the vessels; or with pre-chilling in purpose-built cooling tanks on the processing deck. It is vital that the chilling process does not take too long time and ideally the muscle should be close to the initial freezing point of water from the time it enters storage in the hold. The cooling in pre-chilling tanks can take up to an hour should it be done sufficiently, depending on size of the fish, throughput and cooling media. The temperature in fish that is only chilled with ice in the hold can take many hours to reach the desired 0°C depending on the quality of the icing. Amongst the risks associated with inefficient cooling is that if the catch is not chilled properly from the beginning, it will have the effects that the fish will go earlier and faster through rigor mortis, which will result in gaping and shortening of shelf life. The effects of fish going fast through rigor mortis is intermuscular loosening and the fish becomes slimy and undesirable.

Equally vital to proper cooling of the catch is the maintenance of cold temperatures in the fish muscles. Vessels that use ice to cool down their products before storing are simply not cooling their fish as efficiently as possible; as ice slurry is more efficient cooling medium. When fish at sea temperature enters a fishing tub or box full of ice, the ice starts to melt, leading to the fish being stored in water. Another factor to consider is that storage holds are not designed to cool products down, but to maintain even temperatures. If these things are misunderstood, temperature will rise in the storage hold. Research have shown that by pre-cooling products before going into temperature-controlled storage, their shelf life can be extended by 1-4 days (Martinsdóttir, et al., 2010).

Grading the catch according to species and size is important part of on board handling. In many fisheries it is a matter of legislation to keep species separate, but it is also important with regards to the processing to grade according to species and size. The correct species and sizes can then be transferred directly to the desired processing and production can be better planned. The grading is in most cases manual and can either be done by personnel on the processing deck during gutting or by the personnel in the hold during storing preparations. On board larger vessels it is common to send only the target species directly to the hold and store by-catches in purpose-built boxes on the processing deck, until all target catches from the haul have been handled.

When it comes to grading of UUC it will depend upon what products are going to be made from the raw material and what requirements will be set by the authorities with for example separation between catches intended for human consumption and non-human consumption. There may also be potentials for grading all materials intended for non-human consumption in one lot, as far as catches can be registered adequately by species.

When fish is brought down to the cargo hold, it should be placed in dedicated storage vessels. This can be in the form of specially made fish boxes, usually storing up to 50 kg of fish, or thermally insulated fish tubs of various sizes. As most vessels in Europe use fish boxes for storage of fish in the cargo hold, this will be used as an example in this chapter.

3.2 Handling of by-products and materials for non-human consumption

One of the main challenges involving the material handling on board fishing vessels of this size is how to deal with the material side streams; particularly those not meant for human consumption.

Handling this low value catches require considerable labour and space, both in regard to handling and stowage. The “best-practise” approach would probably be to treat these catches just the same as the target catches; but that is not really applicable in most cases, due to lack of space. An alternative that is relatively simple, requires little labour and space is to produce silage from these catches. Other side streams can then as well be used as raw materials for the silage e.g. viscera from target catches.

Silage preservation and/or production of fully prepared silage is one of the potential methods to reduce discards and waste in the marine industry today. The procedure is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra effort of employees compared to other methods. The raw material is acidified, which not only increases the shelf life of the material but allows it to be stored at room temperatures for more than a year with little reduction of quality. The latest trend in silage, and which has for example been practiced in Norway for considerable time, is to produce fish feed pellets out of thickened silage. The silage is thickened to about 50% dry matter contents and mixed with 40% binder such as alginate or guar gum to prevent disintegration of the pellets when they enter water. The benefits of this method are that the process requires much less energy compared to fishmeal pellets which are dried down to approximately 10% dry matter content. This results in much less heating and will contribute to equal or better quality. Silage production is not new despite its recent interest to reduce waste in the marine industry. It was first introduced in Finland in the 1920s to make green fodder using sulfuric and hydrochloric acid. Later, the method was adapted to whole fish and fish waste and production on industrial scale started in Denmark around 1950. At that time, Denmark produced about 15,000 tons a year in 14 companies. The Norwegian seafood industry is one of the largest producer of silage in the world today, producing large amounts annually, both from whitefish, pelagic species and the aquaculture industry. A total of 45% of their rest raw materials and unwanted catches in 2015 were utilized into silage as seen in Figure 10 (Richardsen, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016). One of the reasons why Norway has expanded into silage and has managed to implement it on the whitefish fleet as well, can be explained by the fact that silage processing facilities are relatively common all over Norway, due to its presence in the aquaculture industry. This makes easier access to the silage facilities for whitefish operators to land their rest raw materials (RRM) or their pre-made silage all year around.

Figure 10. Allocated Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Materials (RRM) used for production of by-products in Norway in 2015 (in tons) (Richardson, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016).

The implementation of silage production has been tried in other countries, such as Faroe Islands, Iceland and Denmark, with variable success.

On board silage production has been practiced in North-Atlantic fisheries for considerable time. It was installed on board a few Icelandic trawlers in and around 1980, but the production came to an end few years later, primarily due to design flaws and opposition from the fishermen. The Faroese silage industry is still in operation, but it is mostly considered as solution to disposal problems, rather than an industry that is supposed to return profits. The Norwegian silage industry has however kept growing, alongside the aquaculture industry. Many Norwegian trawlers are now equipped with specific units for producing preserved silage while other boats, such as the Norwegian freezer trawler Molnes, have taken it even further and produce fish oil and fully prepared de-oiled and thickened silage on board. Figure 11 shows both the freezer trawler Molnes and a silage solution from Steinsvik ltd. that fits into a 40" container.

Figure 11. The freezer trawler Molnes along with a Steinsvik ltd. system that can be fitted on board vessels for silage production (Steinsvik, 2018) (Nordic Wildfish, 2018).

The unit shown in the figure above can be fitted on board fishing vessels of certain size and it is almost completely automatic. It is however difficult to find a space for such a unit on board small and medium sized bottom trawlers and Danish seiners, even though the unit is quite compact. It is though in some cases possible, especially since the storage tanks can be located just about anywhere on the boat. Another alternative is to locate the silage unit in the port, so that many vessels can use the same facilities for silage production.

3.2.1 Silage production

The procedure of making and storing silage is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra labour effort for crewmembers, and all additional raw materials can be utilized for the production as well. The acidification of the silage increases the shelf life of the material which can be extended up to two years without little reduction of quality. Temperatures do not have to be reduced below zero degrees in the storage as is done with fresh materials or during transportation since the acid works as a preserver of the material, which is one of the big advantages of this method. When silage preservation is compared to other preservation methods such as freezing, cooling and/or maintaining material frozen or cooled through transport and in storage, the advantages of this low energy use becomes even clearer. The process of making silage is broken into the following steps.

Mincing

The mincing is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. A primary silage tank is used to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion and a secondary silage tank is then used to store the silage and maintain digestion. The equipment needed can be variable and is dependent on the raw material. Whole fish and pelagic species need powerful mincing before going into the silage tank, while viscera and offal require less. Small particles should not be any greater than 3-4 mm in diameter to get even distribution in the tank. Mincing is also carried out to activate enzymes that will, along with the acid, work on preserving and breaking down the material as well as ensuring even degradation of the material. One example of effective and powerful mincers are macerators, they suit perfectly for mincing of both whole fish and viscera. These mincers consist of two rotating wheels with blades, the wheels are located side by side and when the material catches into the blades it is shred apart through the wheels, an example of that can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Drawings of macerators, which make excellent mincers for silage production

These types of mincers are designed to handle material in different sizes without stopping the production. When big particles enter the blades, the mincer continues to shred the material at

lower speed. The size of the macerator needs, however, to be decided according to the size of the raw material (Arason & Harðarson, 1982).

Acidification

When choosing the type of acid used for the digestion, two possibilities arise, i.e. mineral acids and organic acids. The mineral acids that have been used include hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid, while the organic ones are mainly acetic-, propionic-, formate-, acetate- and propionate acids to name a few. In the beginning, when silage production was on the rise, the usage of mineral acids was more common. They are less expensive than their organic counterparts but involve at least one relatively large disadvantage. The mineral acids don't start to act as preservative mediums until their pH value is below 2.0, rendering the solutions made by those acids to be relatively strong. This requires the fishermen or the companies buying silage made by inorganic acids to neutralize them prior to making products. It has been suggested that adding 20-50 kg of chalk to a one ton of silage can neutralize the solution. However, when the chalk binds to the acid, precipitate salts are formed which are nutritionally undesirable.

For organic acids, this is not needed as their preservative action starts already at pH levels of 4.0. However, these acids are more expensive than the inorganic ones, but as silage made by those types does not require neutralization prior to processing they could be the favourable option. The most commonly used acid in silage production is the formic acid.

Handling acid on board a fishing vessel can introduce certain difficulties, if things are not carried out the right way. Acid of this concentration is highly hazardous if exposed to humans. The acid should therefore be stored in a closed system where there is no risk of leak or spillage. Crewmembers should never have to handle the acid on sea in other ways than pushing a button or opening valves. Another factor to consider is the corrosion properties of the acid. In this concentration it needs to be handled with extreme caution and acidity control is therefore critical. It is subsequently advised to install a computer-controlled system that monitors the silage and measures the correct amount of acid needed to be added. These systems will add more acid into the solution if the pH value is rising too much above the desired value. Vacuum pumps can then be used to circulate the silage from the bottom of the tank to the top, for the acidity to be uniform throughout the solution. The acid can also be added relative to the mass flow into the silage tank, thus the silage will be fully blended when it enters the storage tank. The amount of acid needed for production of silage is around 2-3% of 85% organic acid, or roughly 20-30 kilograms of acid per ton of raw material (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). This does, however, not apply for all species and raw material, since silage made of viscera and offal does not require as much acidification. The optimal approach is therefore to have computer control, like mentioned before, which doses acid according to volume added into the tank and temperature controls to ensure rapid digestion during the initial stages.

Pre-blending in tanks

Silage tanks are categorized into primary- and secondary silage tanks. The role of the primary silage tanks is to receive material from the processing line, blend it with acid by using automatic temperature and acidification control and to trigger the digestion. Adding primary silage tanks for blending of the material helps with creating uniform material for even digestion. The secondary silage tank is however meant to store and maintain digestion of the material. The breakdown of the silage is dependent on the concentration of the acid and temperature. A heater is therefore often used to increase the breakdown rate. It takes silage made of whitefish offal around two days to break down at temperatures around 20°C and five to ten days at temperatures around 10°C (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

The number and size of the silage tanks used for the acidification process on board fishing vessels is optional, the reason is that catch sizes vary between vessels. That is since silage production on sea is a batch production and is only run for a few hauls at a time. This is done to ensure as even breakdown as possible without investing in too many acidification tanks. The optimal approach would be to have a silage tank for each haul, but that would not be economically feasible.

There are a few elements that need to be considered in the design of the silage tanks. The tanks need to be designed without sharp corners and with smooth inner surface to eliminate the risk of infection from bacteria settling on the surface. The primary silage tanks need to be constructed with cone in the bottom for settling of unwanted particles as stones. These tanks can be constructed from normal construction steel (st37) if the temperature of the silage is under 18°C, since temperatures greater than 18°C can lead to corrosion of the steel. For temperatures up to 30°C and more, anti-corrosive stainless steel is required or even plastic material (Arason S. , 1994). It is recommended to use anti-corrosive material for the primary tanks since the fermentation process has an optimum temperature between 25°C to 30°C (Archer, Watson, & Denton, 2001). Mixing of the silage is essential to get even chemical composition. Mechanical stir could be considered but optimal approach is to have vacuum pumping for constant circulation of the material. If stirring is poorly done the silage can separate into three phases, a liquid protein soluble on the top, an aqueous soluble in the middle and small sediment of heavy and insoluble fragments at the bottom (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

Not all species are ideal for silage production. Shells of crustaceans are for example hard to process into silage and species with high urea content in the meat are not ideal for silage production either, such as sharks and skates. It is therefore best to categorize the UUC before using them into silage. The crustaceans can then be processed into other products, such as chitosan which is used in food supplements and as colour treatment in aquaculture.

The equipment needed for silage preservation can be purpose-built and adjusted according to the needs of each vessel i.e. catch volumes and the available space on board. The primary tanks are usually located where there is easy access, but the secondary tank is often located below where there is unused space, such as where there was previously fuel- or ballast tanks in the bottom of the ship.

Temperatures do also have to be considered when choosing locations for the silage tanks, as temperatures close to freezing point slows the digestion of the material. However, the digestion

does not have to be fully completed on board of the fishing vessel, since the main goal is to preserve the material for on-land handling. Temperatures in and around the silage tanks may therefore vary between 10-30°C without any problems. But, the higher the heat is the more digested material will be when landing occurs.

Silage designs

To further define between silage preservation and the process of making fully prepared silage, silage preservation is the process of only preserving the material for further processing while fully prepared silage has been thickened and de-oiled. For that reason, preserved silage is commonly sold directly into fishmeal plant or to animal feed producers while fully prepared silage can be sold as livestock- and aquaculture feed or to the fur industry. The fish oil can moreover be sold to feed producers.

Silage preservation

The silage preservation process can generally be broken into three main steps, shown in Figure 13. Firstly, mincing, which is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. Secondly, digestion in primary silage tanks to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion and thirdly the silage storage tank to store the silage and maintain digestion.

Figure 13. Processing streams and setup for silage preservation

After mincing, acid is added to the material into the primary day tanks to trigger the digestion, generally in the proportions 3,5% formic acid is used but other acid such as sulfuric acid can also be used (Arason S. , 1994). By having a primary silage tanks for blending of the material,

sometimes called day tanks, helps to create more even digestion and more uniform material. While the secondary silage tank, is however, meant to store and maintain digestion of the material. Regarding the blending of acid, it is advised to install computer-controlled systems that monitor the silage and measures the correct amount of acid needed to be added. These systems will add more acid into the solution if the pH value is rising too much above the desired value. Pumps can then be used to circulate the silage from the bottom of the tank to the top, for the acidity to be uniform throughout the solution. However, acid can also be added relative to the mass flow into the silage tank, thus the silage will be fully blended when it enters the storage tank.

Fully prepared silage and fish oil

It is possible to take the silage production process further, which allows for more value creation, but it also means increased investment cost and more complex processing. The end products coming from this process are fish oil and de-oiled silage. The fish oil can be sold directly to feed producers for example and the de-oiled silage is a marketable product that commonly sold to fishmeal factories, feed- or biofuel producers and to farmers as feed supplement or fertilizer. One of the major benefits of this process is that water is removed from the product making concentrated and de-oiled silage, which gives a product that is easier to store, takes much less space and is more valuable.

The production process is similarly to the silage preservation process to begin with. In the first stages, material is minced and then mixed thoroughly in one of the primary acidification tanks along with acid. The material is treated with temperature and acid control to enforce rapid and powerful start of the digestion. By optimizing all necessary conditions, such as temperature, acid control and other relevant factors, the silage can finish digesting in two days (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The secondary silage tank is therefore not necessary, since the digested silage can be utilized right away. Three primary silage tanks are needed, as full digestion takes two days. Once the silage is digested, it is sent through a heat exchanger where much of the water is removed from the silage. It then goes into a centrifuge, where the wet silage is separated into fish oil and de-oiled fish silage. The fish oil is then ready as a final product, but the de-oiled fish silage is sent into an evaporator where most of the remaining water is removed. The final de-oiled silage is then ready as a powder with very low water content, which takes relatively little space, is easy to store and has long shelf life. The processing steps are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Processing streams and setup for full silage production.

The ratio of oil in the de-oiled silage can be adjusted according to the buyer's requirement, as for example feed producers would want silage of specific oil content. Silage is normally priced by the fat and protein content. But there are a few other quality factors that can also influence the price. Higher fat content increases the risk of rancidity which reduces the shelf life of the silage.

3.3 The demonstration vessel

Figure 15 shows typical medium sized bottom trawlers within this fleet sector. To the left is Áskell EA, a 29-meter long, 9.2-meter wide, 362 GT bottom trawler from Iceland (photo: Jósef Ægir Stefánsson). To the right is Ocean Harvest PD, a 28-meter long, 8-meter wide, 349 GT UK bottom trawler (photo: Larry Smith).

Figure 15. Áskell EA and Ocean Harvest PD (photos: Jósef Ægir Stefánsson and Larry Smith).

The vessels used to demonstrate the suggested solutions for this fleet type is a 29-metre long and 9.2- meter wide bottom trawler; with a 952 hp engine.

When considering catch volumes and composition of the demonstration vessel, the catches of a typical medium sized Danish bottom trawlers operated in the North Sea and adjacent waters were used. The vessel has a capacity for landing approximately 25-30 tons of raw materials and their main species include demersal fish such as cod, haddock, hake, plaice, sole, Nephrops, etc. Discard rates in this fleet segment were logged at around 0.9% in 2014 and the main species discarded were reported to be thorny skate (55%), cod (14%) and grey gurnard (6%) (STECF, 2015). The average evisceration ratio is estimated to be around 10-12%, meaning that if the “discards” and viscera are used for producing silage, the raw material would translate to roughly 3-4 tons on each fishing trip.

The 3D drawings that eventually were made to visualize the solutions were made from 2D technical drawings obtained from SkipaSýn. These drawings can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16. An example of the 2D technical drawings obtained from SkipaSýn for the demonstration vessel

The solutions offered for this vessel for handling of main catches, as well as catches categorized as UUC and under MCRS focuses on placing the highest emphasis on handling as well as bleeding and cooling. The vessel as presented in 3D can be seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17. A demonstration of the 3D drawing made from the technical drawings from SkipaSýn

The catch is hauled on board from the rear of the vessel, from where it is released from the nets down to the reception. To limit impacts the fish might experience, it is recommended that the reception has some amount of seawater in it. From the reception, batches of fish are brought to the processing tables, where the crew bleeds and, when applicable guts the relevant species. Species as well as offal and viscera not meant for human consumption are to be transferred to the silage belt and ground to produce the silage solution. The processing deck can be seen in Figure 18.

Figure 18. The processing deck of the demonstration vessel. The silage line can be seen at the right side of the deck whereas the bleeding and cooling mechanism is seen in the bottom left.

A substantial advantage is presented by having bleeding/cleaning tank with controllable throughput rate that ensures first-in-first-out. Sufficient time in a bleeding tank with good circulation and water replacement should be around 10-15 minutes (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). There are a few such solutions available with for example special bucket conveyer belts or snails. On average, a system for this vessel would cost around 60 thousand EUR, with an extra 40 thousand EUR for a cooling equipment which acts as to chill the seawater used as the cooling medium for the fish. It can seem to be difficult to justify investment costs of the magnitude

presented for these solutions, but with the better material handling and increased freshness, it could be argued that the overall price increase during auctions might be 3-5%, thus substantially increasing the value of the catch on a yearly basis.

Based on average measured discard rates in 2014 for bottom trawlers in the North Sea (STECF, 2015) it can be estimated that about 1% of the vessel's catches will be UUC. It is though likely that this portion will decrease due to efforts that will be made to avoid catching UUC, following the implementation of the Landing Obligation. From available numbers, it can be estimated that the annual landings of a vessel of this type and size could be as much as 3,000 tons*, so UUC within a discard ban can be expected to be approximately 30 tonnes a year, which translates to 300-450 kg per fishing trip. For this, there need to be separate containers on the lower deck in the storage hold. Thorny skate will likely represent about ½ of the UUC, cod will be around 15% and grey gurnard, hake, dab and plaice around 5% each. Most of the skates and grey gurnard have been discarded because of low commercial value, whilst the other species have been discarded because of lack of quota and size limits (under MCRS/MLS). The simplest and probably the most economically feasible alternative for handling the UUC and under MCRS catch will be to have differently coloured boxes, which will be stored in specially allocated parts of the hold. This will not require any additional investments, apart from investing in few boxes/tubs. This part of the solution can be visualized in Figure 19.

Figure 19. The visualization of how the hold might be set up. The main species are categorized into boxes while other catch not meant for silage is sorted into the tubs. The silage storage container can be seen in the compartment in front of the hold.

It might also be possible to utilize the UUC for silage production in addition to the viscera. The raw material supplies for the silage production would then be, in addition to the 30 tons UUC, around

* 3,000 tons per year is an ambitious goal for vessel in this fleet category operating in the North Sea

300 tonnes of viscera (i.e. roe would be utilised, but all the rest of the viscera and offal would go to silage production, which is around 10% of total wet weight of the catches). The average volume of raw materials going to silage production would therefore be around 1200-1500 kg per normal fishing trip.

As there is considerable space on board a vessel of the size presented in this case study, the silage tanks could be divided into pre-silage and post-silage production units. The collection tank could be placed on the lower deck, in front of the cargo hold, as shown in Figure 19. When the fish goes into the mincer to produce the base for the silage, a solution of acid would be added in at the same time. The desired temperature would be from above 10°C, this leads to digestion time between 2-10 days determining on the temperatures. This would mean that the material would need further time to digest on-land before being utilised in most cases. The cost of the silage system, including instillation cost, is estimated to be 149 thousand EUR, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The installation cost of a high-grade silage production system.

Cost items	EUR
Mincer	45.000
Acidification equipment	4.000
Primary tank	7.000
Secondary tank	10.000
Conveyor belts	5.000
Vacuum pumps	15.000
Hoses, fittings and other miscellaneous	25.000
Instillation 6 persons for two weeks	38.000
Total cost	149.000

Given the above assumptions, it is estimated that the silage preservation will be operated at considerable losses on board this demonstration vessel, as shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. The estimated silage production from the raw materials and the revenues generated.

Raw material	Raw material (T)	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Minerals & other (%)	Acid addition (T)	Silage (T)	Silage (EUR)
UUC	30	75%	18%	4%	3%	1	31	6.654
Viscera & offal from target species	300	83%	10%	4%	3%	9	309	36.966
Total	330						340	43.620

Table 3. The estimated cost and revenue of a silage preservation system on board the demonstration vessel, based on the pre-given assumptions

	Silage preservation
Revenue	€ 43.620
Energy cost	€ 0
Chemical cost	€ 8.415
Labour Cost	€ 10.338
Other costs	€ 2.084
Variable cost	€ 20.837
Contribution margin	€ 22.783
Investment cost	€ 149.000
Loan payment	€ 13.622
Insurance	€ 3.320
Repairs	€ 1.660
Depreciation	€ 9.694
Fixed cost	€ 28.297
Tax (20%)	€ 0
Profit/Loss	-€ 5.514

There is a clear loss of having such a system on board for these types of vessels, even if all the raw material normally discarded is utilized. The fact is that silage preservation provides very low value, as much of it is still water that needs to be removed. The above-mentioned solutions are presented in technical drawings rendered in 3D and animated videos that are available on the DiscardLess webpage; along with a cost-benefit analysis tool that allows for a rough estimation on the return of investment for these vessel types, given the equipment that is provided in the example. The cost benefit tool does also allow for exploring different basic assumptions, e.g. catch volumes and catch composition.

3.4 Summary

Small and medium sized bottom trawlers and Danish seiners represent an important part of the EU fishing fleet, especially in the North Sea and adjacent waters. They take part in a mixed fishery where there are variable target species. Historically this fleet segment has had relatively high portion of UUC, consisting of choke species, under MCRS species and species of little or no commercial value. When it comes to identifying alternatives for improving on board handling for this fleet there are some general improvements that can be suggested that primarily refer to

improving bleeding, gutting, cleaning and chilling of the catch. But when it comes to identifying alternatives that are solely focused at the UUC, there are very few applicable options that can be identified. This fleet has very limited alternatives for handling UUC any differently from other catches, but because discard rates are for the most part low in this fleet category fishing in the North Sea, the recommended “best practice” solutions include to simply handle the UUC as any other catches and then store them in specially labelled (coloured) boxes/tubs that can then be diverted to the proper production upon landing. However, there is a possibility of installing silage production unit on board to deal with both viscera as well as some UUC, if preferable for any type of vessel. However, the prices for prepared silage are not high as there is not any considerable value added to the raw material. The initial investment cost is high compared to the revenues and the maintenance and operating costs outweigh the total profit generated. Therefore, putting silage preservation units on board these vessels will most likely result in overall losses.

4 Large bottom trawlers

Highlights of chapter

- Large fresh fish trawlers ranging between 40 and 80 meters in length represent an important part of the EU fishing fleet.
- This fleet is often engaged in mixed fisheries where considerable part of the catches are species of low- or no commercial value; and catches below MCRS can be significant.
- These vessels do often have available alternatives to properly handle and stow unwanted catches, by classifying, handling and stowing the catches in a manner applicable for the intended production channels.
- Good practice on board handling makes it possible to utilise the catches in as valuable products as possible e.g. pet food, pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals etc.
- Silage production and even Fish Protein Hydrolysis production are alternatives that are applicable for this fleet section. The economic returns of such processing are though marginal.

Large wetfish trawlers ranging between 40 and 80 meters in length represent an important part of the EU fleet. This type of vessels used to be quite common within Europe but have been decreasing in numbers for the past few decades. This is though still a sizable fleet, which is very efficient and accounts for a significant part of EU catches. The vessels are mostly fishing in deep waters targeting cod, haddock, hake, saithe, redfish, monkfish, plaice and other similar species. The setup on board these vessels can be quite variable, which is why the authors of this report have chosen a “demonstration vessel” to identify and discuss suggested solutions. The demonstration vessel is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20. A 50-meter long bottom trawler that is used as demonstration vessel for this fleet category

Vessels in this fleet sector are generally owned by big companies that operate several trawlers. Investment in technology has been relatively high as the companies have tried to optimise their operation and maximise profits. Automation level is relatively high and emphasis on utilisation and quality is high. The current on-board handling procedures and the available technology for maximising value and maintaining quality are therefore usually well in order.

4.1 On board handling

All catches need to go through the same on-board handling to maximise quality and extend shelf life. This applies to target catches as well as UUC, because making top quality products from second rate raw material is impossible. The main steps in the on-board handling of the catch are bleeding, gutting, cleaning, chilling, grading, storing and ensuring adequate traceability. There are a few exceptions when looking at UUC, as some of them are not intended for human consumption and do therefore not have to hold up to the same standards (Viðarsson, Iñarra, Pérez-Villarreal, & Larsen, 2016). Following is a short discussion on the main steps in on board handling of the catches on board large fresh fish trawlers.

Firstly, the catch must be brought on board the vessel in a manner that will not damage the fish or cause material deterioration of any kind. In this regard, it is important not to haul too large quantities at the same time on board to limit the fish getting squashed at the bottom of the cod-end.

After the fish is brought on board, the bleeding and gutting are essential to rid the fish of contamination bacteria which reduce the quality of the raw material (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). These bacteria start to grow at accelerated rates post rigor mortis and therefore all mediums in which they linger, such as blood and intestines must be removed to slow the deterioration process of the fish muscles during storage. For most lean whitefish species such as cod and hake, given adequate cooling and proper bleeding and gutting, the shelf life is 2 – 1½ weeks at most; and for fatty species such as mackerel and herring this time can dip down to only 1 – 1½ weeks. Another factor to consider is the iron content of the blood, as iron acts as an oxidation agent when exposed to oxygen and therefore it can have severe impact on the quality of the fish fillets, most noticeably in colour and taste. This is especially noticeable for fatty species, but the fat is quick to lose the freshness and rancidity grows exponentially. If gutting is not possible or cannot be done properly on board after the fish has been bled, it is best to leave that part of the process out until the catch has been landed. Improper gutting of the fish can often result in worse material quality due to spoilage bacteria and enzymes from the intestines making their way into the fish muscle post-improper gutting.

Washing should be done in seawater, which may be also chilled to speed up the chilling process. Simply immersing the fish for a few seconds is not enough time for the blood to completely drain from the muscles. For best results, the heart should still be beating when the fish is bled since then the heart acts as a pump which drains the fish quicker. Special bleeding tanks are advised for these

applications, thus immersing the fish for a few minutes after bleeding until it is gutted and sent through cooling.

Chilling and maintenance of unbroken chill-chain is extremely important, as it is a deciding factor on quality and shelf life of the catch. Cooling is generally either done with ice or slurry in boxes/tubs in the hold of the vessels; or with pre-chilling in purpose-built cooling tanks on the processing deck. It is vital that the chilling process does not take too long time and ideally the muscle should be close to the initial freezing point of water from the time it enters storage in the hold. The cooling in pre-chilling tanks can take up to an hour should it be done sufficiently, depending on size of the fish, throughput and cooling media. The temperature in fish that is only chilled with ice in the hold can take many hours to reach the desired 0°C depending on the quality of the icing. Amongst the risks associated with inefficient cooling is that if the catch is not chilled properly from the beginning, it will have the effects that the fish will go earlier and faster through rigor mortis, which will result in gaping and shortening of shelf life. The effects of fish going fast through rigor mortis is intermuscular loosening and the fish becomes slimy and undesirable.

Equally vital to proper cooling of the catch is the maintenance of cold temperatures in the fish muscles. Vessels that use ice to cool down their products before storing are simply not cooling their fish as efficiently as possible. When fish at sea temperature enters a fishing tub or box full of ice, the ice starts to melt, leading to the fish being stored in water. Another factor to consider is that storage holds are not designed to cool products down, but to maintain even temperatures. If these things are misunderstood, temperature will rise in the storage hold. Researches have shown that by pre-cooling products before going into temperature-controlled storage, their shelf life can be extended by 1-4 days (Martinsdóttir, et al., 2010).

Grading the catch according to species and size is an important part of on board handling. In many fisheries it is a matter of legislation to keep species separate, but it is also important with regards to the processing to grade according to species and size. The correct species and sizes can then be transferred directly to the desired processing and production can be better planned. The grading is in most cases manual and can either be done by personnel on the processing deck during gutting or by the personnel in the hold during storing preparations. On board larger vessels it is common to send only the target species directly to the hold and store by-catches in purpose-built boxes on the processing deck, until all target catches from the haul have been handled.

When it comes to grading of UUC it will depend upon what products are going to be made from the raw material and what requirements will be set by the authorities and potential buyers with for example separation between catches intended for human consumption and non-human consumption. There may also be potentials for grading all materials intended for non-human consumption in one lot, as far as catches can be registered adequately by species.

When fish is brought down to the cargo hold, it should be placed in dedicated storage vessels. This can be in the form of specially made fish boxes, usually storing up to 50 kg of fish, or thermally insulated fish tubs of various sizes.

4.2 Handling of by-products and materials for non-human consumption

Unlike with the other demonstration vessels discussed in this report, the on board handling procedures and available technology to optimise quality and utilisation of target catches have already been optimised. There are also a limited number of obstacles in the way of sorting MCRS catches and storing them separately from target catches intended for human consumption in the cargo hold for processing on-land. There are however not a lot of other plausible alternatives that can be identified to handle, store and utilise UUC on board this type of vessel. Having protein plants or fishmeal factories on board a vessel of this size is generally not considered realistically feasible, due to lack of space. Mincing the UUC to store fresh is also not an ideal option, as such products will have very short shelf life. It is however possible to install silage preservation or production units on board the vessel, and production of Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH) could even be an option. There may be some legal obstacles in the way of utilizing UUC into silage or other products which content cannot be easily identified upon landing, as mentioned earlier in this report. But it is nevertheless an alternative that is being used in fisheries outside CFP waters and should therefore be regarded as a potential option for EU vessels; particularly if reliable methods can be provided to monitor or confirm the content of the silage/material. Following is a discussion on four alternatives regarded by the authors as “most applicable” regarding handling of UUC on board larger fresh fish trawlers.

4.2.1 Classification of UUC for processing on-land

The simplest way of dealing with UUC on board large wetfish trawlers under Landing Obligation is to use the current setup. The only catches needing to be handled differently under the Landing Obligation are therefore catches under MCRS. Since under-MCRS catches cannot be utilised for direct human consumption there will be a need to separate between the two categories. It is relatively simple and inexpensive to separate between human and non-human consumption catches on the processing deck and in the hold. There are by-catch collection boxes located on the processing deck that can be used to store the UUC while the target catches are being processed; and the UUC can then be handled afterwards. A part of the hold can be boxed off for storing catches intended for non-human consumption and having differently coloured boxes or tubs for those catches will also be beneficial. The MCRS catches should ideally be sorted by species into the tubs, but it could also be an option to do the sorting during landing. Storing the UUC in the hold will naturally influence how much target catch can be fitted in the hold and might result in shortening of fishing trips, as the hold will fill up quicker. This should, however, not be a major problem as the vessel rarely came to port fully loaded prior to the implementation of the Landing Obligation. Discards have accounted for approximately 20% of catches in this fleet category (larger fresh fish trawlers operating in the NE-Atlantic, North Sea and adjacent waters) in the past. For the purpose of this study it, is assumed that 50% of the discards have been below MCRS and that the implementation of the Landing Obligation will contribute to 25% reduction in catches of below MCRS, due to improved size selectivity measures. This means that the below MCRS catches will account for 7.5% of total catches. That will translate to roughly 500 tonnes of MCRS catches a year for the demonstration vessel, which are likely to fetch a landing value of around 200 thousand EUR, if assuming average prices will be 0.4 EUR/kg. The added value will give good return on the required investment within months, as the only investment required will be in a few differently

coloured tubs and setting up movable panels in the hold to separate human and non-human consumption catches. However, given the above-mentioned assumptions, the added value will only account for 1.3% of the annual landing value and the on-board handling will add to the already busy schedule of the crew. Furthermore, in some instances, the space occupied by MCRS catches in the hold will result in shortening of fishing trips, which may lead to increased oil consumption as extra fishing trips will be needed to fill the quota. This alternative is therefore simple, inexpensive to implement and applicable in most aspects. However, it does require significant efforts from the crew and gives little economic incentive.

There is an option to install an automated size grader on the vessel and in some instances, it is even theoretically possible to have an automated species grader; but such a solution is not commercially available yet (except where catches include very limited number of species). These are, however, solutions that may not be permitted on board EU vessels, as they can enable automated high-grading. Automated size graders are nevertheless being used on board Norwegian, Icelandic and Faroese fishing vessels and there is currently no evidence to suggest that they have been misused to the extent of high-grading the catch. These are therefore solutions that should be considered as alternatives, even though current legislation may not permit their use.

In those cases where all catches that are sent through the processing line are of the same species, which is quite common when fishing in the NE-Atlantic, it is possible to have an automated grading system on board the vessel. These grading systems are for example being used on some Icelandic wetfish trawlers. An example of the equipment providers is Marel and 3X-Technology. The demonstration vessel has the system partly set-up, shown as stations 7 & 8 on Figure 23, later in this report. Station 7 would then be a belt weight that weighs each fish and decides to which batch it should belong. The fish goes then onto station 8 where it is diverted to the right batch according to the weight. Each batch is then ready to be sent down to the hold when the pre-decided batch size has been reached, which in the demonstration vessel's case would be 300 kg. Each tub will then contain the right amount of fish, which will all be of similar size. It is even possible to let the data follow the tub, given that the tubs are fitted with a microchip (RFID) and the crew down in the hold have handheld scanners to connect the chip to the data collected by the grader. During on-land processing the production managers will then have detailed information on the raw material they have and can scan each tub to see what is in it, as well as where and when it was caught etc. This is a system that has for example been partly in operation at FISK Seafoods, Gunnvör and HB Grandi in Iceland. This kind of size grading system would be very helpful in separating between MCRS catches and catches intended for human consumption, in addition to allowing for better production management after landing.

Species grading is currently at experimental stages, except where there are very few species in the catch, and there is probably some time until it will be a marketable solution for mixed species fisheries where there are 50-100 different species in the catch. There are already prototypes available that can separate between limited number of species, which can work in NE-Atlantic fisheries where species diversity is not that variable. Star-Oddi in Iceland, Marine Scotland in UK and CSIC in Spain are amongst the companies/institutions that have been working on using computer vision to identify species at sea, but this is a field that is still on its early stages.

The economic benefits of investing in size- or species graders are not that clear, as the manual grading does not carry a high investment cost for the vessel owners. It is a task that is simply a part of what the crew does on board the vessel. Improved grading, more uniformed batches and increased data availability are, however, factors that could potentially be of economic benefit for the vessel owners.

4.2.2 Silage preservation

A relatively simple way of handling the UUC is to make silage out of it for preservation purposes. The wet silage will then be sold as raw material for further processing upon landing. The raw materials used for producing the silage will consist of below MCRS catches, species not subjected to catch limits that would otherwise have been discarded and viscera/offal from target catches. The expected raw material used for silage preservation could be close to 1,000 tonnes, given that 50% of discards in the past have been below MCRS and that the implementation of the Landing Obligation will improve size selectivity by 25%. It is also assumed that all catches not subjected to catch limits will be used for the silage preservation (with the exception of the 20% size selectivity improvements and release of species that are not suitable for silage production, such as skates, dogfish and sharks) and that viscera/offal from target species (where applicable) will be used as raw material for silage (with the exception of roe and liver). These estimates are based on several “best available” assumptions, but it is clear that margin of error can be significant. The estimated raw materials for the silage preservation by main species/material group are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Estimated volumes of raw materials that can be used for silage preservation on the demonstration vessel under Landing Obligation.

Raw material	MCRS catches (T)	Species not subjected to catch limits (T)	Viscera & offal from target species (T)
Cod	38		170
Saithe	11		150
Redfish	150		
Whiting	113		40
Haddock	75		30
Atlantic Argentine	4		
Hake	55		0
Mackerel	38		
Ling	2		5
Flatfish species	1		
Wolffish	0		1
Tusk	0		0
Other	56	30	5
Total	542	30	401

The equipment needed for silage preservation of these materials is a simple equipment which nevertheless bears some initial investment cost. The processing capacity needed will be around

5-6 tonnes a day, given that the shortest full-load fishing trips will be 5 days and 15-20% of the catches will be used for silage preservation. Digestion in each primary silage tank is estimated to be around 24 hours and therefore it is required to have two primary silage tanks. They run separately to always be able to receive material. Required minimum size of each primary tank is therefore 6 cubic meters since density of silage is around 1.2 kilograms. The system has then a little extra capacity to use when catches are “abnormal”. The minimum required size of the secondary silage tank is then close to 30 cubic meters. The primary tanks can be located port-side next to the discard chute and the secondary tank can be fitted on a lower deck.

The cost of setting up this silage preservation system can vary depending on the equipment and manufacturers chosen. But given the specifications already discussed, the total cost of the silage preservation system could be around 170 thousand EUR, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Estimated costs of installing a silage preservation system on board the demonstration vessel

Cost items	EUR
Mincer	45.000
Acidification equipment	4.000
Primary tanks	14.000
Secondary tank	20.000
Conveyor belts	5.000
Vacuum pumps	15.000
Hoses, fittings and other miscellaneous	25.000
Instillation 6 persons for two weeks	38.000
Total cost	166.000

Estimating the potential added value from the investment can be difficult, as there are uncertainties about both future supplies of UUC and the price of silage. Basing estimates on future supplies under a Landing Obligation on data on discards where discards are permitted or required involves making assumptions that are questionable at best. The value of silage is also difficult to estimate, as it depends on protein and fat content, which varies considerably depending on species and time of year. Given that the estimates are correct, and it is assumed that all the extra raw materials are used for silage preservation, mass balance calculations can be used to estimate potential value of the silage. Silage in this form can be sold to fishmeal factories for further processing. The price is then decided based on how much fishmeal and fish oil can be produced from it, and a few quality parameters that decide what grade fishmeal and fish oil it will be. Given some assumptions regarding chemical composition of the UUC, the mass balance calculations suggest that the silage could be used to produce approximately 1,000 tons of silage annually, as shown in Table 6. This silage contains bones as well, which would have to be separated from the mix for further processing once landed on shore.

Table 6: Estimated volume of silage and its potential value for the demonstration vessel

Raw material	Raw material (T)	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Minerals & other (%)	Formic acid (T)	Silage (T)	Silage (EUR)
MCRS catches	542	73%	18%	8%	1%	16	558	120,213
Species not subjected to catch limits	30	75%	18%	4%	3%	1	31	6,654
Viscera & offal from target species	401	83%	10%	4%	3%	12	413	49,411
Total	971						1,002	176,278

Prices per ton of fishmeal and fish oil are dependent on many factors, but in this case, it is assumed that a fishmeal factory will buy the silage and produce from it low quality feed grade fishmeal and fish oil. Basing the estimates on world market prices of such fishmeal and fish oil and assuming that the fishmeal factory will buy the silage for 65% of the final end product value (which is a common practice in the fishmeal industry), it is estimated that the annual value of the silage will be close to 176 thousand EUR.

According to these calculations the payback time for the investment would be just under one year. These estimations are, however, based on many assumptions. The value could of course be lower or higher, but precautions have been made in the calculations to use only prices for low quality feed grade fishmeal and fish oil, whilst there are potentials to use the silage for more valuable fishmeal and oil.

The form of the silage is a factor regarding the process itself, as silage in which the moisture has been removed from results in higher prices. Allowing water to evaporate from the silage could therefore potentially increase the value.

4.2.3 Full on-board silage production

It is possible to take the silage production process further on board the demonstration vessel, which allows for more value adding. But it also means increased investment cost and much more complicated processes. The end products coming from this process are fish oil and de-oiled silage. The fish oil can be sold directly, for example to feed producers. The de-oiled silage is also a marketable product that can for example be sold to fishmeal factories, feed producers and to farmers as feed supplements or fertilizer. One of the major benefits of this process is that water and acid are removed from the final product de-oiled silage, which gives a product that is easier to store, takes much less space, has longer shelf life and is more valuable.

This production process is like the silage preservation process to begin with. In the first stages, material is minced and then mixed thoroughly in one of the primary acidification tanks along with acid. The material is treated with temperature and acid control to enforce rapid and powerful start of the digestion. By optimising all necessary conditions, such as temperature, acid control and

other relevant factors, the silage can finish digesting in two days (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The secondary silage tank is therefore not necessary, since the melted silage can be utilized right away. There might however be necessary instead to have three primary silage tanks, as full digestion takes two days. Once the silage is digested it is sent through a heat exchanger where much of the water is removed from the silage. It then goes into a centrifuge, where the wet silage is separated into fish oil and de-oiled fish silage. The fish oil is then ready as a final product, but the de-oiled fish silage is sent into an evaporator where most of the remaining water is removed. The final de-oiled silage is then ready as a powder with very low water content, which takes relatively little space, is easy to store and has long shelf life. The processing steps are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Processing streams and setup for full silage production on board the demonstration vessel

The investment cost of installing such a system on board the demonstration vessel is estimated at 340 thousand EUR, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Estimated costs of installing a full silage production system on board the demonstration vessel

Cost items	EUR
Mincer	45.000
Acidification equipment	4.000
Primary tanks	21.000
Heat exchanger	20.000
Centrifuge	50.000
Fish oil tank	4.000
Evaporator	20.000
Storage tank for de-oiled silage	25.000
Conveyor belts	5.000
Vacuum pumps	25.000
Hoses, fittings and other miscellaneous	25.000
Instillation (10 persons for three weeks)	96.000
Total cost	340.000

The ratio of oil in the de-oiled silage can be adjusted according the buyer's requirement, as for example feed producers would like to have some oil content in the silage powder. Silage is normally priced by the fat and protein content. However, there are a few other quality factors that can also influence the price. Higher fat content increases the risk of rancidity which reduces the shelf life of the silage.

Estimating added value of this investment depends on a few factors and can vary significantly depending on what assumptions are given. Given that raw material supplies are the same as in the previous silage preservation example and that all of the available fish oil is removed from the de-oiled silage, it can be expected that the volume of fish oil and silage powder produced will be similar as if the silage would have been otherwise processed in the fishmeal factory (see Table 6). Assuming same final prices as in that example i.e. world market prices for low quality feed grade fishmeal and fish oil, the added value of the investment would be around 300 thousand EUR a year. The difference being that the fishing vessel would get the full final value of the products, instead of selling silage to a fishmeal factory at 65% of final value. The payback time for the investment would therefore be little over a year, not considering the share of the crew in the landing value or the production costs.

The Norwegian freezer trawler Molnes was recently equipped with a full on-board silage production system. This was a part of a major renovation that was done on this 66-meter-long and 14-meter-wide whitefish trawler. The vessel has only been in operation for limited time, but they have not run into any major problems with the system yet and the products have been favourably received by their customers (Roaldsnes, 2016). The experience gained by Molnes will give valuable insight into the applicability of having full silage production systems on board fishing vessels.

4.2.4 Fish protein hydrolysate

Producing Fish Protein hydrolysate (FPH) on board fishing vessels is an alternative that could be considered plausible, even though the process can be quite complicated and requires using hazardous materials, such as acids and enzymes. FPH in its simplest form is minced fish, viscera and offal which are processed and separated down to three streams. The first one being FPH which is protein rich powder. The second one is cake which consists of bones and skin. Finally, there is the third stream of fish oil. The aim of FPH production is to produce material with high protein content, therefore whole demersal fish is most favourable since it is relatively high in protein and with a controllable level of fat. Species higher in fat content such as pelagic species will need further processing to remove oils before being processed into FPH. That is done to prevent strong fishy flavours of the material.

The UUC of the demonstration vessel are excellent raw materials for FPH, as they are high protein and relatively low in fat. But as with the silage production there are some legal barriers for implementing this solution now in the EU fleet, since CFP landing regulations require full traceability of all catch under MCRS and UUC. Blending of these parts of the catch with viscera and offal, as well as with species not subjected to catch limits could therefore be problematic.

The first steps of producing FPH are quite like silage production. The material needs to be minced before it goes into the digestion tank to increase the surface area of the material and to promote uniformity. Unlike during silage production, enzyme microbial starters are added along with the acid to accelerate proteolysis and the breakdown of proteins down to ammonia acids. The blending tank needs to be equipped with stirring of some kind to get uniform material throughout the digestion. It can either have a built in mechanical stir or vacuum pump to ensure circulation in the tank.

The digestion of the material is controlled by acidity (pH), temperature, proteolytic activity, reaction mixture and the protein percentage (Archer, Watson, & Denton, 2001). To control the digestion, the most common approach is to add acid along with enzymes while temperature control speeds up the process. The material is digested at temperatures around 50-55°C which shortens the digestion time down to about 30 minutes. Enzyme microbial starters are deactivated by heating the material up to 70-75°C. This procedure can be carried out in the digestion tank where heat elements or heat exchangers control the temperature. The heating also promotes better conditions for sieving since the material is warmer where oils and liquids separate more easily from the mass.

When the enzymes have finished digesting the material and proteins have broken down into amino acids, the liquefied proteins are drained off and filtered by a sieving procedure. This procedure separates digested material into two streams. The former part consists of proteins and oils and the latter is cake, consisting of bones, skin and other particles. This cake is well suited for further utilization such as in a fishmeal factory or it can be utilized into fertilisers. Drum sieves are well suited for this process, the drum spins as the liquefied soluble particles are forced out of the drum and form liquid with high fat and protein content. After the sieving, the soluble particles are separated into oils, liquefied protein and cake. This is conducted with a dual stage centrifuge. The first centrifuge separates cake from the soluble material and the second one separates the

material down to FPH and Fish oil. The on board drying of FPH is optional since the procedure is highly energy demanding. The drying is usually conducted with spray, drip or freeze dryers. The processing steps in producing FPH are shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Processing streams and setup for FPH production

As in the silage production the material streams can be adjusted with the aim of increasing the final value. The degree of processing can also be selected as a two-stage centrifuge would not be considered necessary except to get clearer fish oil.

FPH is most commonly used in animal feed and is particularly sought after in aquaculture and pet food production. High-grade FPH are also increasingly being used for producing fish protein powders, which are then used as additives for making food supplements, functional foods and nutraceuticals, as an example.

Estimating costs and benefits for this kind of processing is difficult, as it has not been attempted before, as far as the authors of this report are aware of. This suggested alternative for on board handling of UUC is therefore purely theoretical. The complexity of the process and the fact that dangerous chemicals are being used in the process do also raise concerns. The potential value addition is also very uncertain, as FPH have enormous price range, depending on quality. Prices can as example easily vary from 1,000 EUR to 6,000 EUR per ton.

4.3 The demonstration vessel

The trawler selected to demonstrate suggested solutions is a 51-meter-long and 12.8-meter-wide wetfish trawler with a 2,400 hp engine that is mostly operated in the North-East Atlantic Ocean, as shown in Figure 20. The trawler has a crew of 14 persons and the average fishing trip is around 6 to 8 days. Their main target species are cod, saithe, redfish, whiting and haddock and the total discard rates have been estimated at 21% in recent years, indicating that there are significant

volumes of UUC that needs to be handled. The trawler has a large refrigerated storage hold which is rarely full; so UUC catches and fish under MCRS could therefore be landed in a traditional way without reducing the fishing capacity of the trawler.

This specific trawler chosen focuses mainly on deep-sea areas in the North-Western Waters, North-Sea, West of Scotland and goes occasionally as far north as the Norwegian Sea, Jan Mayen and Barents Sea. The vessel has a crew of 14 persons working on six-hour shifts. The length of the fishing trips depends on catch volumes, the location of the fishing grounds and where the catch is landed. The average fishing trip is, however, somewhere around 6-8 days, but the longest trips can stretch up to two weeks when fishing on grounds further away. The number of fishing trips per year can vary but they are usually about 60 trips per year. The refrigerated hold can store around 150 tonnes of catches, but the vessel is rarely full when landing. Annual catches can fluctuate a little between years and the catch composition does also vary, but total landings are generally somewhere around six or seven thousand tonnes, consisting mainly of cod, saithe, redfish, whiting and haddock. The annual landing value of the vessel is typically around 15 million EUR. Discard rates for the vessel have been around 20%, consisting mainly of species under MCRS and choke species. Table 8 shows the average annual catch composition by main species and estimated discards prior to the implementation of the Landing Obligation.

Table 8. Average annual landings and estimated discards of the demonstration vessel.

Species	Catches (T)	Landings (T)	Discards (T)	Discard rate
Cod	1.800	1.700	100	6%
Saithe	1.530	1.500	30	2%
Redfish	1.500	1.100	400	27%
Whiting	700	400	300	43%
Haddock	500	300	200	40%
Atlantic Argentine	310	300	10	3%
Hake	150	3	147	98%
Mackerel	100	0	100	100%
Ling	55	50	5	9%
Flatfish species	13	10	3	23%
Wolfish	13	12	1	8%
Tusk	3	3	0	0%
Other	350	200	150	43%
Total	7.024	5.578	1.446	21%

The current on-board handling of the materials is standard to a ship of this size and operation. When the catch arrives on board it is released from the trawl down to the reception unit. From there it is fed onto a conveyor belt to the processing line. The processing depends on which species are being caught, as some species can be sent directly down to the hold, whilst others need to be bled, gutted and cleaned. Redfish is for example not bled or gutted and cannot be sent through cleaning stations designed for the other catches, because it will then lose colour and as a result, be downgraded in price. Figure 23 shows how one of the processing lines (red arrow) bypasses the gutting and cleaning stations and goes straight to the grading station (8) and goes from there

down to the hold (9) where the fish is arranged and iced into 460 litre tubs, which hold around 300 kg of fish each. On its way the crewmembers remove the under-MCRS catches and other UUC and discard it through the discard chute (13).

Figure 23. The processing line in the demonstration vessel (1. Reception unit - 2. bleeding/gutting/sorting station - 3. Collection boxes for by-catches - 4. Gutting machine - 5. Bleeding in fresh sea water - 6. Pre-cooling in RSW - 7. Measuring & monitoring - 8. Sorting - 9. Hatch down to hold - 10. Access panel to the hold for landing the catches - 11. Storage for liver and roe - 12. RSW reservoir tank - 13. Discard chute.

Most catches must be bled and gutted. Mixed catches do therefore go from the reception (1) to the bleeding and gutting stations (2). Main target catches are after bleeding and gutting sent to the bleeding/cleaning- and pre-cooling tanks (5 & 6), but by-catches are stored in collection boxes (3) where they wait in RSW until the target catches from the haul have been taken care of. UUC, MLS, viscera and offal are sent on conveyor belts to the discard chute (13), except for roe and liver that go on different conveyor belts leading to a special storage box intended for such materials (11). The automated gutting machine (4) is sometimes used, particularly when mainstay of the catches is small saithe, but manual gutting is preferred because of quality concerns. Each fish is in the bleeding/cleaning tank for 5 minutes, where there is good circulation of fresh seawater. The fish goes from the bleeding/cleaning tank to the pre-cooling tank (6) where RSW cools the catch down to approximately 0°C in 30 minutes. The RSW used for the collection boxes (3) and pre-cooling tanks come from the slush reservoir tank (12) which is fed by slurry Ice machines located in the engine room. After pre-cooling the fish is sent to sorting and grading station (7 & 8) where there is an option to sort the catch by species and size. That sorting can be programmed so that each lot is divided into 300 kg portions, which then fit into one tub in the hold.

As discussed earlier, there are a number of solutions available for vessels of this size to meet with requirements of the Landing Obligation. Following is a suggestion for the demonstration vessel, that would allow for utilisation of all catches. In general, the setup is designed to make sure that best-practice handling is guaranteed for all relevant catches as well as to provide viable options

for UUC and catch under MCRS that will be realistic of most trawlers of this size. The catch is brought in from the reception onto a main conveyor belt placed in the middle of the deck, as shown on Figure 24. The crewmembers are located on each side and perform sorting, bleeding and gutting of the fish. Target species that need to be bled and gutted are drawn from the main conveyor, processed and placed on either of the two conveyors leading to the bleeding and cooling units. Viscera and offal that are left over at the gutting station are transferred into slides located under each gutting board and to a conveyor that leads to the silage mincer. Other parts such as liver and roe can be sorted into specific holes in the gutting table before being transferred in pipes to storage tubs located in the hold. This arrangement allows for 100% utilisation of all catches and ensures that nothing goes to waste.

Figure 24. Overview of the production deck. No. 1: The main conveyor, No. 2: Gutting board, No. 3: Bleeding tank, No. 4: Rotary cooling tank, No. 5: Automatic sorting unit, No. 6: Main conveyor (no bleeding or gutting), No. 7: Sorting tubs for under-MCRS, No. 8: Silage mincer, No. 9: Silage storage tanks, No. 10: Slurry ice buffer tank.

One of the advantages of this setup is that fish species such as redfish that are not bled, gutted or cooled can be conveyed directly down to the hold on the main conveyor. This eases the handling when redfish is caught in large volumes as workers won't have to lift or transfer large amount fish between conveyor belts. The reason for redfish not being treated as cod and saithe and sent to bleeding and cooling is due to buyer's requirement of redfish.

The sorting takes place on the gutting station, where UUC and fish under MCRS can be sorted into specific temporary-storage tubs for later processing or sent directly with the viscera into silage processing, as shown on Figure 25. These tubs are filled with slurry ice, as they may have to stay there for some amount of time before being processed. When it comes to processing these catches, the bottom plate of the tubs is raised, and fish brought up on the conveyor belt for processing. These tubs are also used for other target species that are caught in small volumes.

Figure 25. On the left, silage mincer and the silage conveyor. In the middle is the gutting and sorting station with the main conveyor in the middle, gutting tables with holes in them and sorting tubs on the sides. On the right side is the slurry ice buffer tank.

These recommendations are presented as an alternative over the status quo scenario with the knowledge of the fact that some legal issues should be addressed. There are however examples from within EU where vessels have been granted permission to produce silage on board (Fiskeritidende, 2016).

The first stage of the silage production is to gather the raw material. Slides are located under each gutting station so that crewmembers can throw in viscera, offal's, UUC and fish under MCRS. These slides lead down to a conveyor belt which feeds the material to a mincer. The mincer shreds the material apart and feeds it forward with the help of a pump into the primary silage tanks. In these tanks, commonly referred to as day tanks, formic acid is mixed in proportions with the raw material and heated up to 25-30 °C to speed up the digestion and to create a more uniform product. Each tank has a pump for constant circulation of the material to prevent settling of bones and other particles.

When the material has been kept in these conditions for approximately 24 hours it is pumped into a storage tank, which can be located at any place where space can be found and so that they are easily cleaned and emptied. Taking into consideration the expected catches of this vessel, the day tanks should hold 6 cubic meters each and the storage tank approximately 30 cubic meters. These two tanks, both the primary as well as the storage tanks can be seen in Figure 26. The variability in catches and catch composition within this fleet segment is considerable and the suggested solutions presented are therefore only a few of many alternatives.

Figure 26. The primary silage tanks (top) and the storage tanks (bottom).

As the vessel is equipped with a highly automated system prior to the Landing Obligation and the suggested solution of putting all previously discarded material to silage production, it is financially difficult to justify going for a silage option on the revenues alone. The equipment purchase is expensive but varies depending on how far into the process the raw material is brought on board the vessel. For a full silage production with evaporators, a cost of around 300-340 thousand Euros should be expected for installation of this equipment. However, this cost might be halved if only a silage preservation system is installed with no additional material processing. Despite that fact, the revenues generated by selling silage when on shore are not high and the payback period is therefore longer. This can be further seen in Table 9, where the revenues from producing preserved silage on board are shown. The initial investment cost for a system like this is relatively low while at the same time producing a profit annually.

Table 9. The estimated costs and revenues from producing silage in preservation units on board the demonstration vessel.

	Silage preservation
Revenue	€ 176,278
Energy cost	€ 0
Chemical cost	€ 24,812
Labour Cost	€ 41,778
Other costs	€ 7,399
Variable cost	€ 73,988
Contribution margin	€ 102,290
Investment cost	€ 166,000
Loan payment	€ 13,622
Insurance	€ 3,320
Repairs	€ 1,660
Depreciation	€ 9,694
Fixed cost	€ 28,297
Tax (20%)	€ 14,799
Profit/Loss	€ 59,195

For some vessels of this size, it might be possible to go into a fully prepared silage and fish oil production which might in turn give off a higher profit, but it is unlikely that is the case for most of the vessels in this size category, especially if they were not designed for that purposes to begin with. This equipment takes up a lot of space and as can be seen in the figures above, there is already very little space left for any extra equipment to be fitted on the processing deck.

4.4 Summary

The vessel demonstrated in this chapter is already at a relatively advanced state when it comes to on board handling. The solutions suggested in this chapter for the demonstration vessel have therefore primarily focused on how to deal with UUC that will have to be brought ashore to meet with requirements of the Landing Obligation. The discard rate in this fleet category is relatively high compared to other vessels previously presented in this report, as discards are estimated to represent 20% of catches. The catch composition can be quite variable, including many species and sizes. It is suggested that most catches will just be handled as before, and that the catches intended for non-human consumption will be used for silage production. There are, however, variable advanced versions of silage production available and subsequent processing depends largely on what kind of space the trawlers have to accommodate the mechanism on board. The

equipment presented for the demonstration vessel is a simpler silage preservation system, as the system that produces fully prepared (thickened and de-oiled silage) takes up considerably more space and is quite expensive.

5 Large factory trawlers

Highlights of chapter

- Despite their limited number, factory trawlers represent a big part of EU catches, particularly in distant waters.
- This fleet is often engaged in mixed fisheries where considerable part of the catches are species of low- or no commercial value; by-products or rest raw materials from the processing can be significant and catches below MCRS can represent a big part of the total catches.
- These vessels have opportunities for processing or freezing unwanted catches, but the freezers and storage in the hold are often limiting factors; and processing catches of human and non-human consumption does generally not go well together.
- Fishmeal and fish oil, as well as silage or Fish Protein Hydrolysate production are alternatives that can be applicable for this fleet type; and under the right circumstances should be economically feasible.

Factory bottom trawlers or freezer trawlers represent a relatively small part of the EU fleet in number of vessels, but it is an important sector when considering catch volumes and values. Vessels in this sector fish mostly far offshore, on fishing grounds that many other vessel types are unable to fish such as high-seas, Barents sea, waters of third countries where the EU has negotiated Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) and deep waters far away from the nearest ports. These factory vessels range in size from 60 – 150 meters, have a crew of 25 up to 100 persons and can stay out at sea for months. Some factory trawlers only dock when needing service, such as engine maintenance and keel cleaning; landing their catches via transshipment. Figure 27 shows the 70-meter long factory vessel, Sólberg ÓF.

Figure 27: Factory trawler (photo: Rammi)

The main processes on board factory bottom trawlers involve, as the name suggests, making fully processed frozen products out of the raw material. The fish is brought down to the processing deck where it is bled, gutted, beheaded and washed before being either frozen immediately as H&G (Headed and Gutted) or transferred to filleting and trimming. The fillets are then placed into plates or pans, from where they are passed into the freezers. Normally, the freezers are contact freezers, using two plates to pressure the fish in between whilst removing the heat from the raw material. The freezing time is much quicker this way, as heat removal is accelerated through conduction, rather than using convection. The freezing rate is important as to limit the damage of the raw material as much as possible but research has shown that inadequate freezing in the form of either slow freezing rate or not fully frozen products can result in larger ice crystals forming within the muscle of the fish, lowering water retainability and quality once thawed (Burgaard, 2010). Frozen blocks are then transferred to the storage hold to be stored until landing. It is important to maintain the storage temperature as stable as possible but fluctuations in temperature for frozen products influence the growth of ice crystals within the muscle, reducing quality (Gutiérrez, Oliveira, Melo, & Silveira Júnior, 2017). There are also some factory trawlers that produce more consumer facing products, such as IQF (individually quickly frozen) fillets or portions, or frozen portions in consumer packages.

With regards to the side streams from the main material processing, there is currently not much done to reduce discards of UCC on board factory trawlers. There are however a considerable number of alternatives available for dealing with these materials or side streams; which are identified and discussed in the following sub-chapters.

5.1 Handling of by-products and materials for non-human consumption

Due to the space available on board large factory trawlers, there are possibilities for processing different products from UUC on board such vessels. Utilization of by-products is however generally relatively low on-board factory trawlers which may, to some extent, be traced to the on-board conditions for storing and processing these secondary material streams. Their main alternative for utilisation of by-products is to freeze them and stow in the same hold as the main products. This is fairly simple when dealing with cut-offs and minced materials, but by-products such as liver, heads and roe are more complicated, as freezing such materials requires installation of separate freezers; since contamination from by-products can affect the quality of the fillets which are the main products. Most factory trawlers are equipped with contact freezers which makes it difficult to freeze parts such as fish heads. This results in longer freezing time which may affect the freezing capacity of the trawler and is often the bottleneck of the processing (Jónsson & Viðarsson, 2016). Another barrier is that these by-products take up valuable space in the hold which could be utilized for more profitable products such as fillets. Some of the largest factory vessels do however have fishmeal factory's on board, where all UUC, heads, frames and cut-offs are utilised for fishmeal and fish oil production.

Among the options most applicable to meet with the requirement of the Landing Obligation (at least in short term) are for example sophisticated designs of either silage or full fishmeal processes. These alternatives are further explained in the following sub-chapters.

5.1.1 Fishmeal and fish oil production

Offshore fishmeal plants, commonly named compact fishmeal plants, have gotten increased attention lately in connection with changes in mentality towards utilisation and elimination of discards. These plants have been designed and installed to take up little space, be simple and easy to operate along with being affordable. Despite its recent interest, these plants have been around and on-board processing vessels for more than 40 years. However, the disadvantages of these older plants are often considerably low efficiencies as the press cake is an absolute priority in these plants and press liquor is often discarded to the sea with all the oils and protein within. Thus, it can only produce fishmeal out of the press cake discarding the oils and excess protein source into the ocean. The press liquor contains valuable compounds such as proteins, oils, minerals and vitamins that can weigh up to 20-40% of the total fishmeal produced, depending on the raw material (FAO, 1986). Considerable development has taken place in design of equipment such as cookers, decanters, tricanter and centrifuges in recent years, which has resulted in more advanced solutions that are better adapted to the needs of the customer. An example of traditional compact fishmeal plant can be seen in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Compact conventional offshore fishmeal plant without oil processing. Main components are mincer, screw cooker, twin screw press and indirect steam dryer. (FAO, 1986)

The main principles of fishmeal and fish oil processing can be seen in Figure 29. Even though offshore fishmeal plants can be designed where some steps are diminished or simplified, these are the main processes.

Figure 29 Main processes of onshore production of fishmeal and oil.

Mincing

When the fish has been processed, the raw material is brought onto a conveyor belt which leads to a large hopper (FAO, 1986). The hopper is constructed with a feeding screw at the bottom which allows for even input of raw materials into the plant. The input stream needs to be controlled according to the output flow as the production is continuous. The feeding screw feeds the material into a mincer which evenly tears the material into the right particle size. This is however dependent on the raw material as whole fish requires mincing while other materials such as offal's should preferably not be minced. One type of mincers commonly used is the knife hasher. It consists of a rotor with staggered knives and a frame with a row of stationary knives. There is a wide variety of mincers available, but the most important thing is the particle size.

Heating

The heating process is carried out to extract the oils and moisture from the material for better sieving as well as to inactivate bacteria, viruses and parasites that can ruin the material. The temperature of the heating process has gained increased discussion in the past decade as research has shown that the fat cells are broken down before the temperature reaches 50 °C (Ruiter, 1995). Another research has shown that coagulation of proteins occurs around 75 °C quite rapidly (FAO, 1986). Inactivation of viruses, bacteria and parasites within the fish is another factor that needs consideration in relation to temperature and residence time. According to Nygaard (2010), the minimum duration time required in cookers is at least 20 minutes at temperatures above 70 °C for wild minced fish. This will ensure that viruses, bacteria and parasites will be successfully inactivated after that time. This indicate that the heating procedure should be conducted around 75 °C for 20 minutes to ensure optimal results. And theoretically there should be no reason to heat the material above that as has been done for centuries in the industry, where optimal temperature has been considered 100 °C (FAO, 1986). It should although be mentioned that the temperature is also dependent upon the components within the plant as some separators require more heating of the material. Higher temperatures can also be used to ensure rapid temperature increase.

Heating above 75 °C can therefore be accepted in some cases. In addition, the residence time described earlier does not have to be conducted entirely in the heater as the material travels into the dryer, evaporators or heat exchangers where the deactivation can also be conducted. Moreover, higher temperatures are commonly used to accelerate the heating.

Most common cookers used in the fishmeal industry are steam or water heated. The steam can be retrieved from electric or fuel steam kettles, excess condensate steam or material vapor from dryers or evaporators.

Pre-cookers are commonly used in the onshore processing of fishmeal. They are often powered by excess steam or condensate from the evaporators or other equipment to contribute to better energy efficiency. It moreover reduces the steam needed in the main cooker, as the material is often around 40-50 °C after the preheating (Arason S. , 2001). Pre-cookers are often cylindrical pipe heat exchangers and the material is either pumped through the heated pipes or with screw in the middle to feed the material. The screw also helps with blending of the material and makes the material more uniform. The risk with the preheating is however increased viscosity in the press cake and stick water due to slow heating. The excess heat source is commonly not hot enough to contribute to rapid heating (Arason S. , 2001).

Conventional screw cookers (Figure 30) are undoubtedly the most common cookers used in the fishmeal industry. The cooker is equipped with steam heated jacket and heated screw in the middle to feed the material and to increase the heat transfer. A common design is to have the heat surface in the proportions 60% screw and 40% jacket (Arason S. , 2001).

Figure 30 Conventional screw cooker from Fjell (AMOF Fjell, n.d.).

Figure 31 Contherm apparatus in cross sectional view (Process Cooling, 2001).

Contherm apparatus (Figure 31) is one type of pipe heat exchanger. They are commonly used as pre-heaters but can also serve as main cookers with multiple units connected in series. They are constructed as normal pipe heat exchangers with steam heated jacket which ensures heat transfer to the material. In addition, they are constructed with rotating blades inside that evenly scrape the contact area to prevent formation of burnt material. It moreover ensures effective heat transfer as the material is continuously in motion. Widespread practice is to recirculate stick water that has already been separated from the mass to accelerate the heat transfer. Contherm

apparatus have gained increased popularity in the fishmeal industry; they are compact, require less space and are designed to be able to receive excess heat sources such as vapor. Their rapid heating results in shorter holding time which reduces viscosity. They are moreover simple to operate as well as being easy to clean and maintain (FAO, 1986) and they have high transfer rates which can be controlled by the rotational speed (Earle & Earle, 1983).

Straining

After the heating, oils and most of the water is released and can therefore be removed to a large extent by strainer. The goal is to increase the compression of the press cake and the material entering the press becomes porous with open channels in the material for drainage of liquids. The material is separated down to two streams; press liquor and wet press cake.

The straining procedure is conducted to increase the compression of the material before pressing, promoting lower moisture and oil content. Straining is most often conducted after the heating procedure where oils and water are more soluble. Removing liquor and oils earlier in the process will ensure better pressing and less energy needed to dry the considerably wetter material (FAO, 1986).

Conveyor strainer consists of a porous conveyor belt which feeds the material towards the press while draining oil and liquids through the belt. Other strainers such as screw strainers feed the material towards the next process and have porous frame at the bottom which leaves the liquid through. These strainers are most often constructed in an upward slope (Arason S. , 2001).

Vibrating strainer is powered by motor and rotating shaft which creates vibration. The material is fed to a downward sloped porous plate and the vibration forces the material downwards while the liquids fall through (Arason S. , 2001).

Rotating strainers can be of two types. One of them has a horizontal cylindrical drum which is rotated. The material is fed in by the other side of the drum, liquids are extracted through the drum with rotational force while the solid cake goes through the other end (Arason S. , 2001). The other type consists of a circular plate that is rotated. The material is brought to the centre of the porous circle and spins to the outer surface and is scraped of while the liquids are drained through the bottom (FAO, 1986).

Pressing

After the straining process the wet press cake is fed into a press which squeezes the rest of the liquids out of the material. The press cake is then ready for drying while the press liquor goes into further processing or is discarded into the ocean.

Screw presses are standard component in the fishmeal industry. The most common is the twin-screw press (Figure 32) but presses with one screw are also available. The compression ratio of these presses is dependent on the material and the processing methods. Under average on land condition one may estimate 70% stick water and 30% press cake in the press liquor coming from the press (FAO, 1986).

Figure 32 Twin screw press from Stord, the inlet is at the right side and outlet on the left (ATI Group, n.d.)

Twin screw press consists of two screws that rotate in opposite direction. The structure of the press ensures that the material is pressed and does not rotate along with the screw. The already strained material is fed into funnel which evenly feeds the material into the press. The two rotating screws grab the mass forcing them against each other. The further the material goes into the press the pressure increases and the porous plate at the bottom drains the liquid. In the front, these plates have larger mesh size which decreases further into the press, the space becomes tighter thus forcing liquid and oils out. The desired compression can be controlled by the size of the screw blades and the axles. These parameters must be controlled according to the raw material as less pressure is needed during pressing for material rich in solutes compared to material with high dry matter and with fibres. The press volume ratio in most fishmeal plants is 1:4-5 which is the ratio between inlet and outlet. This ratio indicates the pressure ratio in the opposite end of the press (Arason S. , 2001). These factors must be determined carefully with professionals.

Decanter centrifugation of solids

Decanter centrifuges are used to remove solid particles from the press liquor. They have gained increased attention as replacement for the main screw press in smaller fishmeal plants (Gíslason, et al., 2014). This presents both advantages and disadvantages for the whole production. Firstly, using decanter centrifuges simplifies the process, they are compact, with more controllable separation as presses and sieves, faster separation, reduced head load on the material, promote better hygiene and easier cleaning of the components. Most important though is their ability to process soft and very fluid material, but here is where the press would fail. However, they have their disadvantages as well, which is press cake with higher moisture content and more soluble fines in the stick water which calls for more intensive separation of oils. Higher moisture content will moreover lead to higher energy consumption in the dryer (FAO, 1986).

In practice, there are two types of decanter centrifuges; the two phase, which leaves liquid and solid and three phase which leaves liquid, solids and oil. Even though this section is called

decanter centrifugation, other separation methods could be well suited for this section, as vibration screen or other sieves. Centrifuges or so called horizontal decanters are however considered more effective (FAO, 1986).

Two phase horizontal decanter centrifuges (Figure 33) use rotational forces that can be over 3,000 times greater than the force of gravity. They are constructed as a horizontal cylinder with a bowl in one end where the solid phase is collected and discharged and with a rotational screw/scroll conveyor in the middle to feed the solid phase further into the bowl. The sludge is brought in at the opposite end through piping and enters the cylinder in the middle.

In theory, the larger solid particles with higher density are pressed outwards against the rotating bowl in the end of the centrifuge under the force of gravity. Meanwhile, the less dense liquid forms a concentric inner layer which expels towards the liquid outlet. Thus, the solids are pressed into the bowl and liquid in the opposite direction due to rotational forces. This can be obtained by the bowl shape at the other end of the centrifuge. The solids are removed by cylindrical discharger which rotates at greater speed than the bowl itself. The solid phase is discharged by a dam which ensures fullness of the centrifuge. The outflow can therefore be controlled by the rotation speed of the solid discharger. Moreover, the speed of the screw/scroll conveyor can be controlled in to adjust the solid load.

Figure 33 Horizontal decanter centrifuge (Flottweg, n.d.)

Figure 34 Horizontal tricanter centrifuge (Flottweg, n.d.)

Three-phase horizontal tricanter centrifuges (Figure 34) have similar structure and function as decanters. Their alternative is that they can separate the material down to three material streams. The one with the highest density, the press cake, the water in the middle and oil with the lowest density. The same principle applies as the solids are separated with pressure in a bowl but unlike the two-phase decanters, the middle dens liquids (the water) are discharged by pressure as well (Flottweg, n.d.). The lower dens liquid (oil) is forced to the inner surface of the screw by rotation and the higher dens liquid (water) is forced to the outer surface of the bowl. Thus, they can be discharged separately. These two liquids are not always in the same proportions which can promote challenges. For that purpose, adjustable impellers have been developed. They control the diameter of the two liquid outlets to separate different material (Flottweg, n.d.). The impeller is placed on the right side of the tricanter.

Centrifugation of liquids

Centrifugation of liquids include the process of separating stick water and the oils. This is most often conducted in vertical centrifuges, either a nozzle type which operates continuously or a self-cleaning one which requires fresh water supply (FAO, 1986). The liquor sludge is then fed into the evaporator system while the oil is lead into further polishing. The oil can go through several stages of centrifugation before it enters the oil polishing. It's a matter of the degree of processing, how far the producer wants to go. In onshore plants, it's common to have several stages of centrifugation before evaporation. It's not so common on offshore plants as limiting factors as space on board and high energy cost may affect the design. Oil polishers are nevertheless becoming more common on offshore plants to purify the oil. They retrieve crude oil from decanters, tricanter or from other centrifuges, depending on the plant's design. It's worth mentioning that oil polishers, other centrifuges and decanters require buffer tanks. These components operate continuously, and erratic input can affect the material quality. Oil polishers and other centrifuges moreover require material to be heated up to 95-90 °C to help with the separation and purity of the product.

Nozzle-type centrifuge is a vertical centrifuge which discharges continuously. The light dense/density liquid (oil) is forced at the centre and is discharged in the upper part of the centrifuge. The higher dense liquid (water) is accumulated to the outer surface through discs and discharged on the lower part of the centrifuge depending on the design. The main principle is that they discharge continuously (Pigott, 1967). Three phase nozzle type centrifuges are also available, they are designed to separate stick water oils and sludge at the same time (Arason S. , 2001).

Self-cleaning centrifuge is a vertical centrifuge which discharges intermittently. The stick water is fed into the inlet at the bottom or the top. The light dense liquor is forced to the centre and the higher dense to the outside. The main difference is that the discharge outlet for the higher dens (sludge) liquid is not always open but has a piston that controls the discharge. When the piston is closed, the lower dens liquid is therefore discharged. Water injection is used to open the piston and when it is drained it closes (Pigott, 1967).

Oil polishers are used on the final refining stage to clear the oil. A buffer tank is placed in front of the polisher to ensure constant inflow of crude oil, but they are often equipped with some sort of heating elements to ensure 90-95 °C hot material. Oil polishers are technically constructed as a self-cleaning centrifuge. However, their design needs to consider different particle sizes. Oil polishers moreover require hot water to be ejected into the crude oil for more effective separation. Common practice when the piston is opened for solids, is to circulate portion of the oil back into the buffer tank before and after each opening to prevent excess water and solids from going with the oil (Arason S. , 2001).

Evaporation

After separation of solids in decanters or other centrifuges, large portion of the oils and solids have already been removed from the press liquor. The next step is to process the excess stick water which undergoes evaporation for thickening to retrieve extra yield. Even though stick water contains low portion of solids (6-9%), it is estimated that it can hold up 20% of the final weight of

the fishmeal. The stick water contains compounds as dissolved and suspended proteins, minerals, residual oils, vitamins and amines/ammonia. Evaporation of stick water is highly energy demanding and in effort to reduce the energy cost, evaporators can be constructed in series, called multiple effect evaporators. The main principle is that steam is used on the first stage to evaporate and the vapor that comes out is used as a source of heat for the next evaporator. Thus, they can reuse the heat source at different stages with different evaporation temperature. The excess vapor that comes out of the last stage can moreover be used for other purposes in the plant such as preheating of the material.

Four stage multi effect evaporators are common in onshore plants. Having more stages is not preferred as it will require too high temperatures in the first stages (Arason S. , 2001).

The factor that greatly affects the degree of evaporation is the viscosity. It determines how much water can be removed before running into trouble, such as problems with pumping of the material or unwanted formation on the heating surface. For that reason, stick water is concentrated to 30-50% dry matter to prevent further viscosity development. However, viscosity decreases with higher temperatures for most fluids (Kim, Morr, & Schenz, 1996). To take advantage of this, the last stage of evaporation may be conducted in the first evaporator with the highest temperature to reduce the viscosity (FAO, 1986). A special care must be taken not to overheat the material since too high temperatures can damage vitamins, proteins, amino acids such as cystine, lysine and tryptophan since they are particularly heat sensitive. Thus, it's not required to heat the material up to 130 °C for any length of time (FAO, 1986).

When it comes to choosing the proper evaporator, many possibilities arise. Stick water is relatively heat sensitive and can be quite viscous on the last stages so evaporators should be chosen with that in mind. Another thing to consider is the space requirement, since available space on board can be a limiting factor.

Long tube vertical evaporators are commonly used in the onshore fishmeal industry. They are constructed either as falling film (Figure 35) or rising film type. The main principle is that liquids are led into long horizontal tubes while the steam condenses on the outside. The heat transfer coefficient is relatively high which allows for high liquid velocity and short residence time.

In rising film mode, the liquid travels upward from the bottom, the formations of bubbles rapidly accrue due to increased heat and acts as pump on the liquids, giving high vapor velocities. The liquid vapor then goes into a separator which separates the concentrate and the vapor. Their main advantages are excellent heat transfer, they are generally inexpensive and take up little floor space but correspondingly require good head space from 3 to 10 m high (Geankoplis, 1993). Their short residence time makes them especially good for evaporation of heat sensitive liquids.

Figure 35 Falling film evaporator (Geankoplis, 1993)

Regarding the falling film type, the liquid stick water is fed in at the top and flows down the pipes while evaporation occurs. Liquids are partly drained out at the bottom of the evaporator while the vapor is ejected through a pipe into a separation unit which condenses the unwanted liquid drops within the vapor. Falling film evaporators are widely used for heat sensitive liquids that require short residence time (5 to 10 s or more) and high heat transfer coefficient (Geankoplis, 1993).

Both evaporators are well suited for heat sensitive liquids. However, the falling film type is considered more effective do to its downward flow device and advantages of being able to use low temperatures with little difference between the heat surface and material. They can however be more expensive and are slightly bigger (Whalley, 1991).

Plate evaporators (Figure 36) are one alternative which can fit well for offshore plants. They require little space compared to the tower ones, typically around 3 m high. They can be used for very heat sensitive and highly viscous products due to their low residence time (GEA, n.d.). They give excellent heat transfer rate due to liquids being in the form of thin film. They can also be installed as multi effect evaporators and they have the alternative to be easily arranged by increasing the number of plates for larger flow rates (Whalley, 1991).

In principle, stem is injected at the top, transferring heat into the surrounding plates and into the feed liquor which boils and evaporates upward between the plates. The plates are constructed with channels for each production stream and sealing to prevent leakage, they are tightly screwed together and can easily be arranged. The extracted vapor is finally separated in a specific separation unit into concentrate and vapor, the vapor can moreover be reused in multi effect system which promotes better energy efficiency.

Figure 36 The outlook of GEA plate evaporator with steam trap (GEA, n.d.).

Figure 37 shows how the feed liquor is evaporated in plate evaporator. Plate no. 1 is a condensing steam plate, the hot steam condenses and transfers heat into the plate at each side. Plate no. 2 acts as a rising film on the feed liquor, where the liquid instantly heats up and the bubbles created do to rapid heat transfer act as a pump on both the vapor and the feed liquid forcing them between the plates. The feed liquid and vapor are moreover lead through plate no. 3 and down between plate no. 3 and 4 in a falling film mode to a separation vessel which separates the concentrate and vapor. Plates no. 3 and 4 are heated with the steam to ensure good heat transfer to plate no. 4. The rapid heat transfer leads to condensation on the steam which flows in a liquid state between plates no. 1, 3 and 5. The fifth plate is the first plate in another series of four plates (Whalley, 1991).

Figure 37. The function of plate evaporator and different production streams (Whalley, 1991).

Mechanical vapor recompression evaporators (MVR) is another alternative that has gained increased interest among fishmeal producers (Arason S., 2001). MVR evaporators are constructed similarly to single effect falling film evaporator, seen on Figure 38. The main difference however is that the energy source comes from an electrical compressor instead of a heat kettle. The compressor compresses the vapor extracted from the feeding liquid to increase the temperatures and is circulated through the falling film evaporator. This process continues as concentrate is discharged and feeding liquid is fed in. The feeding liquid entering the system requires preheating in heat exchangers powered by the condensed vapor before it enters the evaporator.

Figure 38 A simplified diagram of the MVR evaporation process. The MVR consists of compressor, heat exchanger, falling film tower and drive units (Geankoplis, 1993).

MVR evaporators normally operate on low difference temperatures between 5 to 10 °C which requires large heating surface for successful evaporation and to prevent viscosity development (Geankoplis, 1993). The advantages are low energy cost, capability to process heat sensitive materials and allows for a very controllable evaporation (Arason, 2001; Geankoplis, 1993).

However, the defects are high capital cost due to expensive compressors, the drive units and the large surface heating area required.

Drying

In a conventional fishmeal plant with processing of stick water, the dryer receives press cake from the screw press with moisture content of around 50%, sludge from centrifugation and concentrated stick water from evaporators. This leads to a relatively unstable and uneven material that is not well suited for drying. It may therefore be required to blend these different material streams to create more uniform material. This can be done in screw conveyors placed behind the press where the sludge meets the press cake and blends evenly. However, this may require the stick water concentrate to be heated up to 100 °C for even mixing (FAO, 1986). In addition, it may also be required to reduce the particle size of the blended press cake with so called hammer mill to facilitate the evaporation of moisture from the material. Reducing the particle size increases the total surface area which will contribute to more effective drying as well as a more stable and uniform product. Desired moisture content out of the dryer is below 12%. The dryers used in the fishmeal industry can be of two types; an indirect steam dryer or a direct air rotary dryer. The selection is dependent on several factors including their material chemical properties, fuel supply, available space and the production capacity (FAO, 1986).

The main difference between the two dryers is the convection used. The indirect steam dryer uses hot steam to heat up the contact surface, this can be heated tubes, discs, coils, etc. The material is heated in contact with the heated surface, leading to evaporation of the moisture within, while air is blown through the dryer in opposite direction with the material to capture the vapor. The steam dryer is constructed with heated screw in the middle which serves as conveyor, heat source and ensures blending of the material (FAO, 1986). The direct air dryer uses hot air for the convection which can be extracted through heat exchanger or directly from fire. The convection through air contributes to more efficient mass transfer which reflects in shorter holding time. The disadvantage is that when heat is directly extracted from fire, hazardous chemicals from the fuel can contaminate the material (FAO, 1986).

Understanding the difference between direct and indirect drying and its effects on the material properties is crucial for successful drying practices. In the drying of material, whether it is a direct or indirect drying, the material undergoes two processes:

- Process no. 1- the removal of moisture from the outer surface of the material. The removal is dependent on factors such as air humidity, air flow, pressure and the surface area of the material (Mujumdar, 1987).
- Process no. 2- the transport of moisture within the material to the outer surface. This transfer is dependent upon the material properties, temperature, time and the moisture content (Mujumdar, 1987).

At the first stages of the drying when the press cake is relatively wet, the removal of moisture occurs at a higher speed than at the last stages when the moisture content has decreased. That is mainly due to process no. 2 since the transfer of moisture within the material becomes a limiting

factor. In direct air, rotary dryers, too high temperatures can lead to shell formation on the outer surface of the material, thus limiting the transfer of moisture (process no. 2). If too high temperatures are conducted in an indirect steam heated rotary dryer it can lead to burning of the material on the last stages and the material can form as shell on the heating surface. To take advantage of this, secondary dryers can be installed. They run at lower temperatures to prevent burning and shell formation. This can be conducted for both direct and indirect dryers (Arason, 2001). Figure 39 describes how the drying curve changes in relation to the moisture content. At first, the drying rate is stable with constant removal of moisture. When the moisture content lowers, other factors become more limiting and the drying rate decreases. According to Arason (Arason S. , 2001), the drying rate of minced fish starts to decrease when the moisture content reaches 30 to 40%.

Figure 39 Drying curve (Myrvang, Stromman, & Jonassen, 2007)

The advantages of indirect steam dryers are their ability to process large quantities with relatively simple equipment and lower installation cost. They do not require extensive air cleaning, and the fishmeal becomes less dusty than in the direct ones which makes them more acceptable for mink feeding. Indirect steam dryers also allow for renewal of the steam and vapor which can be used for preheating or other purposes in the plant. They do not necessarily require pre-blending of the stick water concentrate and the press cake, due to constant circulation of the material in the dryer (FAO, 1986).

The advantages of direct air rotary dryers are short holding time (between 10 to 20 min compared to 30 min in indirect dryer) and flexibility when it comes to choosing fuel supply as they can be powered with conventional fuels to fish oils. They also require less maintenance and their processes are more controllable (Arason, 2001).

Due to their simplicity and lower space requirements, the indirect steam dryers are the most widely used in the offshore fishmeal plants.

Additives

Additions of antioxidant chemicals can be used to stabilize reactive fishmeal and fish oil to avoid undue heating of the material. But first, the objective of all drying practices is to lower the moisture content while reducing the water activity of the product. Water activity is defined as the partial vapor pressure of water in a substance divided by the standard state partial vapor pressure of water. Indicating when the relative humidity reaches equilibrium with pure water. The water activity is also dependent upon dissolved chemicals within and can be used to lower the water activity (salt, sugar, et al.). Figure 40 describes the reaction rates for foods in relation with water activity.

Figure 40 Reaction rates in food as function of water activity (Rockland and Stewart, 1981)

The objective of fishmeal production is to reach water activity 0,2 to minimize possible deterioration (Ariyawansa, 2000). It's moreover important not to overly dry the material as it can lead to lowering of the water content below 0,2 in water activity, causing oxidation of lipids. This can moreover be a safety concern since too dry fishmeal is highly flammable due to oxidation (Murasawa, Koseki, Iwata, & Sakamoto, 2018). There are more than one instances where boats have caught on fire at sea due to heating of the material. Antioxidants do however, not affect the water activity but are used to stabilize the material by reducing the risk of oxidation. The amount used is dependent upon many factors, but it is most commonly standardised for each species. According to FAO, adding 700 ppm of BHT-antioxidant or 200 ppm of ethoxyquin is sufficient to stabilize herring meal. The chemicals can be injected into the material after the drying procedure which requires blending, or it can be added with the stick water which blends the press cake before entering the dryer. Both methods are practiced today (FAO, 1986).

The use of antioxidants has raised concerns among regulators as it may have adverse effect on animals consuming it. The Food and Drug Administration of The United States (FDA) has for example decreased the maximum amount of ethoxyquin in pet food from 150 ppm (0,015%) to 75 ppm due to health concerns (FDA, 2016). More research is needed to proof these concerns as the FDA nevertheless stated themselves along with the European Food safety authorities.

Fish oil is very rich in omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids that are considered healthier for human consumption than the saturated ones (Ackman, 1988). However, it is much more difficult to store the unsaturated fatty acids as they are more sensitive to oxidation. The oxidation often occurs due to so called autoxidation of fat when exposed to oxygen (Labuza & Dugan Jr., 1971). One alternative to reduce the risk of oxidation is to add antioxidants to preserve the oil (FAO, 1986).

Nitrogen injection can also help with reducing oxidisation. Matís Ltd. conducted a study in cooperation with the fishmeal plant producer Héðinn Ltd. in 2014, which concluded that injection of nitrogen in the heating process resulted in reduced oxidation. This limits oxygen uptake which leads to a more stable product (Gíslason, et al., 2014).

Cooling

When the dried material leaves the dryer, it is at temperatures around 80 °C. The air holds a lot of moisture that needs to be removed as quickly as possible, otherwise the material can absorb that moisture resulting in higher water activity which can have negative effects on the material quality. Cooling the material before it enters the milling procedure also helps with more successful milling. The cooling will reduce the moisture content by 1-2%, making fishmeal with desired water content in the range between 9-11 % (Arason, 2001). The aim is to reduce the temperature from around 80 °C down to room temperature. (FAO, 1986).

The most common way to cool fishmeal is to use air blowers. Various versions are available, in some the air is blown in the same direction as the material flow and in others the opposite one (Arason, 2001).

Milling

After the cooling procedure, the dried material undergoes milling to retrieve homogeneous particle size. The physical properties of the material can however be a concern as large part of the material is already in right particle size or even smaller than wanted. Thus, it is often required to set up vibrating sieves to separate the smaller particles from the larger ones that need to be milled (FAO, 1986). This moreover ensures removal of unwanted particles such as pieces of wood, cloth, fish hooks and nails that could have entered the process. But more importantly, it ensures the right particle size for the customer. Most purchasers require the meal to pass through a 10-mesh screen which is a widespread scale for the particle size (FAO, 1986). The risk that follows continuous milling of all the material is the creation of dusting. The material becomes dusty which can cause contamination or loss, as the dust has access through the packing. Too small particles can moreover lead to oxidation as oxygen seems to have better access with more surface area (Gíslason et al., 2014).

Packaging and storage

When it comes to deciding on the packaging for fishmeal and oil, few possibilities are available. The main principle is that the fishmeal must be able to ventilate as heat and moisture have to have access out of the packaging to prevent condensation inside, which can lead to damages. This however requires strict and stable temperature and humidity control during storage to prevent the material from absorbing moisture from the environment. The most common practice is to package fishmeal into bags. They can be of various sizes and of different material. The most commonly used bags are the hessian bags, multilayer paper bags (without and with plastic lining), sheet bags or woven plastic bags (low density polyethylene). These types have their own advantages and disadvantages, but the most important principle is that they can let moisture and heat out without being too porous so that oxygen has unlimited access (FAO, 1986). Figure 41 and Figure 42 show different approaches of packaging. It should be considered that the packaging on board *Þerney* (Figure 41), is done in a much older plant than in *Norðborg* which is newly built (Figure 42).

When it comes to stacking the bags, same principles should be kept in mind; ventilation of moisture and heat, and prevention of access to oxygen. Therefore, it's not required to stack bags up to more than 5 m in width surface area (FAO, 1986). Too tight stacking can lead to undue heating in the material which causes moisture migration, condensation, mould growth and lumping.

Figure 41 Fishmeal packaging and weighing on board the Icelandic trawler *Þerney* (Sæmundsson, 2014).

Figure 42 Fishmeal packaging and weighing on board the Faroese trawler *Norðborg* (Atli S, 2013).

Bulk storage is another alternative. Fishmeal is often stored in silos or even sheds in onshore plants. Bulk storage reduces the work needed by employees and makes transportation and handling of the material easier. In general, bulk storage can be distinguished by two principles; the open type or the sealed type. In the open type, air has access through the bulk density by doors or other valves and openings. In the sealed type, the space is sealed off from the surroundings, but this requires aeration of the material and especially on the first stages when the material is most reactive. Silos can be used for this kind of storage, it involves constant conveying of the material from the bottom which ensures cooling of the material and promotes uniformity of the material (protein, fat and water), particle size and colour (FAO, 1986).

The most preferable method of storing fish oils is in mild steel tanks. (FAO, 1986). This prevents oxidation due to sunlight and conduction of oxygen through the constructed material. The tanks should be constructed with a cone in the bottom to have the option to drain out existing water. This is especially important in the first days and it is recommended to drain off existing water daily. It is also preferred not to store the oil in too cold condition as it can cause transformation of oils into solids. It is recommended to have heating of the tanks to prevent solids formation and to ease the transportation. Finally, it is also recommended to eliminate air in the tanks to avoid oxygen or to use nitrogen to remove the existing oxygen in the tank (Arason, 2001).

5.1.2 Fishmeal plant designs

There are three general fishmeal plant designs most commonly in operation today. The major difference between these plant designs is to what extent different material streams within the processing are utilised such as oil, press liquor and stick water and the energy efficiency. These three designs are explained below. The principle of the Low degree processing is a compact design that only utilizes the press cake into fishmeal, discarding the press liquor. The High degree design has more advanced processing and more focus on material handling and efficiency, producing fishmeal and oil. It utilizes all material streams and is equipped with an evaporation system, centrifuges and oil polishers which ensure that nothing goes to waste. The Hybrid design is in a way a combination of these two designs, it is equipped with extensive oil polishing and centrifugation of solids but without evaporation of stick water.

Low degree processing

The low degree processing design is simply a conventional fishmeal plant commonly used in the past decade on board trawlers. It's a compact solution which is relatively simple to operate and maintain. However, it has one major disadvantage, the press liquor containing valuable sources of protein and oil is discarded directly into the ocean. The basic components of the process are shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43 Flowchart for low degree processing of fishmeal

The low degree system design is without processing of the press liquor after the screw pressing procedure. As a result, it only utilizes the press cake discarding the press liquor with all the oils and protein within. Screw presses reduce the water content of the material down to 50-70% and if the plant is equipped with strainers as well, it may go as far down as 50% and the oil content can be reduced to about 4% (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The compression ratio of the press is often in and around 30%, which relates to the amount of press cake after pressing (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). Desired water content of fishmeal is 9% water after the cooling procedure. These assumptions can be used to determine how much press liquor is discarded and the chemical content of the press cake and fishmeal.

High Degree processing

This design is made to correspond to the idea of high degree, state of the art fishmeal and oil processing to retrieve material at its best possible quality. It is influenced by onshore processing plants and could be considered a conventional onshore plant.

The heating is conducted in heat exchangers instead of conventional screw cooker commonly used. They will be lined up with pre-and secondary heating to contribute to energy savings since the preheater uses excess material vapor from a dryer at 120 °C and the secondary heater uses 120 °C steam from kettle to ensure that right temperatures have been obtained. The dryer is basically a conventional indirect steam dryer.

In addition, the plant is equipped with a decanter, a centrifuge and an oil polisher for extensive separation of press liquor, producing refined oil, press sludge and stick water. The stick water is moreover evaporated to retrieve as much protein and solids as possible. The evaporation is conducted in two plate evaporators connected in series which allow for high heat transfer rates and energy recovery since the vapor is reused in steps.

The main components of the High degree processing plant can be seen in Figure 44. It should however be noted that the figure does not contain other components such as buffer tanks in front of the decanter, centrifuge and oil polisher. The oil polisher moreover requires a heat exchanger to heat up the stick water before separation. There is plenty of available heat sources such as condensed material vapor at 100-120 °C which can be used for this but would otherwise go into the sea.

Figure 44. Flowchart for high degree processing of both fishmeal and oil.

The high degree design is different from the low degree design in the way that it has separation and processing of press liquor. The press liquor enters the decanter which separates the solids from the stick water, called press sludge. The press sludge is in most cases around 3% fat and 50% water (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The stick water then enters the centrifuges and oil polisher which refines the oil to about 0,5% water and 99,5% fat. The rest of the stick water that comes from the centrifuges is around 9% FFDM and 0,5% fat. The stick water is evaporated down to 50% water before being blended with the press cake. This increases the final weight of fishmeal since it is believed to contain up to 20% of the overall FFDM (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The mixed press cake then enters the steam dryer and meal cooler which decreases the water content down to 9%. These values can be used to determine how much oil can be produced and the final chemical content of fishmeal.

Hybrid design

The hybrid design, is the idea of compact system that can fully process fish oil without an evaporation system. Oils are separated from the press liquor and the excess stick water is simply discarded. This plant is equipped with a two-stage dryer that is constructed with a pre-and

secondary unit to promote better energy efficiency, since the material vapor from the first stage can be used to power the secondary stage. This can be conducted as the secondary drying does not need to be run at as high temperatures since other factors within the material become more limiting. It moreover decreases the risk of burning the meal and other related defects.

The basic setup of components can be seen in Figure 45, the plant is basically the same as the high degree design beside the evaporation system and the two-stage drying setup. As with the previous figures, this figure doesn't include buffer tanks and heat exchangers for stick water.

Figure 45 Flowchart for hybrid system design

Regarding the chemical content, the only difference between the Hybrid design and High degree design is the evaporation of stick water which the Hybrid design does not have. By that it discards 20% of the total FFDM into the ocean. It lowers the energy cost since evaporation is an energy consuming process.

5.1.3 Silage production

Silage preservation and/or production of fully prepared silage is one of the potential methods to reduce discard and waste in the marine industry today. The procedure is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra effort of employees compared to other methods. The raw material is acidified which not only increases the shelf life of the material but allows it to be stored at room temperatures for more than a year with little reduction of quality. The latest trend in silage, and which has been practiced in Norway for considerable time, is to produce fish feed pellets out of thickened silage. The silage is thickened to about 50% dry matter contents and mixed with 40% binder such as alginate or guar gum to prevent disintegration of the pellets when

they enter water. The benefits of this method are that the process requires much less energy compared to fishmeal pellets which are dried down to approximately 10% dry matter content. This results in much less heating and will contribute to equal or better quality.

Silage production is not new despite its recent interest to reduce waste in the marine industry. It was first introduced in Finland in the 1920 to make greed fodder using sulfuric and hydrochloric acid. Later the method was adapted to whole fish and fish waste and production on industrial scale started in Denmark around 1950. At that time, Denmark produced about 15,000 tons per annum in 14 companies. The Norwegian seafood industry is one of the largest producer of silage in the world and produce large amount annually, both from whitefish, pelagic and aquaculture industry. 45% of their rest raw materials and unwanted catches is utilised into silage (Figure 46). One of the reasons why Norway has expanded into silage and has managed to implement it on the wetfish fleet as well, can be explained by the fact that silage processing facilities are relatively common all over Norway, due to its presence in the aquaculture industry. This makes easier access for whitefish operators to the silage facilities to land their RRM or their pre-made silage all year around. The implementation of silage production has been tried in other countries such as Iceland but failed due to some reasons. One of them could be due to lack of infrastructures, uneven access to raw materials all year around.

Figure 46 Allocated Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Materials (RRM) used for production of by-products in 2015 (in tons) (Richardsen, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016)

On board silage production has been practiced in north Atlantic fisheries for considerable time. It was installed on board few Icelandic trawler in and around 1980 but the production came to an end ten years later due to a few design flaws. However, the industry kept growing in Norway at the same time, beside the aquaculture industry. Many Norwegian trawlers are now equipped with specific unit for producing preserved silage while other boats such as the Norwegian freezer trawler Molnes have taken it even further and produce fish oil and fully prepared de-oiled and thickened silage on board. Figure 47 shows both the freezer trawler Molnes and a silage solution from Steinsvik ltd. which can be fitted in container or on board trawler.

Figure 47 Upper: Molnes freezer trawler, equipped with full on board silage production. Lower: Silage preservation solution by Steinsvik ltd.

Silage production is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra effort for crewmembers, and all RRM can be utilised for the production. The acidification of the silage increases the shelf life of the material which can be extended up to two years without little reduction of quality. Temperatures do not have to be reduced below zero degrees in the storage as is done with fresh materials or during transportation since the acid works as a preserver of the material, which is one of the big advantages of this method. When silage preservation is compared to other preservation methods such as freezing, cooling and/or maintaining material frozen or cooled through transport and in storage, the advantages of low energy use becomes even clearer. Silage production includes the following main steps.

Mincing

The mincing is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. The primary silage tank is used to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion and the secondary silage tank is to store the silage and maintain digestion.

The equipment needed can be variable and are for example dependant on the raw material. Whole fish and pelagic species need for example powerful mincing before going into the silage tank, while viscera and offal require less. Small particles should not be any greater than 3-4 mm in diameter to get even variance in the tank. Mincing is also carried out to activate enzymes that will, along with the acid, work on preserving and breaking down the material as well as ensuring even degradation of the material. One example of effective and powerful mincers are macerators, they suit perfectly for mincing of both whole fish and viscera. These mincers consist of two rotating wheels with blades, the wheels are located side by side and when the material catches into the blades it is shred apart through the wheels, an example of that can be seen in Figure 48.

Figure 48: drawings of macerators, which make excellent mincers for silage production

These types of mincers are designed to handle material in different sizes without stopping the production. When big particles enter the blades, the mincer continues to shred the material at lower speed. The size of the macerator needs however to be decided according to the size of the raw material (Arason & Harðarson, 1982).

Acidification

When choosing the type of acid used for the digestion, two possibilities arise i.e. mineral acids and organic acids. The mineral acids that have been used include hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid, while the organic ones are mainly acetic-, propionic-, formate-, acetate- and propionate acids to name a few. In the beginning, when silage production was on the rise, the usage of inorganic (mineral) acids was more common. They are less expensive than their organic counterparts but involve at least one relatively large disadvantage. The mineral acids don't start to act as preservative mediums until their pH value is below 2, rendering the solutions made by those acids to be relatively strong. This requires the fishermen or the companies buying silage made by inorganic acids to neutralize them prior to making products. It has been suggested that adding 20-50 kg of chalk to a 1 ton of silage can neutralize the solution. However, when the chalk binds to the acid, precipitate salts are formed which are nutritionally undesirable.

For organic acids, this is not needed as their preservative action starts already at pH levels of 4. However, these acids are more expensive than the inorganic ones, but as silage made by those types doesn't require neutralization prior to processing they could be the favourable option. The most commonly used acid in silage production is the formic acid.

Handling acid on board can introduce certain difficulties if things are not carried out the right way. Acid of this concentration is highly hazardous if exposed to humans. The acid should therefore be stored in a closed system where there is no risk of leak or spillage. Crewmembers should never have to handle the acid on sea in other ways than pushing a button or opening valves. Another factor to consider is the corrosion properties of the acid. In this concentration it needs to be handled with extreme caution and acidity control is therefore critical. It is subsequently advised to install a computer-controlled system that monitors the silage and measures the correct amount of acid needed to be added. These systems will add more acid into the solution if the pH value is rising too much above the desired value. Vacuum pumps can then be used to circulate the silage from the bottom of the tank to the top, for the acidity to be uniform throughout the solution. The acid can also be added relative to the mass flow into the silage tank, thus the silage will be fully blended when it enters the storage tank. The amount of acid needed for production of silage is around 2-3% of 85% organic acid, or roughly 20-30 kilograms of acid per ton of raw material (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). This does however not apply for all species and raw material, since silage made of viscera and offal does not require as much acidification. The optimal approach is therefore to have computer control, like mentioned before, which doses acid according to volume added into the tank and temperature controls to ensure rapid digestion during the initial stages.

Pre-blending in tanks

Silage tanks are categorized into primary- and secondary silage tanks. The role of the primary silage tanks is to receive material from the processing line, blend it with acid by using automatic temperature and acidification control and to trigger the digestion. Adding primary silage tanks for blending of the material helps with creating uniform material for even digestion. The secondary silage tank is however meant to store and maintain digestion of the material.

The breakdown of the silage is dependent on the concentration of the acid and temperature. A heater is therefore often used to increase the breakdown rate. It takes silage made of whitefish offal around two days to break down at temperatures around 20°C and five to ten days at temperatures around 10°C (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

The number and size of the silage tanks used for the acidification process on board fishing vessels is optional, the reason is that catch sizes vary between vessels. That is because silage production on sea is a batch production and is only run for a few hauls at a time. This is done to ensure as even breakdown as possible without investing in too many acidification tanks. The optimal approach would be to have a silage tank for each haul, but that would not be economically feasible.

There are few elements that need to be considered in the design of the silage tanks. The tanks need to be designed without sharp corners and with smooth inner surface to eliminate the risk of

infection from bacteria settling on the surface. The primary silage tanks need to be constructed with cone in the bottom for settling of unwanted particles as stones. These tanks can be constructed from normal construction steel (st 37) if the temperature of the silage is under 18°C, since temperatures greater than 18°C can lead to corrosion of the steel. For temperatures up to 30°C and more, anti-corrosive stainless steel is required or even plastic material (Arason, 1994). It is recommended to use anti-corrosive material for the primary tanks since the fermentation process has an optimum temperature between 25°C to 30°C (Archer, Watson, & Denton, 2001). Mixing of the silage is essential to get even chemical composition. Mechanical stir could be considered but optimal approach is to have vacuum pumping for constant circulation of the material. If stirring is poorly done the silage can separate into three phases, a liquid protein soluble on the top, an aqueous soluble in the middle and small sediment of heavy and insoluble fragments at the bottom (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

Not all species are ideal for silage production. Shells of crustaceans are for example hard to process into silage and species with high urea content in the meat are not ideal for silage production either, such as sharks and skates. It is therefore best to categorize the UUC before using them into silage. The crustaceans can then be processed into other products, such as chitosan which is used in food supplements and as colour treatment in aquaculture.

The equipment needed for silage preservation can be purpose-built and adjusted according to the needs of each vessel i.e. catch volumes and the available space on board. The primary tanks are usually located where there is easy access, but the secondary tank is often located below where there is unused space, such as where there was previously fuel- or ballast tanks in the bottom of the ship.

Temperatures do also have to be considered when choosing locations for the silage tanks, as temperatures close to freezing point slows the digestion of the material. However, the digestion does not have to be fully completed on board of the fishing vessel, since the main goal is to preserve the material for on-land handling. Temperatures in and around the silage tanks may therefore vary between 10-30°C without any problems. But, the higher the heat is the more digested material will be when landing occurs.

5.1.4 Silage designs

To further define between silage preservation and the process of making fully prepared silage, silage preservation is the process of only preserving the material for further processing while fully prepared silage has been thickened and de-oiled. For that reason, preserved silage is commonly sold directly into fishmeal plant or to animal feed producers while fully prepared silage can be sold as livestock- and aquaculture feed or to the fur industry. The fish oil can moreover be sold to feed producers. The basic components of silage preservation and full silage production are explained below.

Silage preservation

The silage preservation process can generally be broken into three main steps, shown in Figure 49. Firstly, mincing, which is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. Secondly, digestion in primary silage tanks to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion and thirdly the silage storage tank to store the silage and maintain digestion.

Figure 49 Processing streams and setup for silage preservation

After mincing, acid is added to the material into the primary day tanks to trigger the digestion, generally in the proportions 3,5% formic acid is used but other acid such as sulfuric acid can also be used (Arason S. , 1994). By having a primary silage tanks for blending of the material, sometimes called day tanks, helps to create more even digestion and more uniform material. While the secondary silage tank, is however, meant to store and maintain digestion of the material. Regarding the blending of acid, it is advised to install a computer-controlled system that monitors the silage and measures the correct amount of acid needed to be added. These systems will add more acid into the solution if the pH value is rising too much above the desired value. Pumps can then be used to circulate the silage from the bottom of the tank to the top, for the acidity to be uniform throughout the solution. However, acid can also be added relative to the mass flow into the silage tank, thus the silage will be fully blended when it enters the storage tank.

Fully prepared silage and fish oil

It is possible to take the silage production process further and allows for more value creation, but it also means increased investment cost and more complex processing. The end products coming from this process are fish oil and de-oiled silage. The fish oil can be sold directly to feed producers for example and the de-oiled silage is a marketable product that commonly sold to fishmeal factories, feed- or biofuel producers and to farmers as feed supplement or fertilizer. One of the

major benefits of this process is that water is removed from the product making concentrated and de-oiled silage, which gives a product that is easier to store, takes much less space and is more valuable.

The production process is similarly to the silage preservation process to begin with. In the first stages, material is minced and then mixed thoroughly in one of the primary acidification tanks along with acid. The material is treated with temperature and acid control to enforce rapid and powerful start of the digestion. By optimising all necessary conditions, such as temperature, acid control and other relevant factors, the silage can finish digesting in two days (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The secondary silage tank is therefore not necessary, since the digested silage can be utilized right away. Three primary silage tanks are needed, as full digestion takes two days. Once the silage is digested, it is sent through a heat exchanger where much of the water is removed from the silage. It then goes into a centrifuge, where the wet silage is separated into fish oil and de-oiled fish silage. The fish oil is then ready as a final product, but the de-oiled fish silage is sent into an evaporator where most of the remaining water is removed. The final de-oiled silage is then ready as a powder with very low water content, which takes relatively little space, is easy to store and has long shelf life. The processing steps are shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50 Processing streams and setup for full silage production

The ratio of oil in the de-oiled silage can be adjusted according to the buyer's requirement, as for example feed producers would want silage of specific oil content. Silage is normally priced by the fat and protein content. But there are few other quality factors that can also influence the price. Higher fat content increases the risk of rancidity which reduces the shelf life of the silage.

5.2 The demonstration vessel

The authors of this report have selected an 80-metre, 6,200 horsepower freezer trawler (Figure 51) to demonstrate suggested solutions applicable for this fleet sector. The vessel has a crew of 27-30 people, working on two shifts. Therefore, around 7-10 people might be expected to be working in the processing at once. The vessel is operated in the NE-Atlantic and the main target catches are redfish, cod, silver smelt and Greenland halibut.

Figure 51. The studied vessel, an 80-metre freezer trawler.

The vessel operates generally in the high seas or relatively far offshore, for example in the Barents Sea. The annual landings are in the range of 10-12 thousand tons per year, consisting of various catches. The catch composition of the vessel for the reference year used can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10. Typical catches for a freezer trawler of the size of the demonstration vessel operating in the Northern hemisphere.

	Catches	Landings	Discards	Discard rate
Redfish	5,933	4,351	1,582	27%
Cod	2,904	2,743	161	6%
Silver smelt	2,170	2,100	70	3%
Greenland halibut	1,850	1,423	427	23%
Saithe	102	100	2	2%
Haddock	83	50	33	40%
Other	1,050	600	450	43%
Total	14,092	1,1367	2,726	24%

As can be seen, there is a considerable number of discards, indicating that there are various opportunities to utilize the raw material for production of either silage or a fishmeal plant with a side stream of fish oil.

The normal procedures on board vessels such as this one are relatively high-tech and there is not much room for improvement with regards to the overall material handling. However, handling of species normally discarded as well as the offal and viscera can be dramatically improved and will be further elaborated upon in the next sub-chapter.

5.2.1 Baseline information and critical assumptions

There are a number of baseline information and assumptions that need to be considered when identifying and evaluating solutions for handling UUC on board this demonstration vessel. Especially if the solutions include fishmeal and silage production. These assumptions are further discussed below

Available UUC and RRM

Overall, 5.300 tons of raw material from both by-catch and RRM from the processing are expected to be used annually, given that 50% of the discards in the past have been below MCRS and that the implementation of the Landing Obligation will improve size selectivity by 25%. It is also assumed that all catches not subjected to catch limits will be used for the processing (apart from the 20% size selectivity improvements) and that viscera/offal from target species (where applicable) will be used as raw material for silage (except for roe and liver). These estimates are based on several “best available” assumptions, but the margin of error can be significant. The estimated raw materials for the silage preservation by main species/material group are shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Estimated volumes of raw materials that can be used on the demonstration vessel under Landing Obligation.

Raw material	MCRS catches	Species not subjected to catch limits	Viscera & offal from target species
Redfish	593		1,872
Cod	61		1,377
Silver smelt	26		630
Greenland halibut	160		63
Saithe	1		37
Haddock	13		19
Other	169	84	223
Total	1,022	84	4,221

The volumes indicated in the table for viscera and offal from target species are based on the assumption that production and utilisation rates follow historic trends for the vessel. Figure 52 shows the most common filleting and processing methods for each species on board the trawler. Approximations of these ratios are made according to landed volume of products in the reference year; 2016. It should be mentioned that it is assumed that all trimmings of filleted fish will be frozen on board, rather than used for lower valued products such as fishmeal or silage. The same applies for halibut heads and tails which are also frozen on board and sold separately. These parts are therefore not included in the volume that goes into fishmeal and silage processing.

Figure 52. Ratios for different products produced out of each species. WFF is - (Whole frozen fish). For headed fish there are, NH - (No head), NH/NT - (No head, No tail). For filleted fish there are, WS/WB - (With skin, With bone), NS/WB - (No skin, With bone), NS/NB - (No skin, No bone).

After having established how the fish will be processed, the volume of by-products and RRM can be determined. Table 12 shows the side streams from the main products for each processing method. For whole frozen fish, it's evident that no by-products fall by and headed fish is invariably all gutted. The efficiency of the heading varies between species as some are headed with a linear cut while other get more precise heading and as a result, less volume remains on the head. Another heading method widely practiced for redfish is to cut the head off along with the belly flap and collar bone to speed up the gutting procedure, thus resulting in lower head efficiency as the raw material goes.

Table 12. Processing methodology and by-products.

	HEADING		FILLETS		
PRODUCTS	NH	NH/NT	WS/WB	NS/WB	NS/NB
BY-PRODUCTS	Viscera	Viscera	Viscera	Viscera	Viscera
	Head	Head	Head	Head	Head
		Tail	Backbone	Backbone	Backbone
			Cut-offs	Cut-offs	Cut-offs
				Skin	Skin
					Bone

There are a number of baseline information and assumptions that need to be considered when identifying and evaluating solutions for handling UUC on board this demonstration vessel. Especially if the solutions include fishmeal and silage production.

The first question that needs to be answered, is the volume of by-products from processing on board the trawler and the chemical composition of the raw material. This requires the production methodology on board to be established and analysed with regards to catch schedules. The chemical composition of each by-product will be determined with the help of available data from fisheries, books, reports and experienced experts in this field.

The next step is to calculate the volume of fishmeal, silage and oil obtained by each design along with the chemical composition of those products. This requires number of assumptions to be established with the help of historic data on the chemical content for diverse material streams. These assumptions will then be used in mass balance calculations to determine the volume of fishmeal and oil along with the chemical composition.

After having established the chemical content and the volume of fishmeal, silage and oil, the revenue can easily be determined with the use of world prices. These prices are dependent upon the final chemical composition of the products either fishmeal or silage.

The variable and fixed costs will be determined with the help of available cost estimates that have already been conducted for fishmeal and silage production.

Critical production assumptions for fishmeal and fish oil production

The following assumptions are used to distinguish between different material streams in the processing of fishmeal and oil.

It is assumed that twin screw presses may reduce the water content of raw minced fish down to 50 to 70%, and oil content to about 4% (Windsor, 2001). Presses have common compression ratio around 30% press cake and 70% press liquor (FAO, 1986).

The stick water that is collected after separation of oil and sludge from the press liquor contains around 20% of the overall FFDM, 9% FFDM by weight and 0,5% fat. The oil contains 0,5% water and 99.5% fat and the press sludge is assumed to contain 50% water and 3% fat (Windsor, 2001).

There is little to find on the mineral content for press liquor and stick water which is an important value used to determine the ratio between protein and minerals of the FFDM content. However, it is well known, that most of the minerals in fish are stored in bones and solid particles which follow the press cake after the pressing procedure. The press liquor therefore has relatively low mineral content as well as the stick water which mostly consists of protein and water. For this reason, it is assumed that press liquor contains 10% of the overall minerals by weight and the stick water 2,5% (Arason, 2017).

Critical production assumptions for silage production

Since the silage process is much simpler than the fishmeal process, fewer assumptions are needed. The silage is concentrated down to 50% water and oil is separated resulting in silage with approximately 2,7% oil.

5.2.2 Technical solutions and cost-benefit calculations

Before the solutions to the technical aspects of how to deal with the side streams of by-products from the processing of the raw materials are presented, the cost-benefit analysis of the different options needs to be carried out. One of the ways to determine revenues generated from fishmeal, silage and fish oil in advance is to compare the chemical content of the product with historic prices. The main drawback of this method, however, is that it only considers the protein content of the end products but does not focus on other quality parameters that might have an impact. Therefore, determining the prices of end products can be difficult but the world prices mostly follow availability for a given time. The production output from Peru, which has been the largest supplier of fishmeal and fish oil in the world, is therefore a large contributor to the fluctuations in prices worldwide.

The fishmeal itself is normally priced by the chemical composition and the material quality. The most common way to evaluate fishmeal price for a given material is to compare the amount of protein with fishmeal prices (FAO, 1986). However, fishmeal prices are represented in tons of fishmeal, given that the fishmeal contains 65% protein. The world prices can thus be converted into USD per ton protein, which is around 2.500 USD or 2.030 EUR (CIF), given that fishmeal prices are around 1.600 (CIF) USD per ton or 1.300 EUR (Figure 53).

Fish oil prices are also determined by the chemical composition but also by other quality factors. Impurities in the oil, such as high amounts of free fatty acids, sulphur and water will lower the price as well as malodorous and dark coloured oil (FAO, 1986). These factors can be difficult to determine beforehand, which creates a degree of uncertainty. The European prices of fish oil can be seen in Figure 53 along with fishmeal prices, but the prices fluctuated between 1,600 to 2,400 USD per metric ton during that time. In this work, it is assumed that fish oil prices will be 1.800 USD or 1.460 EUR per ton of oil.

Figure 53. European fish oil and fishmeal prices represented in USD-CIF (FAO, 2016).

According to recent trends and interviews with key stakeholders in the Norwegian silage industry, de-oiled and thickened silage is now becoming more valuable than before. The reason for this can partly be because the Norwegians have increasingly started producing fish pellets out of thickened silage which is mixed up with carbohydrates. This kind of processing does not require as extensive heating, evaporation and drying as the silage is only thickened up to around 50% fat fry dry matter content and then blended. This saves energy and the product will be of better quality compared to traditional fishmeal pellets. The reason they pay higher prices for the silage is because this kind of processing will result in lower free fatty acid composition due to minimal heating of the material which is believed to benefit the aquaculture end users. In addition to fish pellets, the industry has been leaning towards production of human grade products. This includes fish protein, amino acids, fish oil and fish calcium.

It is difficult to get concrete prices on fish silage as many factors contribute to the quality and the usability of the material. A common way to calculate these prices or the revenue, is to use the same method as for fishmeal and use the same prices or price per protein unit and calculate the revenue on protein bases. In addition to that, the assumption can be used that the raw material will be sold directly into a larger processing facility such as larger fishmeal plant, which would buy the material with 40% discount or 60% of what the end fishmeal would be sold for. This translates to roughly 440 EUR per ton de-oiled silage, 1.460 EUR per ton fish oil and 202 EUR per ton preserved silage. This harmonizes with Norwegian data from 2013 on preserved silage, 1,5 to 2 NOK per kg or roughly 160 to 210 EUR per ton.

Analytic studies on the chemical content for most marine species have been conducted and are relatively easy to find. However, these studies mostly focus on the so called edible part of the fish which mainly consists of the fillets. This makes it difficult to find reliable data for whole fish and by-products such as skin, viscera, heads, backbones for diverse species. The chemical content and the ratio of by-products can moreover change dramatically between seasons, locations, puberty, size and the processing efficiency on board, which makes it even more difficult to establish certain values. Table 13 summarizes the chemical content and processing ratios for the by-products that fall by and are utilized into fishmeal and oil based on several separate studies and interviews with experienced experts in the field. The water content of backbones has been increased to adapt the data to the processing arrangements on board.

Table 13. Ratios of each raw material utilized into fishmeal and the chemical content.

	Volume ungutted tons	No.	Byproducts	Ratios of ungutted weight	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals	
Haddock, Saith and other	750	1	Skin	3% ^g	14%	6%	80%	1%	a
Haddock, Saith and other		2	Viscera	10% ^g	12%	27%	61%	2%	b
Haddock, Saith and other		3	Backbone	13% ^g	34%	5%	48%	14%	c
Haddock, Saith and other		4	Head	24% ^g	14%	4%	75%	6%	d
Cod	2743	1	Skin	3% ^g	14%	6%	80%	1%	a
Cod		2	Offal	5% ^g	15%	1%	80%	4%	b
Cod		3	Roe/Milt	2% ^g	20%	3%	76%	2%	d
Cod		4	Liver	5% ^g	6%	64%	30%	0%	d
Cod		5	Backbone	12% ^g	36%	3%	48%	13%	c
Cod		6	Head	24% ^g	14%	4%	75%	6%	e
Redfish species	4351	1	Viscera	9% ^a	9%	20%	67%	5%	f
Redfish species		2	Head	37% ^a	18%	2%	76%	4%	a
Greenlands Halibut	1423	1	Viscera	4% ^a	17%	12%	68%	3%	a
Silvers smelt	2100	1	Viscera	7% ^a	15%	18%	65%	2%	a
Silvers smelt		2	Head	23% ^a	17%	3%	76%	5%	a
By-catch (Lean fish)	718,9	1	Whole	100%	17%	3%	75%	5%	a
By-catch (Fatty fish)	387,1	2	Whole	100%	16%	10%	73%	1%	a

Having established values for each by-product, it becomes easy to compress them into final chemical content for each category of species seen in Table 14.

Table 14. Final chemical content of the raw materials/the by-products.

	Volume of byproducts tons	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	279	15%	10%	69%	5%
Cod	1377	19%	10%	65%	7%
Redfish species	1872	16%	5%	74%	4%
Greenlands Halibut	63	17%	12%	68%	3%
Silvers smelt	630	17%	6%	73%	4%
By-catch	1106	17%	5%	74%	4%
Sum	5327				

After processing, the chemical composition of the final product is affected by the raw material used, the procedures it undergoes during processing and to what extent the material is utilised. The chemical content and especially the protein content is used to evaluate the revenue.

Fishmeal and fish oil production

As mentioned, the fishmeal plant designs are distinguished by the degree of processing which relates to how extensively each material stream such as oil, press liquor and stick water are utilized in the plants.

The principle of the low degree fishmeal processing is a compact design that only utilizes the press cake into fishmeal, discarding the press liquor. The High degree fishmeal design has more advanced processing and more focus on material handling and efficiency, producing fishmeal and oil. It utilizes all material streams and is equipped with an evaporation system, centrifuges and oil polishers which ensure that nothing goes to waste. The hybrid design is in a way a combination of these two designs, as it is equipped with extensive oil polishing and centrifugation of solids but without evaporation of stick water, thus producing little less meal and the same amount of fish oil. The comparisons of the chemical content of the raw material estimations from these designs can be viewed in Table 15, Table 16 and Table 17.

Table 15 The chemical content of a low degree design

	Product	Volume (ton)	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	Fishmeal	46,0	53,7%	7,3%	9,0%	30,0%
Cod	Fishmeal	272,4	55,3%	6,1%	9,0%	29,6%
Redfish species	Fishmeal	308,6	60,8%	7,3%	9,0%	22,9%
Greenlands Halibut	Fishmeal	10,3	67,3%	7,3%	9,0%	16,4%
Silver smelt	Fishmeal	103,8	60,2%	7,3%	9,0%	23,5%
By-catch	Fishmeal	182,3	64,1%	7,3%	9,0%	19,7%
Sum	Fishmeal	923,4				

Table 16 The chemical content of a high degree design

	Product	Volume (ton)	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	Fishmeal	66,8	61,9%	6,1%	9,0%	23,0%
	Oil	24,3		99,0%	1,0%	
Cod	Fishmeal	411,1	62,6%	6,5%	9,0%	21,8%
	Oil	104,9		99,0%	1,0%	
Redfish species	Fishmeal	451,6	67,4%	6,2%	9,0%	17,4%
	Oil	72,0		99,0%	1,0%	
Greenlands Halibut	Fishmeal	14,8	72,2%	6,1%	9,0%	12,7%
	Oil	6,6		99,0%	1,0%	
Silver smelt	Fishmeal	154,6	67,4%	6,1%	9,0%	17,5%
	Oil	29,1		99,0%	1,0%	
By-catch	Fishmeal	186,3	69,8%	6,1%	9,0%	15,1%
	Oil	44,1		99,0%	1,0%	
Sum	Fishmeal	1285,2				
	Oil	281,0				

Table 17 The chemical content of a hybrid design

	Product	Volume (ton)	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	Fishmeal	53,6	56,7%	6,4%	9,0%	27,9%
	Oil	24,3		99,0%	1,0%	
Cod	Fishmeal	329,1	57,8%	6,6%	9,0%	26,6%
	Oil	104,9		99,0%	1,0%	
Redfish species	Fishmeal	362,8	63,4%	6,6%	9,0%	21,1%
	Oil	72,0		99,0%	1,0%	
Greenlands Halibut	Fishmeal	11,8	69,1%	6,4%	9,0%	15,5%
	Oil	6,6		99,0%	1,0%	
Silver smelt	Fishmeal	124,2	63,3%	6,4%	9,0%	21,3%
	Oil	29,1		99,0%	1,0%	
By-catch	Fishmeal	149,6	61,1%	6,4%	9,0%	23,4%
	Oil	44,1		99,0%	1,0%	
Sum	Fishmeal	1031,2				
	Oil	281,0				

Silage production

It is easier to estimate the chemical content of silage since it is a much simpler process. All material streams are utilised and thus it's not necessary to estimate the amount and the content of wasted material streams within the plant. The chemical content remains almost the same for the silage preservation process for example, since no actions are performed other than addition of acid. Regarding the process of making fully prepared silage, only oil and moisture are removed from the raw material which requires no additional assumptions to be made for calculations of other material streams. The summary for the chemical contents of the raw materials can be seen in Table 18 and Table 19.

Table 18 The chemical content of fully prepared silage and fish oil

	Product	Volume (ton)	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	Thickened Silage	119,9	34,5%	2,7%	50,0%	12,8%
	Oil	25,2		99,0%	1,0%	
Cod	Thickened Silage	734,0	35,1%	2,7%	50,0%	12,2%
	Oil	112,0		99,0%	1,0%	
Redfish species	Thickened Silage	809,5	37,6%	2,7%	50,0%	9,7%
	Oil	78,2		99,0%	1,0%	
Greenlands Halibut	Thickened Silage	26,5	40,2%	2,7%	50,0%	7,1%
	Oil	6,8		99,0%	1,0%	
Silver smelt	Thickened Silage	277,5	37,5%	2,7%	50,0%	9,8%
	Oil	31,0		99,0%	1,0%	
By-catch	Thickened Silage	473,5	38,9%	2,7%	50,0%	8,4%
	Oil	47,5		99,0%	1,0%	
Sum	Thickened Silage	2440,9				
	Oil	300,7				

Table 19. The chemical content silage preservation

	Product	Volume (ton)	Protein	Fat	Water	Minerals
Haddock, Saith and other	Silage	279,0	14,8%	10,2%	69,5%	5,5%
Cod	Silage	1376,9	18,7%	9,6%	65,2%	6,5%
Redfish species	Silage	1872,3	16,3%	5,3%	74,2%	4,2%
Greenlands Halibut	Silage	62,6	17,0%	12,0%	68,0%	3,0%
Silver smelt	Silage	630,0	16,5%	6,1%	73,1%	4,3%
By-catch	Silage	1106,0	16,7%	5,5%	74,3%	3,6%
Sum	Silage	5326,8				

Figure 54 shows the accumulated revenue for each solution according to the demonstration vessel over the period of one year. The results clearly show that the highest revenue is obtained by the high degree fishmeal design which utilised the material to a ratio of 100%. Compared to the other fishmeal plant designs, the low degree design makes much less revenue since it discards majority of the oils and valuable protein sources with the press liquor. The hybrid design is a combination of the high and low degree designs as it collects fish oil but discards the stick water containing 20% of the initial protein yield, which explains slightly lower revenue compared to the high degree design. The preserved silage has the lowest revenue, the reason for that is mainly due to low commercial prices. Compared to the fully prepared silage, more is earned by de-oiling the material since it gives off fish oil which is more valuable than silage and the de-oiled silage is a more finished product compared to only preserved silage.

Figure 54. Accumulated revenue for each solution with regards to species over the period of one year.

The revenues give a good image of what can be expected from these designs, but the operating cost of each solution is very different, impacting the decision-making process. The operation cost consists of both variable and fixed costs. These are the expenses regarding the production itself and the costs of the initial investment.

Variable cost is the expense that vary with the production output depending on the plant's production volume while the fixed cost are constant expenses that remain the same no matter

how much or little is produced. These expenses include loan payments, depreciation, insurance, repairs and maintenance. A further breakdown of these aspects can be seen in Table 20.

Table 20. The breakdown of variable costs and fixed costs.

Variable cost	Fixed Cost
Fuel cost	Installation cost
Labour cost	Loan payment and investment cost
Chemical cost	Depreciation
Packaging cost	Insurance
Transportation cost	Repairs and maintenance
Landing cost	

Fuel cost

The fuel cost is closely linked to the energy consumption for each plant. The energy consumption for each design can be seen in Table 21. It shows the annual power demand or amount of marine diesel oil needed to dry or concentrate the material on board the vessel. These numbers are based on calculated values for the equipment and material in question and consider different components within these plants and possible recovery of excess energy sources (Einarsson, 2017). The vapor shown in the table is the water removed from the material. The more moisture is removed, the more energy is required to heat and at the same time dry the material. These values moreover include mechanical power requirements for centrifuges, presses, decanters and tricanter. They also take into consideration different operational conditions on board vessels compared to onshore, as more energy is required when the production is not run continuously. Marine diesel oil costs around 450 EUR per MT.

Table 21. The total energy consumption of each design.

	Energy consumption	Raw material (Ton)	Vapor (Ton)	Diesel oil (Kg) / Raw Material (Ton)	EUR
Fishmeal & Oil	Low degree processing	5,327	675	66.95	€ 22,584
	High degree processing	5,327	3,683	134.96	€ 248,537
	Hybrid processing	5,327	1,580	63.45	€ 50,117
Silage	Fully prepared silage and fish oil	5,327	2,585	66.95	€ 86,547
	Silage preservation	5,327	0	0.00	€ 0

Labour cost

It is essential to have at least one employee with supervision over the plant. He/she will take regular measurements from oils, press cake, fishmeal and other production streams to ensure the best quality. In addition, this person must be able to service the equipment and act when failures occur. They must have got some education on the production and should have experience and knowledge on the equipment in question. It would be required that this person also had mechanical or engineering background. Other procedures such as stacking and packing of the

fishmeal may require another employee. The fishmeal is packed in large bulk bags which are filled in a specific packing unit which weighs up the meal as well. The fishmeal bags are then removed by forklift and stacked in the storage hold. This operation may require two employees as one performs the stacking while the other has control over the process. The fish oil, however, is pumped into storage tanks directly after oil polishing which does not require anyone to take direct action.

The salary management is not as simple as it may seem. In Iceland, it is for example statutory in collective fisheries agreements that proportion of the catch revenue is divided between the crewmembers instead of normal salary. The crew's share may vary between ships, the number of crew member, gas-oil prices and even the age of the boat. According to Hjálmarsson (2017), fleet manager at HB-Grandi, the total overall labour cost as percentage of revenue is 42%, compared to 27 crewmembers on board. For newer trawlers, this value is considerably lower the first seven years or around 34%.

The catch share is not drawn from net income, since the crew has only the right to receive catch share based on the FOB prices, which is only the landed value. Fishmeal and oil prices are based on CIF, which is a term that requires the seller to arrange for carriage of goods over sea. To consider this difference between FOB and CIF, it is assumed that FOB prices are 7% lower than CIF prices. This leads to labour cost being of 31,77% of the (CIF) revenue for 7 years old or younger ships and 39,25% for older ones.

Chemical cost

As previously discussed, additions of antioxidant chemicals are essential to preserve both reactive fishmeal and de-oiled silage to prevent deterioration of the material. It also reduces the risk of fire, since fishmeal can be highly flammable due to oxidation. Ethoxyquin is an example of antioxidant commonly used for both fishmeal and silage. It is used in the proportion around 200 ppm or 0,02 % of the fishmeal and silage weight (Winter & Feltam, 1983). The price of ethoxyquin is around 4 EUR per kg.

The silage processing requires acid in addition to the ethoxyquin. In this case, formic acid will be used in the proportion of 3,5% to the raw material. Formic acid is priced around 570 EUR per ton.

Packaging cost

Fishmeal is packed in 1,2 square meter bulk bags while the oil, the silage and even de-oiled silage can be transported in so called liquid container bags or Flexitank bags as seen in Figure 55.

Figure 55. Bulk Liquid Solutions Flexitank system.

The density for fishmeal is around 0,59 ton per cubic meter, fish oil is around 0,92 ton/cubic meters, thickened silage around 0,62 ton/cubic meter and silage is around 0,8 ton/cubic meters. The number of bags and barrels are shown in Table 22 along with prices of the packing. The fishmeal bags cost around 4 EUR and the 24.000 litre Flexitank bags cost 280 EUR.

Table 22. Cost of packaging.

		No. Fishmeal bags	No. Flexitank bags	Prices: EUR Bag; EUR Flexitank	Cost EUR
Fishmeal & Oil	<i>Low degree design</i>	1,304		4,280	5,217
	<i>High degree design</i>	1,925	13	4,280	11,263
	<i>Hybrid design</i>	1,544	13	4,280	9,741
Silage	<i>Fully prepared silage and fish oil</i>		178	280	49,743
	<i>Preserved silage</i>		277	280	77,682

Transportation cost

Since the trawler examined in this case study will be operated in the north hemisphere and most of the landings will occur in relatively isolated harbours, it is appropriate to assume for transportations cost over sea. If it is assumed that fishmeal and oil will be transported in 40 feet containers and that each container can hold around 40 bags and one Flexitank bag, the number of containers can easily be calculated using density of silage, fishmeal and oil.

If it is assumed that the trawler is operated in Iceland and the material is transported to Rotterdam it must be both sailed and transported by car. According to the Icelandic shipping company Eimskip, transportation of a 40 feet container from Reykjavík fishing harbour to Rotterdam costs 2,507 EUR.

Landing cost

The landing cost is assumed to be 10% of the transportation cost. These are all the expenses involved in landing fishmeal, oil and silage. The material must be weighted, and data registered to the officials. This is something that needs to be considered in context with the implementation of the Landing Obligation and how the surveillance will be carried out.

Installation cost

Fishmeal plants:

It is hard to get a hand on reasonable offers on special designs as it matters who the manufacturer is dealing with. The experience has shown that ship designers and ship constructors tend to get lower prices than the fisheries themselves. After a discussion with a Sævarsson (2017), project manager of an Icelandic company that specializes in ship designing, the price of plant such as these three designs would most likely vary around 1.300.000 EUR for the Low degree design, 2.100.000 EUR for the High degree design and 1.700.000 for the Hybrid design. These estimates are built up on offers that he has received in the years between 2013-2015.

Silage plants:

The cost of setting up this silage preservation system can vary depending on the equipment and manufacturers chosen. But given the specifications already discussed, the total cost of the silage preservation system could be around 170 thousand EUR, as shown in Table 23.

Table 23: Estimated costs of installing a silage preservation system on board the demonstration vessel

Cost items	EUR
Mincer	45.000
Acidification equipment	4.000
Primary tanks	14.000
Secondary tank	20.000
Conveyor belts	5.000
Vacuum pumps	15.000
Hoses, fittings and other miscellaneous	25.000
Instillation 6 persons for two weeks	38.000
Total cost	166.000

The investment cost for full silage production system is estimated to be close to 350 thousand EUR, as shown in Table 24.

Table 24. Estimated costs of installing a full silage production system on board the demonstration vessel.

Cost items	EUR
Mincer	45.000
Acidification equipment	4.000
Primary tanks	21.000
Heat exchanger	20.000
Centrifuge	50.000
Fish oil tank	4.000
Evaporator	20.000
Storage tank for de-oiled silage	25.000
Conveyor belts	5.000
Vacuum pumps	25.000
Hoses, fittings and other miscellaneous	25.000
Instillation (10 persons for three weeks)	96.000
Total cost	340.000

Loan payment and investment cost

The investment will be funded in part with a 70% bank loan and the rest 30% is taken out of the business. The loan will be an annuity loan with 3% interest rates and is payed back in periodic payments in 10 years.

Monthly payments can be calculated with the equation below.

$$A = \frac{r * (1 + r)^n}{(1 + r)^n - 1} * P_0$$

r = interest rate

n = number of years

P_0 = loan capital

r = interest rate

Depreciation

It is assumed that the equipment will depreciate down to 20% of its original value in 20 years which corresponds to an annual discount rate of 7.7%.

Insurance

The annual cost of insurance is 2% of the equipment cost which is a value used by FAO in one of their cost estimations for fishmeal plants (FAO, 1986).

Repairs and maintenance

Repairs and maintenance are a standard factor in operation of all productions. Spare parts are expensive as well as hourly wages by specialized experts. These factors are expected to count for 1% of the total equipment cost annually.

With the total revenues of each design as well as the fixed and variable costs clear, the cost-benefit analysis can be carried out. This is summarized in Table 25 below. This is also visualized in Figure 56.

Table 25. The comparison of each design in the cost-benefit analysis.

	Fishmeal			Silage	
	Low degree processing	High degree processing	Hybrid processing	Fully prepared silage and fish oil	Silage preservation
Revenue	€ 1.095.454	€ 2.208.841	€ 1.761.025	€ 1.517.879	€ 1.079.445
Energy cost	€ 22.584	€ 248.537	€ 50.117	€ 86.547	€ 0
Packaging cost	€ 5.217	€ 11.263	€ 9.741	€ 49.743	€ 77.682
Chemical cost	€ 739	€ 1.090	€ 875	€ 108.710	€ 111.596
Labor Cost	€ 347.259	€ 700.203	€ 558.245	€ 481.168	€ 342.184
Transportation cost	€ 81.746	€ 152.545	€ 128.704	€ 239.762	€ 347.768
Landing cost	€ 8.175	€ 15.255	€ 12.870	€ 23.976	€ 34.777
Variable cost	€ 465.719	€ 1.128.893	€ 760.552	€ 989.906	€ 914.007
Contribution margin	€ 629.734	€ 1.079.948	€ 1.000.473	€ 527.973	€ 165.438
Installation cost (Equipment)	€ 1.300.000	€ 2.100.000	€ 1.700.000	€ 340.000	€ 166.000
Investment cost	€ 390.000	€ 630.000	€ 510.000	€ 102.000	€ 49.800
Loan payment	€ 106.680	€ 172.329	€ 139.504	€ 27.901	€ 13.622
Insurance	€ 26.000	€ 42.000	€ 34.000	€ 6.800	€ 3.320
Repairs	€ 13.000	€ 21.000	€ 17.000	€ 3.400	€ 1.660
Depreciation	€ 52.000	€ 84.000	€ 68.000	€ 13.600	€ 6.640
Fixed cost	€ 197.680	€ 319.329	€ 258.504	€ 51.701	€ 25.242
Tax (20%)	€ 86.411	€ 152.124	€ 148.394	€ 95.254	€ 28.039
Profit	€ 345.644	€ 608.496	€ 593.575	€ 381.018	€ 112.157

Figure 56. Comparison between designs in the cost-benefit analysis.

As the figure clearly shows, the high degree processing is the most profitable one over the span of one-year post-investment and will give an average of roughly 608 thousand EUR in total profit. The hybrid processing is not far behind, though. Based on these calculations, the on board solutions were developed for the demonstration vessel.

Considering the analysis of the different solutions available for this vessel type, the overview of the solutions suggested can be seen in Figure 57.

Figure 57. The overview of the solutions offered on board the 80-metre demonstration vessel.

The catch is first brought on board and lowered from the nets down to the reception area, where it is transferred to the heading and gutting machines. Catch not subjected to heading and gutting is sorted away straight to the grinders, which act as precursors to the fishmeal plant located on the lower deck. This can be further seen in Figure 58. The heads and offal/viscera from the main catches are also transferred to the grinder in the left corner of the processing area for a full utilization of all catch. Catches that are under MCRS can be transferred straight to the sorting station for whole freezing.

Figure 58. The overview of the initial stages in the processing on board the demonstration vessel. Raw material grinder and mixer for fishmeal can be seen in the left-hand corner of the processing area, from where the material is pumped towards the fishmeal plant.

The main catch is then transferred from the heading and gutting towards cleaning before being automatically sorted, as indicated by the grey sorting machines in the middle of the processing deck. Cleaning is a vital part of the process of maintaining the quality of the material as removing blood and harmful bacteria from the offal will extend shelf life.

The catch is sorted into fish that is to be frozen whole and fish that is trimmed and filleted for plate freezing. This is done by automatic weighing on the conveyor belt and the fish is then directed into each respective slot, based on its weight and size. Smaller species and catch under MCRS is usually frozen whole and would be carried to the right on Figure 59 along the conveyor belt. However, main species of the right size, meant for filleting would be transferred to the left. The separate freezer for the whole fish can be seen in Figure 60 along with the plate freezers that handle the filleted main catch.

Figure 59. The view after size grading. Main species are transferred to the left for filleting and trimming while smaller fish is transferred to the right towards being frozen whole.

Figure 60. The freezer where smaller catch is frozen whole (to the left) and the plate freezers for the pans of fillets (on the right).

After the fish has been adequately frozen in both freezers, the fish is transferred in blocks of frozen products towards the hold, where it is packaged on pallets and stowed until landing.

Figure 61. The overview of the rear-end of the processing area. Fish is being transferred in blocks of frozen products towards the hold, where it is packaged and stored until landing.

The fish not meant for human consumption along with offal and viscera is transferred from the grinders on the processing deck towards the fishmeal and fish oil plant located on the lower deck, adjacent to the hold. This high-degree processing is in line with the most profitable solution for this case study and can be seen in Figure 62.

Figure 62. The overview of the fishmeal and fish oil plant located on the lower deck.

By having these solutions on board, it is ensured that all raw material brought on board the vessel is utilized with zero waste.

5.3 Summary

The demonstration vessel is a large factory bottom trawler that is capable of housing different designs of equipment that makes it possible to eliminate discards altogether, while at the same time maximizing the utilization of the material. This is on one hand done by maintaining the product quality of the main species as high as possible by correct handling before freezing and storing, and on the other by utilizing all rest raw materials and unwanted catch into fishmeal and

fish oil production, located on the lower deck. There have been several different alternatives for handling of UUC for the demonstration vessel reviewed in this study, including fishmeal and silage production. However, both a high degree fishmeal processing as well as a hybrid solution were the most profitable ones, with the former returning slightly higher margins given the assumptions in this study. The total profit calculated over a one-year period generated roughly 608 thousand Euros. For vessels of this size, eliminating discards should therefore be a relatively straightforward option, especially with the projected increase in aquaculture and the need for high quality materials from fishmeal production for food pellets.

6 Opportunities for improved utilisation of UUC in Greece

Highlights of chapter

- The Greek fisheries and seafood sector is facing challenges when it comes to implementing the Landing Obligation due to extremely high number of small vessels and landing sites.
- Infrastructure in harbours is limited and few harbours have significant volume of landings to justify major investments.
- Fishmeal and silage production are possible alternatives that can be applied in short-term, given that collection and transport of raw materials can be facilitated. More complicated alternatives can possibly be considered for long-term.
- Given the current status it is unlikely that fishmeal and silage production can be profitable, without EU or governmental investment.

The Greek fisheries sector faces considerable challenges associated with the implementation of the CFP Landing Obligation (LO). The fleet is dispersed and highly variable, landing sites are numerous (275 fishing ports according to the EC fleet register and 11 fish landing sites) and infrastructure is completely absent for dealing with UUC, as is the case with all Mediterranean fishing ports. The main objective of this chapter is to explore and evaluate possible processing solutions for Unavoidable Unwanted Catches (UUC), Rest Raw Material (RRM) and other excess raw materials in the context of the Greek fisheries and supply chains. Considerable amounts of fish is currently being wasted daily in Greece due to lack of infrastructure and solutions for gathering and processing UUC and RRM. In addition to that, the introduction of the Landing Obligation by the EC, is calling for solutions to make value out of non-commercial discard species which will now have to be landed legally. The solutions for dealing with unwanted catches should be based on, in order of priority: avoidance, selection and utilization. This Chapter is discussing the last priority, the utilization of UUC and RRM.

There are two potential processing solutions that are considered in this study, in the form of fishmeal and silage production. Material choices for these two processing methods were assessed based on previously records of discarded catches and fish waste on the retail- and commercial markets in Athens, Thessaloniki (Nea Michaniona) and Kavala; which are by far the most important harbours in Greece. The solutions were compared by the investment and accumulated profits along with the potential future development of marine by-products.

6.1 The Greek seafood sector

There is a longstanding tradition and history for fisheries in Greece and the industry has taken an important place in the Greece economy and employment. The annual landings, have however, been decreasing since 2006, but the aquaculture industry has grown over the same period, as shown in Figure 63.

Figure 63 Aquaculture production (2004-2017) and Total catches (2005-2017) (ELSTAT, 2018)

The annual catches are relatively low compared to other neighbouring countries as the total catches usually amount to 60-80 thousand tonnes with about 77 thousand tonnes in 2017. Most of the fishing fleet consists of small vessels (14,290) and only 485 open sea fishery vessels (2017 data) which makes the introduction of the Landing Obligation more challenging.

Greece has a coastline of 15,021 km and covers the mainland, 220 inhabited islands and 4.800 islets, representing 13.89 % of the total EU-23 coastline. Many different sized commercial fishing ports are scattered over the country and can be found all around the coastline. The main ports are Pireaus, Thessaloniki, Patra, Kavala, Volos and Alexandroupolis, seen on Figure 64.

Figure 64 Main fishing ports in Greece

The three largest ports are in Athens (Piraeus), Thessaloniki and Kavala and they represent roughly 83% of the total landings. Each of them play an important role in the Greek fisheries, both in terms of landings, sales and transportation of fresh and frozen goods. Considerable amounts of fish is being wasted around these occupations daily and throughout the value chain, which is the main challenge of this work.

Considering the supply chain for fish in the Greek fisheries, from fisherman to consumer, fish is thrown away on many stages. UUC are present on-board the fishing vessels and commercial fish markets often have to deal with excess unsold fish as well as merchants on retail markets. Fish is moreover ruined during processing and during transportation, but the fish most often ends up on the fish markets, either on the retail- or commercial markets regardless of the quality, which creates difficulties. For that reason, there is a great need for new preservation or processing solutions, so these raw goods can be processed before they become ruined.

The three largest fishing ports previously mentioned in Athens, Thessaloniki and Kavala represent the largest landing volumes. As can be seen, considerable amount of excess fish is currently being wasted in these areas every day, it occurs on the fish markets due to lack of solutions and infrastructure to support utilisation of those raw materials. The markets and the occupation around these main harbours are scattered over large area which makes it difficult to create value added solutions since collaboration or trade between different sectors is required to stand under investment. In addition to spoiled fish on these markets, the new Landing Obligation of the European Commission (EC) will call for actions and investment in new infrastructure, so

that bycatch and fish under minimum conservation reference size (MCRS) can be landed and utilised into valuable products.

The conditions in Greece are in many ways challenging. The fisheries fishing in the Mediterranean Sea face high biodiversity as more than 150 species are caught and only 15-20% of the discarded volume are MCRS catches while the rest 80-85% consists of unwanted non-commercial species (Machias, Vassilopoulou, Tsagarakis, & Karachle, 2015).

6.1.1 Discard amounts in Greece

Considerable research has been conducted on discards in the Mediterranean Sea. Discard rates have been published for countries fishing in the Mediterranean waters, according to each fleet category, fishing gear and species. The discard rate on board Greek trawlers are estimated around 38-45%, purse seiners 2.2-4.6% and artisanal 3.2-14.7%². This corresponds to roughly \approx 20.000 tons being discarded from trawlers, \approx 2.200 tons from purse seiners and \approx 19.000 tons from artisanal (Machias, Vassilopoulou, Tsagarakis, & Karachle, 2015)³. In total this is around 41,2 thousand tons which are discarded annually and compared to annual landings, which are 65 thousand tons, this correlates to discard rate of 39 % of the total catch.

There has been much less research done on the amount of fish that is thrown away on commercial and retail markets. For that reason, there is more uncertainty regarding the amounts of fish that is being spoiled around those occupations compared to the discard volumes. It is estimated that 70% of the annual catches will go through these markets while 5-15% of that volume is discarded, 5% on commercial markets and 10% on retail markets. Table 26 shows a rough estimation of discards and other wasted materials in the Greek wild capture seafood value chains.

Table 26. Amount of raw material in the main fishing ports and on commercial and retail markets

	Raw material									
	Annual landings	Discard off-shore		Total volume through domestic markets		Commercial markets		Retail markets		Sum (ton)
Total Greece	60.000	39%	38361	70%	45000	5%	2250	10%	4500	45.111
Athens	20.000	39%	12787	70%	15000	5%	750	10%	1500	15.037
Thessaloniki	15.000	39%	9590	70%	11250	5%	563	10%	1125	11.278
Kavala	15.000	39%	9590	70%	11250	5%	563	10%	1125	11.278
Sum (ton)	50.000		31.967				1.875		3.750	37.592

The numbers in Table 27, show the volumes that are being wasted or at least can be utilised in the area around Athens, or 37% of the total amount while 46% is divided between Thessaloniki and Kavala. This corresponds to 69 tons a day in Athens and 86 tons in the area around Thessaloniki and Kavala, compared to 260 working days in a year. In this context, the expected combination of

² Tsagarakis et al., 2014

³ See: http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_eventi/2015/01/racmed_discards_hcmr.pdf

these volumes is 65% fatty fish vs 35% lean species, where fatty species are distinguished from the lean by storing their fat within their muscle layers rather than in the liver.

Table 27. Total volumes of fatty and lean fish species in the three locations.

	Discard- & Spoiled fish				
	Total	Lean 65%		Fatty 35%	
		Ton annually	Ton/24h	Ton annually	Ton/24h
<i>Athens</i>	9.774	6.353	24	3.421	13
<i>Thessaloniki</i>	7.330	4.765	18	2.566	10
<i>Kavala</i>	7.330	4.765	18	2.566	10

This suggests that there might be considerable opportunities in utilising these materials.

6.1.2 Potential on-land uses of UUC and RRM

When it comes to processing of fish waste or bycatch many possibilities arise. Commercial products such as fishmeal, fish oil, silage, marine bait, and fertilisers are well known alternatives and with relatively steady markets. This creates stable operational conditions and lower risk but may result in lower or poorer contribution margin since these products no high-end products. The fact that more valuable products can be made has drawn the attention towards more valued and innovative products such as fish protein hydrolysate, fish protein powder, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. Where there are opportunities for more value creation. This may, however, call for more investment and more risk since these products require additional marketing. Following is a list of few conventional methods for processing RRM, low value catches and fish waste.

- **Fishmeal:** can be obtained from any fish or fish by products, after a thermal process to coagulate the protein and separate the oil, fishmeal is a brown powder rich in protein. The colour is affected by fish species, particle size, fat and moisture content. Fishmeal is mainly used in animal feed. Aquaculture account for > 60 %, pigs 25 %, and poultry 8 %.
- **Fish oil:** obtained in the same process as fishmeal, fish oil is a liquid product composed mainly by fatty acids, high in unsaturated fatty acid, with variable amounts of phospholipids, glycerol ethers and wax esters. Fish oil has different uses that can vary in function of its composition. ~80 % of fish oil is used in aquaculture and ~13 % destined to human consumption.
- **Mink feed:** any fish of fish by-product can be used to feed mink for the fur industry (food regulation does not apply). This alternative is often used for products that cannot be used for anything else as food safety regulations do not have to be taken into consideration i.e. mink is not used for human consumption or for ingredients that become animal feed. Viscera, which contains digestive trace elements can therefore be used as mink feed.

Figure 65 shows how viscera is block frozen in Icelandic fish processing plant and the blocks are then used for mink fee.

Figure 65 Frozen cut-offs from processing of whitefish and block frozen viscera

- **Marine Bait:** discard species can be used as effective pot bait when targeting crabs and lobsters. The condition of the material is generally not important, which makes this a good alternative for low value materials that are difficult to preserve. Fish that is high in fat are usually considered good bait.
- **Fish Protein Concentrate (FPC):** Dehydrated and ground products, with a variable protein content, which may or may not taste and smell fish, depending on the method of production used. This technology aims to achieve a stable product, with a protein concentration higher than that of fish muscle. The manufacture of this type of products allows the use of species that are not accepted for direct consumption, and of the waste from the fish processing industries. Used for animal feed but due to their high nutritional value, they can also be used for human consumption or as a protein source in the elaboration of different foods. This, however, is highly dependent on the quality of the product.
- **Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH):** Stable product (Figure 66) with good functional properties and high nutritional value, prepared from the protein fraction of whole fish, by-products or processing waters thereof, by chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis. A product consisting of mixtures of amino acids and peptides of different sizes are obtained depending on the degree of hydrolysis carried out. It is used mainly in animal feed but can also be used in the food industry as a flavouring or raw material for the elaboration of aromas.

Figure 66. Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH) powder

- **Silage:** Liquid protein hydrolysate made from whole fish or from processed residues. The hydrolysis is carried out by endogenous proteolytic enzymes, located in the viscera and in the meat of the fish, under acidic conditions. Acid conditions limit the growth of degradative bacteria. It is used mainly as a protein supplement in animal feed (cattle, poultry and aquaculture) and as a base to produce fish sauce.
- **Compost/Fertilizers:** obtained by an aerobic decomposition process carried out by the own microorganisms of the organic matter. Compost from fish usually consists of fish waste, saw dust, wood bark chips and is covered with leaf compost to make a compost pile. The compost is used for soil amendment or fertilizer. Also, fish protein hydrolysates can be used as fertilizer.

6.1.3 Alternatives in the Greek context

The authors of this report have chosen two alternatives for further investigation in the Greek context, as they consider those alternatives the most applicable solutions, at least in the short run. These alternatives are fishmeal and fish oil production using small compact fishmeal plants, and silage production which can either be sold as raw material into a larger fishmeal factory or it can for example be used to make feed pellets or more valuable products.

Fishmeal production

Fishmeal production often appears in the discussion around bycatch and by-products, as potential processing solution for those raw materials. Worldwide there is a long tradition for fishmeal production, especially of pelagic species. Fishmeal is very commercial product and known all over the world, which is important for stable operating conditions. Largest part of the industry consists of large facilities built for extreme quantities with large production capacities. These plants are not very convenient for smaller amounts of excess fish from markets or small quantities of bycatch since it is expensive to start such a large processing facility. These sectors demand large volumes for each production set, which may often cause formation of queue in front of the production and the material that enters the production first must wait until minimum volume has been reached. This can cause considerable reduction on the quality. In recent decades however, more and more interest has been towards smaller production units to produce smaller quantities at a time, both from the aquaculture industry as well as fish processors. This development has already occurred, and many freezer or processing trawlers have built in fishmeal plant to process all the rest raw materials that fall by in the processing on board. Figure 67 shows an example of these compact fishmeal plants, one for on land processing and the other for on board processing on sea. Many different versions of these plants are offered, some are advanced and equipped with components for separation of oil while others are designed to only utilise the press cake while protein liqueur and oils are discarded. This of course affects the revenue since valuable protein sources will be lost. The fish oil is also very valuable, it is either sold to feed producers or to fish oil refining facilities for making products for human consumption.

Figure 67. Simplified Héðinn fishmeal and fish oil plants, on left on land version and on right smaller off-shore version.

Compared to silage production, the fishmeal process is relatively complex, as many variable factors affect the quality of the product. It requires a considerable investment in both equipment and housing and the process may leave odour smells into the air, which may affect the surrounding environment and decisions regarding possible location for the plant. The processing requires specialised workforce with engineering or mechanical background, which results in higher labour cost. In context of the Greece fish markets, a good collaboration would be needed to keep such a plant running all year around, or independent operator with ownership of such a plant. The plant must have stable access to raw material to ensure fresh raw material, since the risk of these plants is always that the raw material will not stand up to the quality standards required to make high quality and valuable product since the production may have to wait until certain volume is reached and during that time, the material can be ruined.

Silage production

The other solution in Greece's context is silage preservation on location. This is something that has been on the rise all around Norway and has been practiced for some time. The expansion in silage production in Norway, is partly due to their growing aquaculture activity which ensures the industry a stable access to fresh raw material all year around. The fisheries have also followed up with this development and many trawlers and vessels are now equipped with silage production units on board for processing of heads, viscera and other by-products that fall by in the processing of the fish. The on-shore fish processing plants are in addition, equipped with silage units to process rest raw materials. Large companies in this industry, such as ScanBio and AkvaRen, gather the raw materials from these sectors and deliver it to their processing plants where the raw material is further processed. Norway is, however, not the most accessible country, as narrow mountain roads can be challenging during winter. These companies have despite that managed to develop advanced logistic units and operate both tankers which can unload silage from vessels on sea as well as many trucks. Figure 68 shows an example of Norwegian silage truck and a tanker landing silage.

Figure 68. Norwegian silage truck and a tanker landing silage

The silage can be used for many purposes such as fishmeal and fish oil making, fur- and fish feed, fish protein for human consumption, special chemical product, biofuel and animal nutrition to name a few.

The silage making process is twofold. First, it's the production of preserved silage, where the raw material is minced and acidified. Second de-oiling and thickening. The latter process is in most cases performed in a larger facility while the previous can be made on location, whether it's on board a boat or elsewhere. The first step in this process, is mincing of the material, it is fed into a tunnel shaped tank with mincer on the bottom to shred the material evenly apart. After that it is acidified and enters specific digestion tank which is equipped with mixer at the bottom to ensure even digestion and to reduce the size of bones. Formic acid is used in the proportion 3.5% acid per kg raw material along with antioxidant chemicals to further stabilise the material. After approximately one to four days, depending on the temperatures the digestion was conducted at, the material is considered stable and is ready for transport and further processing.

An example of simple silage preservation making unit can be seen on Figure 69, it's a Norwegian solution produced by Steinsvik. It's simply a shipping container with equipment for making silage. The solution includes computer control, mincer that shreds the material into smaller particles with capacity of 650 kg/h, pumps and tubes for adding acid and antioxidant, pH and temperature sensors along with heat exchanger. The main silage tank is 8.000 litres and is in the end of the container.

Figure 69. The Steinsvik silage plant. (Picture: Steinsvik)

Similar units like this could be very applicable in the Greek context, around fish markets, both commercial and retail markets, around fish processors, on landing sites and around aquaculture units (in allocated zones for aquaculture or POAY in Greek i.e. Organised Areas for Aquaculture Development). Similar units have for example been used widely around Norway and Chile for processing of dead salmon from sea cages. In the same way, bycatch and non-commercial species from fisheries, and unsold fish from markets can be utilised for value creation. Silage production is without doubt the simplest and most energy efficient way of preserving seafood for industrial uses. The process is simple, the equipment is easy to operate and maintain and its relatively unexpansive, or at least compared to a fishmeal plant. After the material has digested after 1-4 days the product is very stable and the shelf life has been extended to at least a year. This is clearly one of the big advantages of silage, since external factors such as, air humidity and temperatures will not affect the quality of the product. Compared to fishmeal which is much more sensitive to external factors such as sunlight and oxygen, which will cause oxidation of fats, humid air will raise the moisture content and at the same time the water activity which creates good condition for bacterial growth. While silage is relatively stable.

The disadvantages of silage, however, are higher transportation cost compared to fishmeal. The infrastructure for a given location may not be in place for gathering the silage and the product

may lack of noticeable opportunities on the markets. On the other hand, silage can be utilised to make more commercial products such as fishmeal powder or feed pellets. It can be sold directly as raw material into a fishmeal factory to produce fishmeal powder and fish oil. Another alternative for silage, which has yet not really caught on for some reason, is to make feed pellets by de-oiling and thickening the silage down to 50% dry matter content, blending it with grain and starch and finally extrude it into feed pellets. This latter process, requires much less energy than conventional fishmeal pellets, since it does not require as extensive drying of the material. The reason this can be done, is that normally when making fish pellets, fishmeal powder is blended with grains and starch along with water to bind the material. However, by using silage with 50% dry matter content, the addition of water is not needed. The process requires less energy for that reason, since less water is removed.

6.2 Small scale Fishmeal and fish oil production

The first suggestion, is to set up in total four small scale fishmeal production units in two locations. One located around Thessaloniki and another group in Athens.

Many different versions of fishmeal plants are available today and can be designed according to the investor's requirements, regarding capacity, utilisation rate of the raw material and type of energy source. Some are designed to utilise only the press cake or the solids, while other plants utilise the material 100% and produce oil as well. This affects the revenue since valuable protein sources can be lost with the stick water and can account up to 20% of the initial protein source and consequently 20% of the revenue as well since fishmeal is priced by the protein content (FAO). More advanced processing will require more investment, for example if evaporators are installed to thicken the stick water. Even though more energy is required to evaporate and thicken the stick water, it is highly recommended as the benefits of it will exceed the costs in the long-term.

Figure 70 Fishmeal & fish oil plants and their location

6.2.1 Investment cost

This suggestion proposes, installation of four separated small-scale fishmeal plants, as seen in Figure 70. Two located in Athens and two in either Thessaloniki or Kavala. The reason assuming for two plants on each location is to make sure that the raw material will not have to wait for more than half a day before being processed. This will make sure that both fatty and lean fish species can be processed separately and right away and will contribute to better quality. This will help these facilities to make more valuable products and will give them more flexibility towards their customers and makes it easier to produce fishmeal with specific fat or moisture content. Having

two small plants on each location will also reduce the start-up cost for each production set, which, in addition, makes the production more flexible towards uneven input of raw material.

Generally, when speaking of small scale fishmeal plants, it applies to plants with production capacity between 2,5 and 75 t/24h. In Athens, the average volume of excess fish is 45 tons each day from fatty species and 24 tons from lean. These numbers will fluctuate and under certain circumstances these volumes may be expected to be multiplied. For that reason, it best to assume for larger plants than the average numbers. The average volumes for Thessaloniki and Kavala combined is 56 tons of fatty fish and 30 tons lean fish species. Since the raw material may come in larger quantities, the production should be designed with bigger capacities, seen on Table 28.

Table 28. Investment cost for the fishmeal plants

		Production capacity (ton/24h)	Investment cost (EUR)	Average volumes (ton/24h)
<i>Athens</i>	Lean fish	50	4.000.000	24
	Fatty fish	50	3.500.000	13
<i>Thessaloniki and Kavala</i>	Lean fish	75	4.200.000	37
	Fatty fish	50	3.500.000	20
Sum		225		94.0

European Commission funding

The European Commission, through the 2014-2020 Fisheries and Maritime Operational Program, supports discard operations. The objective of the Act to be supported is to extend the activities of fishermen on board and to manage their catches in an integrated manner, processing, marketing and direct sales, and improving the quality of fishery products. With the announcement of measure 3.4.4 - "Processing of fishery and aquaculture products", (Reg. (EU) 508/2014, article 69 of EU Priority 5, "Strengthening of marketing and processing", of the Operational Program for Fisheries and the Sea 2014-2020, financed Actions aimed at exploiting discarded catches. Measures for productive investment in this field are covered by Measure 3.4.4 and concern, inter alia, the following types of operations: - Saving energy or reducing the impact on the environment. - Processing of catches not intended for human consumption. The above phrase is the key that opens the door for access to finance for this investment. In Greece, the objectives of these Acts will be achieved through actions such as:

- Establishment of new processing plants
- Extension of existing processing units
- Modernization or relocation of existing processing plants

The budget of the submitted investment proposals must be over 20,000 EURO and not exceed 8,000,000 €. The maximum duration of completion of the Transactions is two (2) years, starting with the date of the Act of Accession.

Table 29 Percentage of Public Expenditure and Private Participation under Measure 3.4.4, "Processing of Fishery and Aquaculture Products" in Greece

		TERRITORY OF THE COUNTRY	DISTANT GREEK ISLANDS
1	Very small, small and medium-sized enterprises	Public Aid	50%
		Private participation	15%
2	Fisheries organizations or other collective beneficiaries	Public Aid	60%
		Private participation	15%
3	Producer organizations, associations of producer organizations or interbranch organizations	Public Aid	75%
		Private participation	15%
4	Operations which serve a collective interest and have a collective beneficiary and innovative characteristics against case, at local level	Public Aid	100%
		Private Participation	0%

6.2.2 Revenues

Fishmeal and fish oil prices can be difficult to determine as many quality factors affect the end price. The world prices mostly follow availability for a given time and the production output from Peru which has been the largest supplier of fishmeal and oil in the world. Fishmeal is normally priced by the chemical composition and the material quality. The most common way to evaluate fishmeal price for given material is to compare the amount of protein with fishmeal prices (FAO, 1986). However, fishmeal prices are represented in tons of fishmeal but given that the fishmeal contains 65% protein. The world prices can thus be converted into USD per ton protein, which is around 2,500 USD (CIF), given that fishmeal prices are around 1,600 (CIF) USD per ton (Figure 71). This corresponds to 1,344 EUR per ton protein.

Figure 71. European fish oil and fishmeal prices represented in USD (Child, Garcia, Josupeit, Nianjun, Rahimzadeh, Sabatini, ... Monfort, 2016).

Fish oil prices however, are not only determined by the chemical composition but also by other quality factors. Defects as high amounts of free fatty acids, sulphur and water will lower the price as well as malodorous and dark coloured oil (FAO, 1986). These factors can be difficult to determine beforehand which creates a degree of uncertainty. The European prices of fish oil can be seen in Figure 71 along with fishmeal prices (FAO, 2016), but the prices fluctuated between 1,600 to 2,400 USD per metric ton during that period. In this work, it is assumed that fish oil prices will be 1,800 USD per ton of oil. This corresponds to 2,069 EUR per ton oil.

Table 29. Mass balance and revenue calculations for the four suggested fishmeal units

Fishmeal production - Mass balance					
		Athens		Thessaloniki & Kavala	
		Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Raw material (ton)		6353	3421	9530	5131
<i>Ton/day</i>	<i>24</i>		<i>13</i>	<i>37</i>	<i>20</i>
Moisture (%)		75.0%	73.0%	75.0%	73.0%
Fat (%)		3.0%	10.0%	3.0%	10.0%
Protein (%)		17.0%	16.0%	17.0%	16.0%
Other (%)		5.1%	1.4%	5.1%	1.4%
FFDM (%)		22.1%	17.4%	22.1%	17.4%
		100%	100%		
Moisture (ton)		4590	2440	6886	3660
Moisture (%)		100%	100%	100%	100%
Fat (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Protein (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Other (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
FFDM (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Fish oil (ton)		108	278	161	416
Moisture (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Fat (%)		100%	100%	100%	100%
Protein (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Other (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
FFDM (%)		0%	0%	0%	0%
Fishmeal (ton)		1662	717	2492	1076
Moisture (%)		10.5%	8.0%	10.5%	8.0%
Fat (%)		5.0%	9.0%	5.0%	9.0%
Protein (%)		65.0%	76.3%	65.0%	76.3%
Other (%)		19.5%	6.7%	19.5%	6.7%
FFDM (%)		84.5%	83.0%	84.5%	83.0%
Fishmeal Revenue		1.898.184 EUR	961.976 EUR	2.847.276 EUR	1.442.964 EUR
Fish oil Revenue		138.268 EUR	356.937 EUR	207.402 EUR	535.406 EUR
Revenue		2.036.452 EUR	1.318.913 EUR	3.054.678 EUR	1.978.370 EUR
Sum		3.355.365 EUR		5.033.048 EUR	
Fishmeal price	1344	EUR/ per ton fishmeal 65% protein			
Fishmeal protein price	2068	EUR/ per ton fishmeal 100% protein			
Fish oil prices	1513	EUR/ per ton fish oil			
Production Efficiency	85%	Affects ther revenue			

6.2.3

Operating costs

The costs associated with the operation of a fishmeal are variable; ranging from energy costs, labour costs, packaging costs, maintenance costs etc. Following is a short overview of the main operational cost items.

Raw material cost

The cost of raw material must be taken into consideration. The raw material cost is expected to be around 40% of the total final revenue of fishmeal and oil. These are the earnings that the merchants on the fish markets and fishermen landing non-commercial discarded species get for their raw material. This corresponds to roughly 0,14 EUR per kg raw material.

Energy cost

The energy source is either fuel, electricity or combination of both. Table 30 shows the comparison between electrical cost and fuel cost. Preferably electric power should be used due to environmental factors, but if availability is limited, these plants may have to rely on fuel. According to FAO Fisheries technical paper – 142, published in 1999, small scale fishmeal plant with capacity between 10-60 ton/24h, consume 55 kg of oil per ton of raw material and 35 kWh per ton raw material, assuming the plant is equipped with evaporators. These values may be overestimated since these plants have improved their energy efficiency in recent years. Héðinn fishmeal plant an Icelandic fishmeal plant producer states, for example, in 2017, that this value may be cut down to 20kg oil per ton raw material by reusing energy sources. In comparison this would translate to roughly 44-16 kg of natural gas but this of course is very dependent upon the design chosen and how excess energy sources are utilised along with insulation.

Crude oil costs around 65 USD per barrel which is close to 400 EUR per ton oil and the power cost in Greece was 0.107 EUR/kWh in 2017 for non-home uses (Bloomberg, 2017). According to Table 30, the electric cost is only one fifth of what it would be if oil was used. For that reason and others, electricity is preferred.

Table 30. Comparison of electrical and crude oil consumption for all the four plants and the energy cost for each.

	Athens		Thessaloniki & Kavala	
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Annual oil consumption (ton)	349	188	524	282
Fuel cost	139.768 EUR	75.260 EUR	209.652 EUR	112.889 EUR
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Natural gas consumption (ton)	280	151	419	226
Electricity cost	195.675 EUR	105.363 EUR	293.512 EUR	158.045 EUR
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Electric power consumption (kWh)	222.358	119.731	333.537	179.597
Electricity cost	23.792 EUR	12.811 EUR	35.688 EUR	19.217 EUR

Labour cost

It is essential to have at least one manager with supervision over each processing plant. He should take care of the staff, sales and the overall management. Regarding the number of other employees, fishmeal plants with production capacity around 70 tons/24h will require on average 3-5 employees on each shift depending on the working conditions and the qualification of the staff. There must be at least one employee with technical background of some kind, he must be able to take measurements from oils, press cake, fishmeal and other production streams to ensure the best quality. In addition, he must be able to service the equipment and act when failures occur. He must have gotten education on fishmeal production and should have experience and knowledge on the equipment. It would be required that he had mechanical or engineering background. There are many other procedures that require employees. The fishmeal is packed in large bulk bags which are filled in a specific packing unit which weighs up the meal as well. The fishmeal bags are then removed by forklift and stacked in the storage hold. This operation may require two employees as one performs the stacking while the other has control over the process. Table 31 shows the annual labour cost for each processing plant. The average labour cost per hour is 15 EUR/h according to aerostat 2016. These plants are normally operated 24h.

Table 31. Annual labour cost for each processing plant

	Number of employees (24h)	Labour cost per-hour (EUR)	Annual labour cost (EUR)
<i>Athens</i>	10	15	657.000
<i>Thessaloniki and Kavala</i>	10	15	-
Sum	20		1.314.000

Chemical cost

Additions of antioxidant chemicals is essential to preserve reactive fishmeal and to prevent deterioration of the material. It also reduces the risk of fire, since fishmeal can be flammable do to oxidation. Ethoxyquin is an example of antioxidant commonly used for fishmeal. It is used in the proportion around 0.02 % of the fishmeal weight (FAO, 1986). The price of ethoxyquin is around 4.2 EUR per kg.

Packaging cost

The fishmeal is packed in 1.2 square meter bulk bags and the oil is put in one cubic meter IBC storage tanks. To determine the total volume and number of containers, densities for fishmeal and oil are used. The density for fishmeal is 0.59 ton per cubic meter and 0.92 for fish oil.

Depreciation

It is assumed that the equipment will depreciate down to 30% of its original value in 20 years which corresponds to an annual discount rate of 5.8%.

Insurance

The annual cost of insurance is 2% of the investment cost which is a value used by FAO in one of their cost estimations for fishmeal plants (FAO, 1986).

Repairs and maintenance

Repairs and maintenance are a standard factor in the operation of fishmeal plants. Spare parts are expensive as well as hourly wages by specialized experts. These factors are expected to count for 5% of the total investment cost annually (FAO, 1986).

Other variable cost

Many expenses can be overseen; therefore, it is assumed for variable expenses which count for 15% of the total variable cost.

6.2.4 Profit and loss account

Table 32 shows the estimated annual profit loss account for the four suggested fishmeal plants, according to the above-mentioned assumptions. The results show that the suggestion is not profitable and there is annual loss of the operations.

Table 32. Annual profit loss account for the suggested fishmeal and fish-oil plants

	Athens		Thessaloniki & Kavala	
	Plant 1 Lean fish	Plant 2 Fatty fish	Plant 1 Lean fish	Plant 2 Fatty fish
Raw material (ton)	6.353	3.421	9.530	5.131
Revenue	2.036.452 €	1.318.913 €	3.054.678 €	1.978.370 €
Raw material cost	814.581 €	527.565 €	1.221.871 €	791.348 €
Energy cost	23.792 €	12.811 €	35.688 €	19.217 €
Packaging cost	37.941 €	20.430 €	56.912 €	30.645 €
Chemical cost	306 €	132 €	459 €	198 €
Labor Cost	328.500 €	328.500 €	328.500 €	328.500 €
Transportation	571.778 €	307.880 €	857.666 €	461.820 €
Other variable cost	180.768 €	133.416 €	246.515 €	175.486 €
Variable cost	1.957.666 €	1.330.734 €	2.747.611 €	1.807.214 €
<i>Investment cost</i>	<i>4.000.000 €</i>	<i>3.500.000 €</i>	<i>4.200.000 €</i>	<i>3.500.000 €</i>
<i>EC Subsidy 50% on equipment</i>	<i>2.000.000 €</i>	<i>1.750.000 €</i>	<i>2.100.000 €</i>	<i>1.750.000 €</i>
Final Investment cost	2.000.000 €	1.750.000 €	2.100.000 €	1.750.000 €
Insurance	80.000 €	70.000 €	84.000 €	70.000 €
Repairs	200.000 €	175.000 €	210.000 €	175.000 €
Depreciation	60.000 €	52.500 €	63.000 €	52.500 €
Fixed cost	340.000 €	297.500 €	357.000 €	297.500 €
Net profit	- 261.214 €	- 309.321 €	- 49.933 €	- 126.344 €
Tax (29%)				
Profit	- 261.214 €	- 309.321 €	- 49.933 €	- 126.344 €
Profit sum	-	570.535 €	-	176.277 €

6.3 Silage production

The second suggestion for Greece, involves making fish silage out of the UUC, RRM and other wasted materials. Three reception stations will be located in the ports of Athens, Thessaloniki (Nea Michaniona) and in Kavala, where the raw material will be gathered. Each, fish market, merchant, fish processor or fishermen will have equipment on location for mincing and acidifying the raw material. These stakeholders will prepare so called preserved silage which will then be gathered in larger silage stations. The reason for this, is that, transportation cost is considerable for silage, since it takes up so large volumes due to high water content. For that reason, it is best if the removal of moisture can occur as early as possible in the value chain, as an effort to reduce transportation cost. This arrangement will not only save up cost in transportation but will help to make more commercial products out of the silage since it is found in much larger quantities in one location. This creates stability for processors and will make it easier to developed more innovative products.

Figure 72: The suggested locations for silage reception stations

Despite all the opportunities that lie in the silage industry and all the valuable products which can be produced such as, pharmaceuticals, protein powder, supplements, omega-3 or cosmetics, this suggestion, proposes to sell the silage into the fishmeal industry, at least to begin with. All businesses must have stable and secure turnover to run, and when the relationship between the stakeholders that provide the raw material and the industry has strengthened, more innovative products could be developed. There are currently no fish meal plants in Greece and until then, the industry may have to rely on more traditional methods to build up the industry.

As with the previous suggestion, fatty fish and lean fish species shall be kept separated, thus making two types if silage. This will expand the usability of the silage and especially if it is intended in fishmeal, since fishmeal is categorised by meal made from fatty fish or lean fish. Fishmeal and silage as well, are however priced by the protein content, but it is always stated whether meal is from fatty fish or lean fish since meal produced from fatty fish is usually fatter an there is a higher risk of rancidity in such meal.

6.3.1 Investment costs

The investment needed for the silage production is twofold. Firstly, it is the investment in small-scale silage units all around the country, and secondly it is the investment in the reception stations. The small-scale silage units are small portable units which consist of mincer, acid blender and computers around that, heat exchangers and two storage tanks for each unit to separate fatty fish species and lean fish. These units can be fitted inside shipping containers and or on board vessels.

The three reception stations however, have to be much larger. These are stations constructed with lot of storage tanks in different sizes to be able to separate between fatty and lean fish species and categorise them after age as well. Along with that, these plants should be equipped with

centrifuges for separation of oil from the silage to make de-oiled silage and fish oil. This requires investment in tricanter centrifuges along with heat exchangers for more successful separation. After de-oiling, the water phase or the stick water, should be thickened in evaporators to retrieve excess proteins. Table 33 shows the investment cost for the portable silage making units and Table 34 show the investment in the reception stations. It is assumed that the portable units have capacity of 8 tons per 24h.

Table 33. Investment in small portable silage units

	Number of small scale silage units	Investment cost (EUR)	Total investment
<i>Athens</i>	8	65.000	520.000
<i>Thessaloniki</i>	4	65.000	260.000
<i>Kavala</i>	8	65.000	520.000
Sum	20		1.300.000

Table 34. Investment cost for the reception stations on each location

	Production capacity (ton/24h)	Total investment
<i>Athens</i>	38	1.650.000
<i>Thessaloniki</i>	28	1.300.000
<i>Kavala</i>	28	1.650.000
Sum	94	4.600.000

As previously mentioned, the European Commission, can offer funding via the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF), where companies can get access to funding in the form of subsidies if they meet certain conditions. In this Greek case, these subsidies could potentially be more than 50% of the total investment.

6.3.2 Revenues

Generally, the same method is used for evaluating the prices of silage as with fishmeal. The chemical composition is analysed and evaluated in context with the amount of proteins and oil within the material. However, if it is assumed that the silage will be sold as a raw material into a fishmeal plant an additional factor has to be considered, which is, that fishmeal processor will not buy in raw material on the same price as they sell the final product. The rule of thumb in these plants, is that the cost of raw material accounts approximately 40% of the revenue. By using this assumption, the revenue of silage that is sold to a fishmeal processor can be determined by multiplying the calculated value with 40%. However, since the reception station separate the oil

from the raw material they can sell the fish oil for higher prices. The revenue and the amount of raw material, fishmeal and fish oil can be seen in Table 35.

Table 35. Mass balance and revenue calculations for the three suggested silage units

	Silage - Mass balance					
	Athens		Thessaloniki		Kavala	
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Raw material (ton)	6353	3421	4765	2566	4765	2566
<i>Ton/day</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>7</i>
Moisture (%)	75,0%	73,0%	75,0%	73,0%	75,0%	73,0%
Fat (%)	3,0%	10,0%	3,0%	10,0%	3,0%	10,0%
Protein (%)	17,0%	16,0%	17,0%	16,0%	17,0%	16,0%
Other (%)	5,1%	1,4%	5,1%	1,4%	5,1%	1,4%
FFDM (%)	22,1%	17,4%	22,1%	17,4%	22,1%	17,4%
	100%	100%				
Moisture (ton)	3501	2009	2626	1507	2626	1507
Moisture (%)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Fat (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Protein (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Other (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
FFDM (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Fish oil (ton)	50	235	38	176	38	176
Moisture (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Fat (%)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Protein (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Other (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
FFDM (%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
De-oiled/thickened Silage	2808	1190	2106	893	2106	893
Moisture (%)	45,0%	41,0%	45,0%	41,0%	45,0%	41,0%
Fat (%)	5,0%	9,0%	5,0%	9,0%	5,0%	9,0%
Protein (%)	38,5%	46,0%	38,5%	46,0%	38,5%	46,0%
Other (%)	11,5%	4,0%	11,5%	4,0%	11,5%	4,0%
FFDM (%)	50,0%	50,0%	50,0%	50,0%	50,0%	50,0%
Fishmeal Revenue	1.233.820 EUR	625.284 EUR	925.365 EUR	468.963 EUR	925.365 EUR	468.963 EUR
Fish oil Revenue	64.546 EUR	302.153 EUR	48.410 EUR	226.615 EUR	48.410 EUR	226.615 EUR
Revenue	1.298.366 EUR	927.438 EUR	973.774 EUR	695.578 EUR	973.774 EUR	695.578 EUR
Sum	2.225.803 EUR		1.669.353 EUR		1.669.353 EUR	
Fishmeal price	1344	EUR/ per ton fishmeal 65% protein				
Fishmeal protein price	2068	EUR/ per ton fishmeal 100% protein				
Fish oil prices	1513	EUR/ per ton fish oil				
Production Efficiency	85%	Affects ther revenue				

6.3.3 Operating costs

The costs associated with the operation of the silage systems are variable; ranging from energy costs, chemical costs, labour costs, packaging costs, maintenance costs etc. Following is a short overview of the main operational cost items.

Raw material cost

As with suggestion 1. The raw material cost is assumed to be 40% of the final total revenue of the silage. This corresponds to roughly 0,09 EUR per kg raw material.

Energy cost

It can be difficult to determine the actual energy usage of the silage process and the amount of energy needed in the evaporation process. It is determined by the equipment in question and how many evaporation stages are built in the design. The energy usage will however, in most cases, not exceed one third of what would be required in a fishmeal factory. These numbers correlate to around 12 kWh per ton raw material. The total power consumption is seen in Table 36.

Table 36. Energy consumption and cost on each location

	Athens		Thessaloniki		Kavala	
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Fatty fish	Fatty fish
Electric power consumption (kWh)	76.237	41.051	57.178	30.788	57.178	30.788
Electricity cost	8.157 EUR	4.392 EUR	6.118 EUR	3.294 EUR	6.118 EUR	3.294 EUR

Labour cost

These calculations do not assume that the merchants or all the stakeholders on the fishing ports retrieve any salary. This labour cost only applies to the reception station and the staff that is working there. There must be a supervisor in each plant with management over the sales and the production. This kind of production requires on average 2 employees on each shift.

The average labour cost per hour is 15 EUR/h according to Eurostat 2016. These plants are normally operated 24h. The annual labour cost for each processing plant are shown in Table 37.

Table 37. Annual labour cost for each processing plant

	Number of employees (24h)	Labour cost per-hour (EUR)	Annual labour cost (EUR)
<i>Athens</i>	6	15	394.200
<i>Thessaloniki</i>	6	15	394.200
<i>Kavala</i>	6	15	394.200
Sum	18		1.182.600

The transportation cost

The transportation cost is extremely difficult to be determined beforehand since many variables are unknown, such as distances, type of transportation, how frequently the material is picked up and so on. However, according to a report made by the Mediterranean Advisory Council, an average cost for handling and transporting fish to an animal feed processing plant in Greece is about 90 EUR / ton (MEDAC, 2016).

Chemical cost

Generally formic acid is used to lower the pH, but other acids such as sulfuric acids have been used as well. Formic acid should be used in the proportions 3,5% in cases where whole fish is being

processed but this value may be lowered in the case of guts. Formic acid can cost up to 800 EUR per metric ton (Alibaba, 2018).

As with fishmeal, addition of antioxidant chemicals is used to prevent deterioration of the material. It is used in the proportion 0.02 % of the silage weight (Winter & Feltam, 1983). The price of ethoxyquin is around 4.2 EUR per kg.

Packaging cost

The silage is not put in specific packaging, but oil is put in one cubic meter IBC storage tanks.

Depreciation

It is assumed that the equipment will depreciate down to 30% of its original value in 20 years which corresponds to an annual discount rate of 5.8%.

Insurance

The annual cost of insurance is 2% of the investment cost which is a value used by FAO in one of their cost estimations for fishmeal plants (FAO, 1986).

Repairs and maintenance

Repairs and maintenance are a standard factor in the operation of fishmeal plants. Spare parts are expensive as well as hourly wages by specialized experts. These factors are expected to count for 5% of the total investment cost annually (FAO, 1986).

Other variable cost

Many expenses can be overseen; therefore, it is assumed for variable expenses which count for 15% of the total variable cost.

6.3.4 Profit and loss account

The profit and loss account for the suggested solutions can be seen in Table 38.

Table 38. Annual profit loss account for the suggested silage processing solution.

	Athens		Thessaloniki		Kavala	
	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish	Lean fish	Fatty fish
Raw material (ton)	6.353	3.421	4.765	2.566	4.765	2.566
Revenue	1.298.366 €	927.438 €	973.774 €	695.578 €	973.774 €	695.578 €
Raw material cost	519.346 €	370.975 €	389.510 €	278.231 €	389.510 €	278.231 €
Energy cost	8.157 €	4.392 €	6.118 €	3.294 €	6.118 €	3.294 €
Packaging cost	27.622 €	14.873 €	20.717 €	11.155 €	20.717 €	11.155 €
Chemical cost	79.142 €	33.552 €	59.357 €	25.164 €	59.357 €	25.164 €
Labor Cost	197.100 €	197.100 €	197.100 €	197.100 €	197.100 €	197.100 €
Transportation	571.778 €	307.880 €	428.833 €	230.910 €	428.833 €	230.910 €
Other variable cost	124.705 €	93.134 €	100.920 €	77.242 €	100.920 €	77.242 €
Variable cost	1.527.851 €	1.021.907 €	1.202.555 €	823.097 €	1.202.555 €	823.097 €
<i>Investment cost</i>	<i>2.170.000 €</i>		<i>1.560.000 €</i>		<i>2.170.000 €</i>	
<i>EC Subsidy 50% on equipment</i>	<i>1.085.000 €</i>		<i>780.000 €</i>		<i>1.085.000 €</i>	
Final Investment cost	1.085.000 €		780.000 €		1.085.000 €	
Insurance	21.700 €	21.700 €	15.600 €	15.600 €	21.700 €	21.700 €
Repairs	54.250 €	54.250 €	39.000 €	39.000 €	54.250 €	54.250 €
Depreciation	16.275 €	16.275 €	11.700 €	11.700 €	16.275 €	16.275 €
Fixed cost	92.225 €	92.225 €	66.300 €	66.300 €	92.225 €	92.225 €
Net profit	- 321.710 €	- 186.695 €	- 295.080 €	- 193.819 €	- 321.005 €	- 219.744 €
Tax (29%)						
Profit	- 321.710 €	- 186.695 €	- 295.080 €	- 193.819 €	- 321.005 €	- 219.744 €
Profit sum	- 508.405 €		- 488.899 €		- 540.749 €	

6.4 Sensitivity analyses

The above results show annual loss on both operations, fishmeal and silage. The two largest cost factors in both cases are transportation and raw material cost. The transportation cost is a fixed number 90 EUR per ton raw material and the raw material cost is fixed percentage of the total revenue of sold silage, fish oil and fishmeal or 40%.

Raw material cost

This 40% results in 0,14 EUR/kg raw material sold to fishmeal and 0,09 EUR/kg if sold to silage and is the price that the stakeholders can sell their product on. If this raw material cost is lowered significantly these cases may become profitable. However, the problem is, that there will not be any raw material to process if the stakeholders won't get a good incentive to collect these raw materials. The following Figure 73, describes the sensitivity between raw material prices and annual profit. This shows that if this operation is not to return annual loss, the raw material cost cannot exceed 0,1 EUR/kg for suggestion 1 and 0,03 EUR/kg for suggestion 2.

Figure 73 Sensitivity between annual Net profit/loss before taxes and raw material prices

Transportation cost

According to average data from Greece on transporting fish and fish waste to an animal feed processing plant is 90 EUR / ton (MEDAC, 2016) making it the largest cost in both suggestion. However, if this cost can be cut down to less than 60 EUR/ ton suggestion 1 becomes profitable and around 20 EUR/ton for suggestion 2, Figure 74.

Figure 74 Sensitivity between annual Net profit/loss before taxes and transportation cost

Raw material

Stable access to raw material is very critical, if not enough raw-material is available, the production will stop, and the staff still needs to get paid. The following Figure 75 shows how changes in raw-material supply and the effect on the operation. If the raw material supply increase by roughly 40% the fishmeal suggestion 1 becomes profitable or at least it stops retuning annual loss. If, however the volumes are reduced the loss only gets bigger.

Figure 75 Sensitivity between annual Net profit/loss before taxes and changes in raw material supply

6.5 Summary

The major finding of this work is that it is not profitable to gather material for either fishmeal processing or silage making as proposed in suggestion 1 and 2. The fishmeal suggestion 1 return -746.812 EUR annual loss and the silage suggestion 2 return -1.538.052 EUR annual loss. Transportation cost is considerable, and the fishing ports are scattered over large area which forces them to transport little amounts over large distances. Fresh fish or rest raw materials need frequent pick up to make sure that they don't go ruined and that quality is maintained.

The second largest cost factor is raw material cost, which is what stakeholders, fisherman or merchants get for their raw material, this is their incentive to collect this material. The raw material cost was calculated 40% of the total revenue of silage, fish oil and fishmeal or 0,14 EUR/kg raw material sold to fishmeal and 0,09 EUR/kg if sold to silage. This may seem a fair price but is however too high for the overall operation. A series of sensitivity analyses showed that this price would need to be reduced to 0,10-0.12 EUR/kg raw material sold to fishmeal and 0,03 EUR/kg for the overall operation to start running minimum profit.

Despite the silage giving off less revenue and more loss annually it is effective material wise and easier to store and maintain quality wise before processing. In this scenario, it might prove

difficult to gather fresh material from several stakeholders and be certain that the raw material qualities are maintained. With fishmeal being dependent upon various quality factors affecting the chemical properties, this might present an obstacle. The limiting factor for the silage suggestion is that the operation cost is simply too high compared to the. One alternative, as an effort to reduce the operation cost would be to narrow the reception station for silage down to one station located in middle of these three suggested stations. This would however mean much more transportation, but it would be interesting to further explore whether it's economical. There are still some unexplored possibilities in silage which can present opportunities for further process development and innovation to give off better products. The suggested silage solution in this work, anticipated that the raw silage would be sold to the fishmeal producers to ensure stable operational conditions. Silage can however, be utilized to make a wide variety of products, such as oil, supplements and cosmetics. Furthermore, it can be used to make more commercial products such as fish feed pellets out of thickened silage blended with grain or starch. The latter processing has been steadily becoming more prominent due to lower energy consumption compared to a standard process involving fish meal as well as the material gets heated less during this process, making it gentler with regards to the overall protein composition. These factors along with others, including transportation cost of the raw material and the product itself will have to be taken into consideration when deciding best practices for a streamlined and practical process.

In the making of any business plan, regardless of whether the bases for the business are known or not, many assumptions need to be established. The above-mentioned assumptions made in this work have different sensitivities towards different external factors such as market condition or even stock size at any given time. The parameter that is the most sensitive in this case however, is the amount of raw material from markets and fishermen which can greatly affect the bases of this kind of processing. In this regard, it will be interesting to see how landing volumes of non-commercial species (i.e. UUC) will develop parallel to the discard ban (a very critical and necessary condition for Greece and the Mediterranean Sea in general) and how new technology and fishing practices can affect the composition of the catch. It is not unlikely that these volumes can be reduced in near future (through selectivity improvement) which can create more challenges for this kind of operation.

Table 39 Combined annual profit loss account for the two suggestions

	Suggestion 1. Fishmeal production	Suggestion 2. Silage production
Raw material (ton)	24.435	24.435
Revenue	8.388.414 €	5.564.508 €
Raw material cost	3.355.365 €	2.225.803 €
Energy cost	91.509 €	31.374 €
Packaging cost	145.928 €	106.239 €
Chemical cost	1.094 €	281.737 €
Labor Cost	1.314.000 €	1.182.600 €
Transportation	2.199.144 €	2.199.144 €
Other variable cost	736.185 €	574.163 €
Variable cost	7.843.226 €	6.601.061 €
<i>Investment cost</i>	15.200.000 €	5.900.000 €
<i>EC Subsidy 50% on equipment</i>	7.600.000 €	2.950.000 €
Final Investment cost	7.600.000 €	2.950.000 €
Insurance	304.000 €	118.000 €
Repairs	760.000 €	295.000 €
Depreciation	228.000 €	88.500 €
Fixed cost	1.292.000 €	501.500 €
Net profit	- 746.812 €	- 1.538.052 €
Tax (29%)		- €
Profit	- 746.812 €	- 1.538.052 €

Figure 76. Different representation of the annual profit loss account for the two suggestions

The investment cost in equipment for fishmeal production, is considerably higher compared to what is needed for making silage. The process requires more staff, maintenance and energy but the product, the fish powder is quite well known and returns stable revenue. The silage processing however, is slightly riskier, since the product has not yet become as commercial around the world as fishmeal powder.

The current EMFF provides support for establishments of utilising discards and UUC that can even reach subsidies of 100% if the action is driven by collective fishermen initiatives and serve a collective interest and have a collective beneficiary and innovative characteristics. It is evident that eventually someone has to pay the costs for a discard ban and real life shows that a realistic solution must engage the fishermen if one would like to have access to the raw material. So far, the private sector is unwilling to invest and our cost estimations further support this unwillingness. Therefore, it seems that only collective fishermen initiatives and EU funding could make the LO to work in Greece and in the Mediterranean Sea in general.

6.6 Appendices

The following are some technical and practical aspects of fishmeal and silage production, which describes the process in more detail.

6.6.1 Fishmeal production

The fishmeal and fish oil processing can in principle be simplified to, removing moisture from the raw material and separating oil and dry matter. Many different versions of processing plants are available today, some are more complex while others are built up on simplified principles and methodologies. These simpler versions take up less space and are less expensive. However, there is a dispute about its efficiency and impact on quality. Recent experiments that were conducted at Matis, where few, once considered crucial production assumptions were altered, showed little as no effect on quality.

The production of fishmeal and fish oil first started on industrial scale in northern Europe and North America, in the 19th century. The production process has developed enormously since then, where centrifugation technology's and other methods have replaced older and more outdated methodology's. For example, with separation liquids and oils, where the original method was to let the oil clear by gravity and time, producers can now perform such an operation with centrifuges within few minutes increasing the production capacity enormously. The production plants have improved on most levels, they have become more energy efficient with higher utilization efficiency's and much more stable production. However, criticism amongst engineers and plants designers has raised in the past years, and especially regarding smaller production systems. They claim that the industry has not followed up with the current technological development and that most plants being produced today are built up on technology developed in the sixties. They also claim that the temperatures used in heating have been weigh too high and that the process will need a total revision and the hole system needs to be rethought.

The traditional fishmeal processes

The traditional fishmeal plant refers to the most common arrangement in larger fishmeal factories in the past century. The material is minced and headed for more successful separation of press liquor and press cake and to further improve the separation in the centrifuges later. After pressing of the material in screw press, liquor is squeezed out of the material leaving press cake with around 50% dry matter and press liquor containing moisture, soluble proteins and fat. The press liquor is sent through intensive centrifugation to separate oils and stick water. The stick water then goes to special evaporators to retrieve the proteins. The press cake is then blended with the sludge from the first decanter and the stick water concentrate from the evaporator. The production arrangement can be seen on Figure 77 along with the production streams.

Figure 77. Main processes of producing fishmeal and oil.

Mincing: Feeding screw feeds the material into a mincer which evenly tears the material into the right particle size. This is however dependent on the raw material as whole fish requires mincing while other materials such as offal's should preferably not be minced (FAO, 1986).

Heating: The heating process is carried out to extract the oils and moisture from the material for better sieving as well as to inactivate bacteria, viruses and parasites that can ruin the material.

The temperature of the heating process has gained increased discussion in the past decade, research has for example shown that the fat cells are broken down before the temperature reaches 50 °C and that coagulation of proteins occurs around 75 °C quite rapidly (Ruiter, 1995) (FAO, 1986). And theoretically there should be no reason to heat the material above that as has been done for centuries in the industry, where optimal temperature has been considered 100 °C (FAO, 1986). It should although be mentioned that the temperature is also dependent upon the components within the plant as some separators require more heating of the material. Higher temperatures can also be used to speed up the heating and heating above 75 °C can therefore be accepted in some cases.

Most common cookers used in the fishmeal industry are steam or water heated. The steam can be retrieved directly from electric or fuel steam kettles and or reused dryers or evaporators. For that matter, pre-cookers are commonly used to retrieve the excess vapor or condensate to contribute to better energy efficiency.

Straining: The straining procedure is conducted to increase the compressibility of the material before pressing, promoting lower moisture and oil content. Straining is most often conducted after the heating procedure where oils and water are more soluble. By removing liquor and oils earlier in the process will ensure better pressing and less energy needed to dry the considerably wetter material (FAO, 1986). The material is separated down to two streams; press liquor and wet press cake.

Pressing: After the straining process, the wet press cake is fed into a press which squeezes the rest of the liquids out of the material. The press cake is then ready for drying while the press liquor goes into further processing or is discarded into the ocean, which is not preferred. Screw presses

are standard component in the fishmeal industry. The most common is the twin-screw press but presses with one screw are also available. Twin screw press consists of two screws that rotate in opposite direction. The structure of the press ensures that the material is pressed and does not rotate along with the screw.

Decanter centrifugation of solids: Decanter centrifuges are used to remove solid particles from the press liquor. Two phase horizontal decanter centrifuges use rotational forces that can be over 3000 times greater than the force of gravity. They are constructed as a horizontal cylinder with a bowl in one end where the solid phase is collected and discharged and with a rotational screw/scroll conveyor in the middle to feed the solid phase further into the bowl. The sludge is brought in at the opposite end through piping and enters the cylinder in the middle (Figure 78).

In theory, the larger solid particles with higher density are pressed outwards against the rotating bowl in the end of the centrifuge under the force of gravity. Meanwhile, the less dense liquid forms a concentric inner layer which expels towards the liquid outlet. Thus, the solids are pressed into the bowl and liquid in the opposite direction due to rotational forces. This can be obtained by the bowl shape at the other end of the centrifuge. The solids are removed by cylindrical discharger which rotates at greater speed than the bowl itself. The solid phase is discharged by a dam which ensures fullness of the centrifuge. The outflow can therefore be controlled by the rotation speed of the solid discharger. Moreover, the speed of the screw/scroll conveyor can be controlled to adjust the solid load.

Figure 78. Horizontal decanter centrifuge (Flottweg, n.d.)

Centrifugation of liquids: Centrifugation of liquids include the process of separating stick water and the oils. This is most often conducted in vertical centrifuges, either a nozzle type which operates continuously or a self-cleaning one which requires fresh water supply (FAO, 1986). The liquor sludge is then fed into the evaporator system while the oil is lead into further polishing. The oil can go through several stages of centrifugation before it enters the oil polishing. It's a matter of the degree of processing, how far the producer wants to go. In onshore plants, it's common to have several stages of centrifugation before evaporation. It's not so common on offshore plants as limiting factors as space on board and high energy cost may affect the design. Oil polishers are nevertheless becoming more common on offshore plants to purify the oil. They retrieve crude oil from decanters, tricanter or from other centrifuges, depending on the plant's design. It's worth mentioning that oil polishers, other centrifuges and decanters require buffer tanks. These

components operate continuously, and erratic input can affect the material quality. Oil polishers and other centrifuges moreover require material to be heated up to 95-90 °C to help with the separation and purity of the product.

Nozzle-type centrifuge is a vertical centrifuge which discharges continuously. The light dense/density liquid (oil) is forced at the centre and is discharged in the upper part of the centrifuge. The higher dense liquid (water) is accumulated to the outer surface through discs and discharged on the lower part of the centrifuge depending on the design. The main principle is that they discharge continuously (Pigott, 1967). Three phase nozzle type centrifuges are also available, they are designed to separate stick water oils and sludge at the same time (Arason S. , 2001).

Self-cleaning centrifuge is a vertical centrifuge which discharges intermittently. The stick water is fed into the inlet at the bottom or the top. The light dense liquor is forced to the centre and the higher dense to the outside. The main difference is that the discharge outlet for the higher dens (sludge) liquid is not open always but has a piston that controls the discharge. When the piston is closed, the lower dens liquid is therefore discharged. Water injection is used to open the piston and when it is drained it closes (Pigott, 1967).

Oil polishers are used on the final refining stage to clear the oil. A buffer tank is placed in front of the polisher to ensure constant inflow of crude oil, but they are often equipped with some sort of heating elements to ensure 90-95 °C hot material. Oil polishers are technically constructed as a self-cleaning centrifuge. However, their design needs to consider different particle sizes. Oil polishers moreover require hot water to be ejected into the crude oil for more effective separation. Common practice when the piston is opened for solids, is to circulate portion of the oil back into the buffer tank before and after each opening to prevent excess water and solids from going with the oil (Arason, 2001).

Evaporation: After separation of solids in decanters or other centrifuges, large portion of the oils and solids have already been removed from the press liquor. The next step is to process the excess stick water which undergoes evaporation for thickening to retrieve extra yield. Even though stick water contains low portion of solids (6-9%), it is estimated that it can hold up 20% of the final weight of the fishmeal. The stick water contains compounds as dissolved and suspended proteins, minerals, residual oils, vitamins and amines/ammonia. Evaporation of stick water is highly energy demanding and in effort to reduce the energy cost, evaporators can be constructed in series, called multiple effect evaporators. The main principle is that steam is used on the first stage to evaporate and the vapor that comes out is used as a source of heat for the next evaporator. Thus, they can reuse the heat source at different stages with different evaporation temperature. The excess vapor that comes out of the last stage can moreover be used for other purposes in the plant such as preheating of the material.

Four stage multi effect evaporators are common in onshore plants. Having more stages is not preferred as it will require too high temperatures in the first stages (Arason, 2001).

When it comes to choosing the proper evaporator, many possibilities arise. Stick water is relatively heat sensitive and can be quite viscous on the last stages so evaporators should be

chosen with that in mind. Another thing to consider is the space requirement, since available space on board can be a limiting factor.

Common evaporators used for this purpose are long tube vertical evaporators constructed either as falling film or rising film type, plate evaporators are which require less space compared to the tower ones and mechanical vapor recompression evaporators (MVR) is another alternative. The advantage of the MPV is low energy cost.

Drying: In principle, two types dryers are most common in the fishmeal industry. It is the indirect steam dryer and the direct air dryer. The main difference between the two dryers is the convection used. The indirect steam dryer uses hot steam to heat up the contact surface, this can be heated tubes, discs, coils, etc. The material is heated in contact with the heated surface, leading to evaporation of the moisture within, while air is blown through the dryer in opposite direction with the material to capture the vapor. The steam dryer is constructed with heated screw in the middle which serves as conveyor, heat source and ensures blending of the material (FAO, 1986). The direct air dryer uses hot air for the convection which can be extracted through heat exchanger or directly from fire. The convection through air contributes to more efficient mass transfer which reflects in shorter holding time. The disadvantage is that when heat is directly extracted from fire, hazardous chemicals from the fuel can contaminate the material (FAO, 1986). Indirect steam dryers are most common today, that is partly due to their ability to process large quantities with relatively simple equipment and lower installation cost. They do not require extensive air cleaning, and the fishmeal becomes less dusty than in the direct ones which makes them more acceptable for mink feeding. Indirect steam dryers also allow for renewal of the steam and vapor which can be used for preheating or other purposes in the plant. They do not necessarily require pre-blending of the stick water concentrate and the press cake, due to constant circulation of the material in the dryer (FAO, 1986).

Cooling: When the dried material leaves the dryer, it is at temperatures around 80 °C. The air within holds a lot of moisture that needs to be removed as quickly as possible, otherwise the material can absorb that moisture resulting in higher water activity which can have negative effects on the material quality. Cooling the material before it enters the milling procedure also helps with successful milling. The cooling will reduce the moisture content by 1-2%, making fishmeal with desired water content in the range between 9-11 % (Arason, 2001).

Milling: After the cooling procedure, the dried material undergoes milling to retrieve homogeneous particle size.

Simplified versions

As mentioned, there is wide variety of fishmeal and fish oil plants. However, when speaking of simplified versions, that most often means, that the evaporator has been omitted. When that has been done, there are only three options left, firstly to discard the otherwise evaporated stick water after clarifying the oil, which means discard of up to 20% of the initial protein source. Secondly, to only mince the material and then dry it, this only applies for lean fish with fat content below 3%. Thirdly, to blend the stick water with the press cake and dry it altogether in two stage dryers. This version, seen on Figure 79, is maybe the most reasonable as it fully utilises the material and nothing is discarded. The disadvantage however, is that the press cake is much wetter and will require more and longer heating of the material which can affect quality of proteins.

Figure 79. Simplified version of fishmeal and fish oil plant that is without evaporators for stick water. The stick water goes through the dryer along with the press cake

Mincer: As with other fishmeal plants, mincing is required.

Heating: The heating procedure can be performed in steam heated screw snail or pipe heat exchanger. The latter, takes up less space and is easier to clean in most cases. A piston or a pump feeds the minced material into the heater.

Tricanter: The tricanter centrifuge is one of the most important equipment in the plant. It separates oil, stick water and press cake. Three-phase horizontal tricanter centrifuges have similar structure and function as the decanter centrifuges. Their alternative is that they can separate the material down to three material streams. The one with the highest density, the press cake, the stick water in the middle and oil with the lowest density. The same principle applies as the solids are separated with pressure in a bowl but unlike the two-phase decanters, the middle dens liquids (the water) are discharged by pressure as well (Flottweg, n.d.). The lower dens liquid (oil) is forced to the inner surface of the screw by rotation and the higher dens liquid (water) is forced to the outer surface of the bowl. Thus, they can be discharged separately. These two liquids are not always in the same proportions which can promote challenges. For that purpose, adjustable impellers have been developed. They control the diameter of the two liquid outlets which helps with controlling the separation of different materials (Flottweg, n.d.).

These centrifuges have been gaining more and more interest and especially as replacement for the main screw press in smaller fishmeal plants (Gíslason, et al., 2014). This arrangement may however, present both advantages and disadvantages for the whole production. Firstly, the advantage of using decanter centrifuges is the simplification of the production process, they are compact, with more controllable separation compared with presses and sieves, faster separation, promote better hygiene and easier cleaning of the components. Most important though is their ability to process soft and very fluid material, where the press would fail. However, they have their disadvantages as well, which is press cake with higher moisture content, if the centrifuge is used instead of traditional screw press, and more soluble fines in the stick water which may call for more intensive oil polishing. Higher moisture content will moreover lead to more energy consumption in the dryer (FAO, 1986).

Dryer: Understanding the drying process and its effects on the material properties is crucial for successful drying practices. In the drying of material, whether it is a direct or indirect drying, the material undergoes two processes:

Process no. 1- the removal of moisture from the outer surface of the material. The removal is dependent on factors such as air humidity, air flow, pressure and the surface area of the material (Mujumdar, 1987).

Process no. 2- the transport of moisture within the material to the outer surface. This transfer is dependent upon the material properties, temperature, time and the moisture content (Mujumdar, 1987).

At the first stages of the drying when the press cake is relatively wet, the removal of moisture occurs at a higher speed than at the last stages when the moisture content has decreased. That is mainly due to process no. 2 since the transfer of moisture within the material becomes a limiting factor. According to Arason, the drying rate of minced fish starts to decrease when the moisture content reaches 30 to 40%, this can be seen on Figure 80 which shows the drying curve and how the removal of moisture behaves by time (Arason, 2013). To take advantage of this the material can be transferred into secondary dryer at this point, which operates on lower temperatures, since the drying rate will become more dependent upon time. This arrangement moreover allows for renewal of energy from hot material vapor coming from the pre-dryer, which can be used to power the last stage of drying.

Figure 80 Drying curve (Myrvang, Strømman, & Jonassen, 2007)

Cooling and milling: As with every other fishmeal plant its essential to cool the meal before, prior or after the milling. This is done to reduce the water activity and the moisture content since the air around the material holds a lot of moisture.

6.6.2 Silage production

Silage preservation and/or production of fully prepared silage is one of the potential methods to reduce discard and waste in the marine industry today. The procedure is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra effort of employees compared to other methods. The raw material is acidified which not only increases the shelf life of the material but allows it to be stored at room temperatures for more than a year with little reduction on quality.

To further define between silage preservation and the process making fully prepared silage, silage preservation is the process of only preserving the material for further processing while fully prepared silage has been thickened and de-oiled. For that reason, preserved silage is commonly sold directly into fishmeal plant or to animal feed producers while fully prepared silage can be sold as livestock- and aquaculture feed or to the fur industry. The fish oil can moreover be sold to feed producers.

Silage production is not new despite its recent interest as to reduce waste in the marine industry. It was first introduced in Finland in the 1920 to make greed fodder using sulfuric and hydrochloric acid. Later the method was adapted to whole fish and fish waste and production on industrial scale started in Denmark around 1950. At that time, Denmark produced about 15 000 tons per annum in 14 companies. The Norwegian seafood industry is one of the largest producer of silage in the world and produce large amount annually, both from whitefish, pelagic and aquaculture industry. Where 45% of their rest raw materials and unwanted catches is utilised into silage (Figure 81).

Figure 81. Allocated Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Materials (RRM) used for production of by-products in 2015 (in tonnes) (Richardsen, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016)

One of the reasons why Norway has become so big in silage and has managed to implement it on the wetfish fleet as well, can be explained by the fact that silage processing facilities are relatively common all over Norway, due to its presence in the aquaculture industry. This makes easier access for whitefish operators to the silage facilities to land their RRM or their pre-made silage all year around. The implementation of silage production has been tried in other countries such as Iceland few decades ago but has failed due to some reasons. Such as lack of infrastructures, uneven access to raw materials all year around and design flaws.

Silage preservation

The silage preservation process can generally be broken into three main steps, shown in Figure 82. Firstly, mincing, which is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. Secondly, digestion in primary silage tanks to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion; and thirdly the silage storage tank to store the silage and maintain digestion.

Figure 82. Processing streams and setup for silage preservation

After mincing, acid is added to the material into the primary day tanks to trigger the digestion, generally formic acid is used but other acid such as sulfuric acid can also be used. By having a primary silage tanks for blending of the material, sometimes called day tanks, helps to create more even digestion. While the secondary silage tank, is meant to store and maintain digestion of the material. Regarding the blending of acid, it is advised to install a computer-controlled system that monitors the silage and measures the correct amount of acid needed to be added. These systems will add more acid into the solution if the pH value is rising too much above the desired value. Vacuum pumps can then be used to circulate the silage from the bottom of the tank to the top, for the acidity to be uniform throughout the solution. However, acid can also be added relative to the mass flow into the silage tank, thus the silage will be fully blended when it enters the storage tank. The number and size of the silage tanks used for the acidification process is optional and dependant on the amount of raw materials, when they arrive and their composition.

The breakdown of the silage is dependent on the concentration of the acid and temperature. A heater is therefore often used to increase the breakdown rate. It takes silage made of whitefish offal around two days to break down at temperatures around 20°C and five to ten days at temperatures around 10°C (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

There are few elements that need to be considered in the design of the silage tanks. The tanks need to be designed without sharp corners and with smooth inner surface to eliminate the risk of infection from bacteria settling on the surface. The primary silage tanks need to be constructed with cone in the bottom for settling of unwanted particles as stones. These tanks can be constructed from normal construction steel (st. 37) if the temperature of the silage is under 18°C, since temperatures greater than 18°C can lead to corrosion of the steel. For temperatures up to 30°C and more, anti-corrosive stainless steel is required or even plastic material (Arason, 1994). It is recommended to use anti-corrosive material for the primary tanks since the fermentation process has an optimum temperature between 25°C to 30°C (Archer, Watson, & Denton, 2001).

Mixing of the silage is essential to get even chemical composition. Mechanical stir could be considered but optimal approach is to have vacuum pumping for constant circulation of the material. If stirring is poorly done the silage can separate into three phases, a liquid protein soluble on the top, an aqueous soluble in the middle and small sediment of heavy and insoluble fragments at the bottom (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001).

Not all species are ideal for silage production. Shells of crustaceans are for example hard to process into silage and species with high urea content in the meat are not ideal for silage production either, such as sharks and skates. It is therefore best to categorize the UUC before using them into silage. The crustaceans can then be processed into other products, such as chitosan which is used in food supplements and as colour treatment in aquaculture. Moreover, lean fish and fatty fish should be separated since silage is often categorised on the market by these two. Silage made of fatty fish and white fish silage made from lean fish species.

Fully prepared fish protein concentrates and fish oil

It is possible to take the silage production process further which allows for more added value. But it also means increased investment cost and more complicated processes. The end products coming from this process are fish oil and de-oiled silage. The fish oil can be sold directly, for example to feed producers. The de-oiled silage is also more marketable product that can for example be sold to fishmeal factories, feed producers and to farmers as feed supplements or fertilizer. One of the benefits of this process is that water is removed along with oil, which not only reduces the volume of the silage for storage and transportation but collects the fish oil which is valuable on its own.

This production process is like the silage preservation process to begin with. In the first stages, material is minced and then mixed thoroughly in one of the primary acidification tanks along with acid. The material is treated with temperature and acid control to enforce rapid and powerful start of the digestion, at around 20°C. By optimising all necessary conditions, such as temperature, acid control and other relevant factors, the silage can finish digesting in two days (Tatterson & Windsor, 2001). The secondary silage tank is therefore not necessary, since the melted silage can be utilized right away. Once the silage is digested it is sent through a heat exchanger to deactivate the enzymes and stop the digestion. After that, it then goes into a centrifuge, where the wet silage is separated into fish oil and de-oiled fish silage. The fish oil is then ready as a final product, but the de-oiled fish silage is sent into an evaporator where it is thickened down to 50 dry matter. The final de-oiled silage is then ready as substance in feed. However, addition of antioxidant chemicals such as Ethoxyquin is needed in the proportion of 150-200 parts per million to further stabilise the material. The processing steps are shown in Figure 83.

Figure 83. Processing streams and setup for full silage production.

7 A Study to Identify Potential uses for Unwanted Catches Landed into Ireland under the Landing Obligation

Highlights of chapter

- The Irish seafood sector is facing challenges when it comes to implementing the Landing Obligation, due to the diversity of the fleets and limited Infrastructure in harbours.
- Drawing on experiences from other countries with experience of discard bans provides valuable insights into possible short-term and long-term solutions.
- Short-term solutions may include fishmeal- and fish oil-, bait-, silage- and pet food production.

Foreword

The content of this chapter is largely based on a report that the authors (Mike Fitzpatrick, Jónas R. Viðarsson and Marvin I. Einarsson) gathered for a report that they wrote for Bord Iascaigh Mhara (BIM). That report was funded by Bord Iascaigh Mhara (BIM) under the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF); but was as well linked to the DiscardLess project.

7.1 Introduction and executive summary

The overall aim of this chapter is to assess likely volumes of unwanted catches which may be landed into Ireland under the Landing Obligation, to identify potential uses for those catches and to carry out a cost-effectiveness/feasibility analysis to establish which of these options have the most potential to deliver an economic return to fishermen. This overall objective was approached through a number of sub tasks:

- A global review of potential uses for unwanted catches based on all available literature, interviews and case studies.
- An assessment of likely volumes of unwanted catches which would be landed in Irish ports under a Landing Obligation. This was done by analysing and cross-referencing landings and discard databases with port and species breakdowns to evaluate which fishing gears generate the most discards and the most likely landing locations as well as quantities.
- Infrastructural and economic factors were analysed through interviews with key personnel in the identified ports who would have responsibility for handling the unwanted catches. Interviews and meetings were held with sales agents, processing companies, bait distributors, industry reps, fishmeal, fish protein and pet food plant managers in order to get their views on likely volumes, constraining factors, infrastructural requirements, market and other economic issues.

- The cost and revenue data collected during the interviews was used to conduct a cost effectiveness analysis of the most promising utilisation options. The cost effectiveness analysis was based in the first place on the economic return to fishermen rather than on points further along the value chain (e.g. return to processors).
- Scenarios were developed accounting for a number of future uncertainties such as changes in expected volumes due to improvements in selectivity or changes in the cost base due to factors such as new processing options and the impact of these scenarios on the cost effectiveness analysis was analysed.
- Finally, the utilisation options with the greatest potential to resolve challenges posed by the Landing Obligation in Ireland were identified. Recommendations are made about which uses have most potential, based on likely volumes and their distribution, infrastructural requirements, economic incentives and likely barriers.

Data sources for the report included the EU Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) database of European fisheries landings and discards (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dd/effort/graphs-annex>) and official Irish landings figures data and port based breakdown of landings as reported under the Data Collection Framework (DCF). Information from published deliverables of the EU funded Horizon 2020 research project DiscardLess was also used, particularly in Section 1.

The key points arising from the above tasks are:

Potential volumes of unwanted catches could be significant. Table 40 below shows a total estimate of unwanted catches (i.e. catches below the Minimum Conservation Reference Size: MCRS) of 6 key species of 4,571 tones which could be landed by the Irish fleet. This table is restricted to key species for which significant quantities of unwanted catch may be landed.

** It must be stressed that due to the numerous uncertainties which could affect implementation of the Landing Obligation as well as uncertainties within the estimation process, the figures reported here should be treated only as indicators of potential volumes of below MCRS fish which may be landed.*

Table 40: total estimate of unwanted catches of 6 key species which could be landed by the Irish fleet

Irish vessels, all fishing gears, ICES areas VI & VII (excluding VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	% Discards <MCRS	Discards <MCRS (t)
Whiting	3,686	39	1,438
Haddock	2,898	49	1,420
Nephrops	1,573	48	752
Hake	1,016	46	467
Plaice	612	44	269
Cod	336	67	225
Total	10,121	45	4,571

Regarding utilisation options there are no “magic bullet” solutions that can produce high economic returns to fishermen for size classes of fish that previously had no economic value. Returns will be in most cases a fraction of the value that smaller grades of above minimum size fish can achieve.

One of the implications of this finding of low economic value is that concerns are unfounded that the Landing Obligation will result in the targeting of undersize and juvenile fish by requiring fishermen to land small fish. At least in the case of Ireland there is no possibility of this occurring under current conditions. Unfortunately, this also implies that there are not significant economic incentives to comply with the Landing Obligation in the sense that compliance means the landing of small fish. Quota Uplift, the raising of quotas to account for fish that was previously discarded, should address at least some of this economic loss issue.

The second implication and the flipside of the first, is that there is a huge incentive to fish more selectively and, as far as possible to utilise the quota available in the most economically rational manner. The landing of below MCRS fish will lead to the loss of a large part of the future economic value in those fish. The values we have calculated for currently available options show that 1 tonne of above MCRS fish is worth at least 6 times the value of 1 tonne of below MCRS fish.

Selectivity improvements alone cannot resolve all Landing Obligation issues however and some residual unwanted catches will always be an issue in most demersal fisheries. In such cases the best current utilisation option appears to be the pot fishery bait market. When averaging between fresh and frozen supplies to this market a value of €100 to €120 per tonne could be returned to the fisherman for below MCRS fish landed. While significant investment in advanced equipment is not required for this option the main infrastructural constraint here is access to refrigerated and frozen storage. This issue has been successfully addressed by a number of co-ops and sales agents who have received EMFF funding from BIM to improve storage infrastructure. Even in upgraded facilities at certain times when large volumes of commercial landings are present there would still be competition for space in refrigerated storage.

The next best currently available utilisation options are fishmeal, which can essentially take an unlimited supply, and pet food that can take more limited quantities. Both options would deliver a price per tonne to fishermen of approximately €50 per tonne. This highlights the fact that the price differential in demersal fish between small size grades of fish sold on the fresh market and fishmeal is far higher than it is for pelagic fish which is why the fishmeal option is only used occasionally for demersal fish. The prices achievable in the fishmeal option are essentially fixed as fishmeal is a global commodity and significant improvements on that price are highly unlikely.

In the pet food option there may be opportunities to improve prices to a level above that outlined in our initial analysis. Conversations with pet food company operators and Enterprise Ireland experts in the area have highlighted that there is a growing market for high quality niche pet food products from whole fish or fish-based ingredients. In common with any other potentially promising options the requirement would be for a reasonably stable and significant supply of good quality fish with as little mixing of species as possible. The high value pet food market is an option that is worth exploring further.

A potential option, which is being discussed throughout Europe as a potential utilisation solution, is the use of small silage units to stabilise unwanted catches either at sea or ashore before distributing the product to fishmeal plants or other buyers. The difficulty with this option is that it does not add significant value to the product without further concentration and concentration requires more significant investment in equipment. The main advantage of the basic silage process is that it prevents further degradation of the product and allows for the accumulation of silage until a full transport load is ready and thereby reduces transport costs. A network of regional silage units, partly funded by EMFF or other funding, with a partnership arrangement for transport with a fishmeal plant or other buyer and fed by a significant supply of raw material would have some potential to reduce costs and deliver a reasonable return to fishermen.

In the medium term there are a number of options that would require more significant investment but could potentially deliver higher value products. A common problem across almost all of these options is that there is a conflict between the investments required, their high supply volume nature, and the policy goal of the LO, which is to reduce the supply of undersized fish. The fact that to date only very small volumes of below MCRS catches have been landed throughout Europe adds to the unattractive nature of these options for investors, at least currently. One exception to this is the possibility that a supply of gadoid fish could potentially be block frozen and processed through the new fish protein plant in the North West of the country. The technical details and economic viability of this would have to be worked out but it is an option worth exploring as potentially there could be a high value market available for the products of this process.

In the long term what should be aimed at, in line with the desired goal of the Landing Obligation to reduce unwanted catches, is high value uses of smaller volumes of below MCRS fish which cannot be avoided. This calls into question any business plans and large infrastructural investments based solely on discards. Viable options would have to be established in conjunction with existing processing operations and existing supply lines of processing waste or low value commercial grades of fish.

To summarise in order to successfully add value to unwanted catches in the longer term it appears that most if not all of the following criteria should be met:

- Prospective operators would have to be confident that a reasonable supply of smaller fish will be available in the first place.
- Prospective plants should ideally be in, or at least in close proximity to, a fishing port where significant landings will occur as protein degradation in fish occurs quickly.
- Synergies with other fish processing activities are essential in particular regarding energy recycling and labour.
- A long-term approach will have to be taken by any prospective operator. Experiences from Norway and Iceland have shown that over time significant economic activity by companies specialising in high-value, niche products from viscera or other parts of fish will not appear overnight but develop over time.

- The financial clout and long-term commitment required means that either a large co-operative or consortium would be necessary in order to sustain the enterprise.
- It will be necessary to fully exploit high value niche markets for all product streams in order to get the most value from the raw material. For example, a fish protein (FPH) operation could target pharmaceutical products or human functional foods at the higher level, performance proteins for high-end animal feed at the middle level and high-quality fertiliser at the lower level. A successful example of this approach is the case of Celtic Sea Minerals, based in Castletownbere, which has gradually, through investment in R&D, increased the niche value of its products over time.
- Achieving this will require significant technical and marketing expertise and a commitment to R&D.
- Companies in other countries with a history of bycatch and by-product utilisation have built up significant expertise in both the technical aspects of these processes and in the marketing of the final products so a partnership approach with such companies would be advisable.

7.2 Section 1: Review of potential uses for unwanted catches

The objective of this section of the report is to identify available alternatives when it comes to utilising unwanted fish catches and low value rest raw materials. The motivation for this work is the implementation of the Landing Obligation (LO) within the EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which states that all catches must be landed and counted against quota once the obligation has been fully implemented. The Landing Obligation also places restrictions on how undersized fish can be utilised i.e. fish under minimum conservation reference size (MCRS) cannot be used for direct human consumption.

There are a number of available alternatives for utilising these materials, all of which have their pros and cons, which are discussed in this report. The report draws upon experience from some of the countries that have been operating within a discard ban policy for a long time and have subsequently developed methods for utilising materials that would otherwise have been discarded.

This section of the report also provides insights into some of the challenges fishermen and processors have experienced when attempting to follow the discard bans in countries that have such bans in place. The authors of the report have as well interviewed fishermen and managers on the subject, which gives some insight into how the sector in selected countries accept discard bans/Landing Obligations.

This section of the report will serve as background information for Section 2 when trying to identify potential uses for unwanted catches landed into Ireland under the Landing Obligation.

7.2.1 Current and potential uses of unwanted catches

The available alternatives for utilisation of excess rest raw materials (RRM) and unwanted unavoidable catches (UUC) can be broken into six main categories, which are shown in Figure 84. These range from being low-tech production of well-established products, to highly innovative high-tech production of novel products.

Figure 84: Rest Raw Materials (RRM) and Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) can be broken into these six main categories

Food

There are considerable opportunities regarding development of new fish products, such as fish fingers, burgers, flavourings, sauces, canned fish products, protein additives and especially for products made out of minced fish muscles. Mince can be processed from cut-offs, other RRM such as heads and backbones, from UUC or even fish under minimum conservation reference size (MCRS) if no legal restrictions stand in the way.

Minced fish products: such as fish sausage, fish paste, hamburgers, fried minced fish along with pre-made fish dishes have gotten increased attention by consumers and authorities as low commercial value fish source that could increase fish consumption. These minced fish products are already well known in Europe, they are either sold fresh or frozen. Nowadays, these minced fish products mainly consist of whitefish species such as cod, haddock, whiting, Alaskan pollock for example and are often extracted from cut-offs, fillets of low quality (e.g. due to gaping), backbones/frames, juvenile catches and other catches of low commercial value. Few experiments have however recently been conducted with other species such as horse mackerel and blue whiting to make fresh fish burgers. The results have been positive as one study showed excellent sensory properties and good suitability for other culinary recipes (fish fillings, fish balls) due to their light fishy flavour, taste and textural properties (chewiness and juiciness) after cooking. In the production process, the fish is de-heated and gutted, a mincer separates skin and bones from the muscle, the mince is mixed with vegetables or other ingredient and natural preservatives, it is then packaged with nitrogen for preservation purposes. The shelf life for these products is considered 7-9 days, at correct storage temperatures.

Figure 85: Fish burgers, fish fingers, surimi, tempura breaded cod and canned mackerel

Other products, such as fish-based extrusion products are also an alternative to look into. These are expanded fish snacks, fish fingers and sticks, protein gels, surimi and surimi-based products. One alternative that is gaining increased attention among NE-Atlantic processors is for example to make surimi from blue whiting, which has almost solely been used for fishmeal in the past.

New fish-products may also rely on other more traditional and modern technologies for producing fish products. Such as proteolyzed fish products which can be fermented fish products, semi-preserved fish products, fish silage and fish protein hydrolysate (FPH). Fish products that have undergone thermal treatment for ready-to-serve meal and canned products. Other processing methods to mention are freezing with forced-air, IQF (Individually Quickly Frozen), cryogenic system, CAS (Cells Alive System). Vacuum drying, irradiation, microwave, DIC (Instantaneous Pressure Drop), HP (static and dynamic High Pressure), pulsed Light, modified atmosphere packaging of seafoods, active packaging (antioxidant, antimicrobial).

Liver, roe & milt: By-products made from cod liver, roe and milt have become increasingly valuable in recent years. The freshest materials become high value premium products and the rest is sold in bulk or used in lesser valued products such as liver oil.

Figure 86: Liver, roe and milt

Dried fish products: There have traditionally been good markets for dried cod heads and fish frames in Africa, particularly in Nigeria, where these products are mostly boiled to make soup. Heads, frames and cut-offs that are left after processing of haddock, saithe, tusk and ling are also suitable, but heads and frames from more fatty fish species like wolffish and redfish are not applicable for drying. Figure 87 shows the end-product made out of cod.

Figure 87: Dried cod frame (bones) and head

The markets for these dried products have however been difficult in recent years, because of financial difficulties in Nigeria due to low oil prices (Nigeria's main export product).

Bio-products

When UUC cannot be used for direct human consumption there are a number of available options for alternative use. Many of these alternatives are gaining increasing attention, which may lead to interesting products and increased revenues. Fishes contains a large number of biomolecules of high value that can be used in food, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics, as well as in the feed industry (pet-food, aquaculture and cattle).

Bioactive Peptides: come from the extensive hydrolysis of fish protein and contains mainly free amino acids di-, tri- and oligopeptides. These peptides present biological activities that make them valuable for pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, food- and feed products. Figure 88 shows peptide powder made out of collagen from cod skin.

Figure 88: Peptides made from cod skin - collagen and gelatine

Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs): come from the purification of fish oil, obtained from viscera or from fatty fishes, and are fats with more than one unsaturation's (double bonds) present in the chain. PUFAs includes important compounds such as essential fatty acids that are correlated with the cardiovascular health of humans.

Proteases and Proteolytic enzymes: extracted from by-products, especially viscera, that contain a large proportion of digestive enzymes including collagenases, trypsin, pepsin, chymotrypsin, elastase, and carboxylpeptidase. Proteolytic enzymes from fish catalyses the degradation of peptide bonds of proteins. They have specificity of action and in the case of those from fish they have activity at low temperature and pH. They play a key role in a wide variety of physiological processes, biotechnology, food processing and other industries.

Chondroitin sulphate: obtained by an enzymatic or chemical hydrolysis process to deproteinize the cartilage and successive purification phases from the skeleton of cartilaginous fish, sharks and rays. Chondroitin sulphate provides cartilage with its mechanical and elastic properties, and gives this tissue a large part of its resistance to compression. It is used as a dietary supplement with anti-inflammatory properties, as an aid against arthritis.

Fat-soluble vitamins: are obtained by solvent extraction of vitamins from fish oil. Vitamins are classified as either fat soluble (vitamins A, D, E and K) or water soluble (vitamins B and C),

difference that determines how each vitamin acts within the body. Fish liver oil is rich in vitamins A and D that are used in pharma, cosmetic and food applications.

Minerals (Calcium, CaCO₃): is obtained from spines, flakes and fins of fish and shells of bivalve molluscs (mussels, clams etc.). It can be used as mineral supplement in nutraceutical market (for human or animals), as food ingredient.

Dye / pigments (Astaxanthin): is extracted mainly from crustacean shells. It is used as a pigment in aquaculture, in fish and crustaceans feeding.

Collagen: is obtained by an acid or basic treatment of spines, scales and skin. The amino acid content of collagen differs from other proteins because of their high content of proline and hydroxyproline. Collagen is widely used in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and also as food supplement. Figure 89 shows some of the products made from collagen.

Figure 89: Collagen is used as ingredient in variety of products and is particularly popular in food supplements, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics

Gelatine: is obtained from the irreversible hydrolysis of the collagen. There are two main types of gelatines, Type A obtained from the acid hydrolysis procedure and Type B obtained from the alkaline hydrolysis procedure. Gelatines is used as gelling agent in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and food. Fish gelatines are preferred for low temperature gelling needs. The world market for gelatine is extremely large, as it is used in variety of products, ranging from puddings to gummy bears; and face masks to capsules around pharmaceuticals, as shown in Figure 90.

Figure 90: Example of products that contain gelatine

Most of the gelatine produced in the world are made from terrestrial animals, but with increasing numbers of consumers that do not want to eat farmed animals the market for fish gelatine is

becoming stronger. There are also large portions of consumers that do for example not want gelatine made from pigs (for religious reasons) or horses (for ethical reasons).

Sterols: steroids found in plants and animals can be obtained by extraction. Phytosterols have received much attention in the last decade because of their cholesterol-lowering properties and can be found in marine organisms in small quantities, as a dietary origin from phytoplankton. The major presence of phytosterols is observed in bivalves, due to phytoplankton food sources. Phytosterols are largely used in the food and beverage industry.

Insulin: extracted from various fish viscera. Insulin is a peptide hormone produced by beta cells of the pancreatic islets, and by the Brockmann body in some teleost fish. Insulin regulates the amount of glucose (sugar) in the blood and is required for the body to function normally and is used for treating diabetes.

Protamine: purified mixture of simple proteins obtained from wild salmon sperm Protamine is a protein (Molecular weight around 4,000-5,000), which works to maintain and protects DNA from being damaged. It is used in pharma as a drug that reverses the anticoagulant effects of heparin by binding to it.

Hyaluronic acid: obtained by successive extraction and purification steps, it is a glycosaminoglycan present in skin, bones and joints. Its function is to give elasticity to these parts of the body. It is used in regenerative cosmetics of the skin and in injections in cosmetic surgery or in the recovery of injuries of joints.

Chitin / Chitosan: Chitin is obtained by deproteinization, discoloration of exoskeleton of arthropods. Chitosan is obtained by further deacetylation of chitin by chemical-enzymatic processes. It has uses such as chelating agent in the Water treatment, clarifier, thickener, fibre, film, chromatography column matrix, gas selective membrane, hypocholesterolemic agent, plant disease resistance promoter, anticancer agent, wound healing promoter and antimicrobial agent. It is used as a technological adjunct and is being tested for applications such as fruit preservation, wound dressings, cosmetics, artificial organs and pharmaceuticals. Chitosan made from the shells of prawns and lobsters is being used for pharmaceuticals and food supplements. All the shells available in Iceland are as example used by the company Primex for making pharmaceutical and food supplement products, shown in Figure 91.

Figure 91: Example of the products Primex produces from Chitin / Chitosan

Pearl Essence: is extracted from fish scales. Guanine is an iridescent substance that is found in the epidermal layer and scales. The suspension of guanine in a solvent is called "essence of pearls". It was used in cosmetics and paints.

Phospholipids: are extracted from fish oil by different procedures. Marine omega-3 phospholipids (n-3 PLs) are defined as PLs containing n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) derived from marine organisms. This makes them different from PLs derived from vegetable sources, since they do not contain long-chain n-3 PUFAs. Phospholipids are used as emulsifiers in the food industry, emollient in cosmetic, antibacterial or drug delivery system in pharma.

Squalene: extracted mainly from shark liver. Hydrocarbon compound, isoprenoid, intermediate in the synthesis of cholesterol, hormones and vitamin D. Used in cosmetics in moisturizers and in pharmacy or dietary supplements as an immune stimulator.

Peptones: produced by controlled enzymatic hydrolysis of proteins. Peptones are polypeptides formed during the enzymatic degradation of proteins. They are the main source of nitrogen in the organic medium for bacterial culture. They are used in the manufacture of culture media for microbiology and biotechnology (industrial fermentations).

Feed

The most common use of fish by-products in most countries is the production of fishmeal and fish oil, which is then mainly used for animal feeding. This alternative may also be of major interest for the processing of UUC as there are often infrastructures available that are generally close to harbours. However, many other valorisation options focused on animal feed can be considered.

Fishmeal: obtained from any fish or fish by products, after a thermal process to coagulate the protein and separate the oil, fishmeal is a brown powder rich in protein. The colour is affected by fish species, particle size, fat and moisture content. Fishmeal is mainly used in animal feed. Aquaculture account for > 60 %, pigs 25 %, and poultry 8 %.

Fish oil: obtained in the same process as fishmeal, fish oil is a liquid product composed mainly by fatty acids, high in unsaturated fatty acid, with variable amounts of phospholipids, glycerol ethers and wax esters. Fish oil has different uses that can vary in function of its composition. Approximately 80 % of the global fish oil production is used in aquaculture and about 13 % is destined to human consumption.

Mink feed: any fish or fish by-product can be used to feed mink for the fur industry (food regulation does not apply). This alternative is often used for products that cannot be used for anything else as food safety regulations do not have to be taken into consideration i.e. mink is not used for human consumption or for ingredients that become animal feed. Viscera, which contains digestive trace elements can therefore be used as mink feed. Figure 92 shows how viscera is block frozen in Icelandic fish processing plant and the blocks are then used for mink feed.

Figure 92: Frozen cut-offs from processing of whitefish and block frozen viscera

Marine Bait: discard species can be used as effective pot bait when targeting crabs and lobsters. The condition of the material is generally not important, which makes this a good alternative for low value materials that are difficult to preserve. Fish that is high in fat are usually considered good bait.

Fish Protein Concentrate (FPC): Dehydrated and grounded products, with a variable protein content, which may or may not taste and smell like fish, depending on the method of production used. This technology aims to achieve a stable product, with a protein concentration higher than that of fish muscle. The manufacture of this type of products allows for the use of species that are not accepted for direct human consumption, and of the waste from the fish processing industries. Used primarily for animal feed, but due to their high nutritional value, they can also be used for human consumption e.g. as food supplements or as a protein source in different foods.

Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH): Stable product with good functional properties and high nutritional value, prepared from the protein fraction of whole fish, by-products or processing waters thereof, by chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis. A product consisting of mixtures of amino acids and peptides of different sizes are obtained depending on the degree of hydrolysis carried out. It is used mainly in animal feed but can also be used in the food industry as e.g. a flavouring or raw material for the elaboration of aromas.

Figure 93: Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH) powder

Silage: Liquid protein hydrolysate made from whole fish or from processed residues. The hydrolysis is carried out by endogenous proteolytic enzymes, located in the viscera and in the meat of the fish, under acidic conditions. Acid conditions limit the growth of degradative bacteria. It is used mainly as a protein supplement in animal feed (cattle, poultry and aquaculture) and as a base for the production of fish sauce.

Insects meal and oil: obtained after the growing of insect over a fish substrate. Insect meal can be used for animal feed.

Industrial uses

When the previous options are not available, for example due to legal constraints, quality of the raw materials or of the products, other technical uses may be considered, which are often considered as industrial uses such as:

Leather: is the cured and tanned skins of fish. Fish leather can be used to make a wide variety of items such as jewellery, accessories, belts, wallets, bags and in shoes. It can also be used for a much larger variety of crafts.

Low quality Fish oil: obtained in the fishmeal production process can be used for industrial usage, such as solvent for painting, when it doesn't meet feed quality standards.

Low quality Minerals: Calcium, CaCO₃: is obtained from spines, flakes and fins of fish and shells of bivalve molluscs (mussels, clams, etc) and can be used as soil improver or mineral fertiliser.

Low quality Chitin / Chitosan: when the product is obtained with low purity or quality the chitosan may be used in less demanding uses such as biological systems, agricultural use or as filtering agent in water treatment.

Energy

Biogas: is produced through the anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic matter. This is a complex biological process in which anaerobic bacteria decompose organic matter in environments with little or no oxygen. The process produces biogas (55-65 % methane, 35-45 % carbon dioxide, and other) which is used as energetic source for heating or producing electricity. Also, a digested substrate is produced that can be used as fertilizer in agriculture.

Biodiesel: is obtained by a transesterification process of the fish oil. Biodiesel is later used in diesel engines as an energy source.

Agronomic uses

Compost/Fertilizers: obtained by an aerobic decomposition process carried out by the own microorganisms of the organic matter. Compost from fish usually consists of fish waste, saw dust, wood bark chips and is covered with leaf compost to make a compost pile. The compost is used for soil amendment or fertilizer. Also, fish protein hydrolysates can be used as fertilizer.

7.2.2 Current utilization of unwanted catches in Norway and Iceland

There are number of countries outside of EU that have been operating under a Landing Obligation for considerable time. Iceland and Norway are one of those countries that have gradually improved their methodologies and approaches throughout the years and the experiences of these countries can therefore benefit others with the implementation of a LO. The following chapters address how the Norwegian and Icelandic industry have tackled the discard ban.

Norway

A discard ban has been in force in Norway since 1983 and is widely accepted within the Norwegian fishing industry and by the public. It was first implemented only on the most important species but applies to all commercial species today and all vessels fishing in Norwegian waters. These species are managed under Individual Transferable Quotas (ITQs) and vessel group quotas. Catch is counted against quotas and all fishing activities that run the risk of over catching must stop when the quota is filled. Larger catches that exceed quotas or catches under MCRS can be landed without prosecution or penalties, but the catch is confiscated by the sales organisations or the Directorate of Fisheries. The fishing company receives then 20% of the sales value, in order to cover landing costs and provide incentives for landing the catch. The sales organisations and the Directorate of Fisheries keep 80% for themselves. There are no restrictions on the use of juvenile/small fish and the first priority is therefore to use as much as possible for human consumption. The approach the Norwegians have applied in minimising the targeting of small fish are seasonal and emergency closures of fishing grounds with high proportions of small fish, as well as gear restrictions where selectivity mechanisms are required.

Norwegian demersal whitefish catches have amounted to around 800 thousand tonnes a year, for the past five years (Statistics Norway, 2017). By far the most important species are cod, saithe and haddock, representing over 90% of the catches. The share of each of these species can fluctuate slightly between years depending on stock size, but in 2016 cod accounted for 57% of the total whitefish demersal catches, saithe for 21% and haddock for 15%. The fisheries for these species are highly seasonal, particularly for cod and saithe, as over 60% of the cod catches are landed in the first four months of the year and 50% of the saithe catches are landed in the period between February and May. This uneven seasonal distribution has the effect that production needs to cope with extremely high throughput during the first four months of the year, making it difficult to allocate efforts on by-products and RRM that do not create similar value as the main products. According to recent estimations on the utilisation factor of whitefish in Norway, it is estimated that about 82% of the whitefish catches (in life weight) is utilised, in one way or another (Richardson, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016). About 57% are used for primary products, meaning that 43% are RRM of which 48% are utilised. Compared to the pelagic- and aquaculture industries in Norway, this utilisation of RRM from whitefish is however relatively low. All RRM are for example utilised in the pelagic industry and 91% in the aquaculture industry. The reason for this difference can to a some extent be traced back to the seasonal variability in catches of whitefish, high labour cost and lack of space and conditions for processing excess rest raw materials. But also, due to the fact that utilisation of whitefish RRM is mostly limited to boats that land fresh fish, while the majority of freezer trawlers discard their RRM i.e. viscera, heads and frames.

Boats landing fresh catches land the fish whole, usually with head-on, either gutted or un-gutted. This allows for increased utilisation of RRM on land, since the catch is processed on-shore where there are conditions for collecting and processing these secondary material streams. These fresh

fish boats are in addition often fitted with equipment for gathering and processing liver, roe and milt on board and or silage tanks that receive viscera offal's and sometimes heads.

The utilisation of RRM from both fishery and aquaculture industries has been towards production of silage, fishmeal and fish oil where only 12% of the RRM are intended for human consumption. This can be seen on Figure 94, which shows the distribution of the RRM going for different processing in 2015 (Richardsen, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016).

Figure 94: Allocated Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Materials (RRM) used for production of by-products in 2015 (in tonnes)

The trend in utilisation of UUC and RRM from whitefish and especially from cod has been moving towards production of products for human consumption, for example, by utilising cut-offs for mince production and for production of surimi or other foods for human consumption; instead of producing silage or fishmeal. The liver is for example now rather used for making canned liver for human consumption instead of producing fish oil for aquaculture, the roe are used for making caviar (Figure 95), the heads are dried for human consumption and more. There are however always parts such as viscera that are not ideal for human consumption and are therefore used in silage or fishmeal.

Figure 95: Norwegian caviar and salted roe made from cod roe

The Norwegian seafood industry produces large amount of silage, both from whitefish, pelagic and aquaculture industry. Silage is particularly relevant when it comes to processing and gathering of UUC and MCRS catches offshore when labour cost is high and when space is limited,

for example in the vessels storage hold. The reason why Norway has become so big in silage and has managed to implement it on the wetfish fleet as well, can be explained by the fact that silage processing is relatively common all over Norway, due to its presence in the aquaculture industry. This makes easier access for whitefish operators to the silage facilities to land their RRM or their pre-made silage all year around. The leading company in the processing of silage in Norway is Hardafor AS. They produce fish silage from aquaculture species, pelagic and whitefish as well as producing and selling equipment for production of silage; offering ready to install solutions for the global market. They run their own production facilities in nine locations in Norway, Denmark and Faroe Island. They also run five specially equipped silage transportation tanker vessels and four trucks that can collect silage from all across Norway and even from abroad. They also buy in silage from smaller producers.

Silage is relatively cheap product when sold directly as mink-, livestock feed or directly into a fishmeal factory as a raw material. However, more valuable products are being made out of the silage such as fish protein hydrolysate (FPH) and fish protein concentrate (FPC). FPH is mostly used as an additive into both aquaculture and livestock feed. The production process is slightly different from the silage process as enzymes are added along with the acid during the degradation process to make it possible to extract specific peptides and ammonia acids. Along with that, the silage is de-oiled and bones are sieved out, a description of that can be seen on Figure 96. FPH is also sold as health supplement for human consumption and nutraceuticals. It has also been shown that FPH can serve as a disease resistance for aquaculture species and as stimulator for their immune system and can increase feed consumption as well, which makes FPH particularly interesting option as an aquaculture feed additive (Shahidi & Barrow, 2007). Almost 15 thousand tons of FPH were produced in Norway 2015 which primarily went into aquaculture feed.

Figure 96: Simplified schema of protein hydrolysate process

FPC is a much simpler production than FPH, as it is basically a de-oiled and thickened silage that has gone through oil separation and thickening in evaporators. Figure 97 shows the main steps in the production of FPC. Despite FPC not being as valuable as FPH, fish oil is produced along with the FPC which increases the margin. Fish protein concentrate is mostly used for aquaculture-, livestock- and fur breeding feed.

Figure 97: Simplified schema of fish protein concentrate process

In 2015 a total of 77 thousand tonnes of FPC were produced in Norway from UUC and RRM. Figure 98 shows the main product categories and production volumes, in tonnes, derived from UUC and RRM in 2015 (Richardsen, Nystöyl, Strandheim, & Marthinussen, 2016).

Figure 98: Products made from Unwanted Unavoidable Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Materials (RRM) in 2015, in tonnes

It is difficult to estimate the contribution of the discard ban to improving selective fishing practises and increasing utilisation of UUC and RRM in Norwegian fisheries. The management system has at least been successful at reducing the capture of juvenile fish (Graham, Ferro, Karp, & MacMullen, 2007). But some species, such as the Norwegian coastal cod, are though still struggling due to low stock size and overfishing (ICES, 2017). The fact that all catches are utilised for making valuable products, along with strict surveillance and wide scale social opposition against discarding, has contributed to making discarding a minor issue in Norwegian fisheries.

Iceland

A number of measures have been implemented over the past three decades with the aim of reducing discards in the Icelandic groundfish fishery. In 1977 the landing of all catch of six main commercial fish species (cod, haddock, saithe, golden redfish, plaice and Greenland halibut) was made mandatory by law, and, thus, discards prohibited for the species in question (EC, 2007). Then in 1984, along with the introduction of the ITQ-system in the demersal fisheries, some restrictive measures regarding minimum landings size were abolished. Prohibitions of discarding were however retained. At the same time, it was permitted to land and retain “undersized” fish up to a certain percentage of each landing without that volume being counted against the vessel’s annual quota. The purpose of this stipulation was to provide further incentives against discarding. The particulars of these regulations have been subject to numerous changes in subsequent years. In 1986, the discard ban was extended to cover catches of all ITQ-regulated species and in 1996 it became a part of the Icelandic fisheries management legislation that all fish caught, irrespective of species or size, should be landed, and discards of any kind thereby prohibited.

The discard ban is generally accepted by the fisheries in Iceland and there is a wide acceptance as well for it amongst the public. The Icelandic fishery provides an example of where Landing Obligation has been in effect for decades and where the success of the implementation can be studied to give other fisheries ideas on what to proceed with implementation and what to avoid. Discards today are minor, but that is the results of a long process where many variable factors have contributed to a successful development. The individual transferable quota (ITQ) system, integration of the value chains, consolidation in the industry and negative public opinion of discards play an important role, but a key factor is also that all catches are used for producing as much value as possible; there are no constrains on the use of for example undersized fish.

One of the advantages of the Icelandic discard ban is the many built in flexibilities that create incentives for landing all catches. One of those is a regulation that refers to fisheries being able to transfer up to 5% of its quota between years. This creates incentives to land excess catches legally and deduct it from the quota that would otherwise be intended for next year. The fisheries may also choose to land the excess catches or UUC without deducting it from quota, however, as in Norway that means they can only receive 20% of the revenue where the rest 80% goes to research funds where this 20% of the sales value is only intended to cover the landing cost (Directorate of fisheries, 2017a). Regarding catches that are under minimum conservation reference size (MCRS), landings can be counted 50% against quota creating incentive to land these catches. The MCRS catches are moreover accepted for human consumption which increases its value. In addition, larger overruns or large amount of non-target catches can be solved by purchasing additional quota.

The Icelandic fishery is different from other fisheries in many ways. One important factor that needs to be considered is the extensive consolidation and optimisation that has occurred over the last 20-30 years in the sector. These are side effects from the Individual Transferable Quota (ITQ) system where the quota has been aggregating on fewer hands. As an example, in 1992 ten of the largest quota holders owned 24% of the quota, and in 2017 the share of the ten largest had risen

to 50% (Islandsbanki, 2016); (Directorate of Fisheries, 2017b). The share of the twenty largest quota holders today is 70%. This may have simplified the implementation of a discard ban, since much fewer stakeholders are involved. Fishery companies have been growing larger and individual and self-employed companies that operate only one boat are slowly disappearing. The companies are not only becoming bigger but have much larger funds for investing in new technology and are in better position to develop innovative products.

Directorate of Fisheries holds an accessible database on annual landings of catches and landings of MCRS^{4*} catches. When discards are examined, these data are used where the amount of landed catch is evaluated in context with MCRS landings and population size. This is done by examining the ratios between MCRS and target catches and evaluate them with expected percentage of juvenile fishes in the stock to determine discard rates. This ratio is examined by measuring and analysing the stock sizes with regards to its age and size distribution. According to the Marine & freshwater Research Institute, haddock discard rates were 0.64% in 2015, whilst cod discard rates were 2.13%. Figure 99 shows the estimated discards in tonnes and discard rates for cod and haddock 2001-2015 (Sigurðsson, et al., 2016).

Figure 99: Estimated amount of discarded cod and haddock in Icelandic waters from 2011-2015

The reliability of these estimations may however be questioned, but there is a general belief amongst the industry, researchers and stakeholders that these estimations are relatively reliable. The fact though remains that discarding is illegal and estimations that are not able to rely on discard reporting from fishermen will always be subjected to questioning on reliability.

The Icelandic fishery has developed in such a way that today there are not really any catches that can be defined as UUC. This is however a development that has taken thirty years to gradually change. When the discard ban was first implemented in the Icelandic fishery there were significant discards in place, but with a number of concurrent actions and a change in mentality

^{4*} These are not actual MCRS, as such definition is not used in the Icelandic fishery. What this is in reality is juvenile, undersized fish (IS smáfiskur) which is defined in cm for all commercial species.

the sector has progressed so that today all catches are regarded as raw material for valuable products. The ITQ system has probably played the most important part in this progress, as incentives for discarding have been removed and efforts placed on developing products from all catches. The results are that today there are basically no unwanted catches in Icelandic waters.

The Icelandic Industry has many opportunities when comes to utilising UUC and MCRS catches since no legal restrictions are set regarding human consumption. The trend with MCRS catches has been towards bulk freezing for foreign markets, filleting & freezing or drying. Low value fish fillets from MCRS catches are for example widely available in Icelandic retail stores. Figure 100 shows frozen cod nuggets made from MCRS that are available in Icelandic retail stores.

Figure 100: Cod nuggets made from undersized fish

UUC species that have little commercial value are commonly dried whole (gutted), these are species such as starry ray, dab, megrim, flounder and even gurnard. The drying was traditionally performed outside but has been moving towards indoor mechanical drying in more controllable environment which results in much better and more stable end products. These products are then sold to foreign markets, mostly in Africa. A key component in this development is that the Icelandic Industry has access to unexpansive geothermal energy source to power the drying, so the production cost is relatively low. Figure 101 shows dried starry ray, which is a good example of UUC that previously would have been discarded but is now considered valuable catch.

Figure 101: dried starry ray

Regarding the current utilisation of UUC and RRM, the Icelandic case is slightly different from Norway. Silage production has for example not caught on in Iceland and the focus has been more towards production of more valuable products for human consumption and bio technical products. Other UUC and RRM that are not readily applicable for added value production are commonly frozen for mink feed. In essence it can be claimed that everything that is landed is utilized, there are however materials that are not landed, these are particularly viscera from fresh fish vessels and parts of the heads and frames from the processing vessels. This is though changing now, as vessels are being fitted with equipment that allows for collection and storage of these UUC and RRM. Regulations have also been changed, so that factory vessels are now obligated to land part of the cod heads.

This development indicates that the utilisation of RRM may increase in near future in Iceland, particularly on larger processing vessels. Smaller fishmeal plants have also been set-up around harbours in Iceland, they receive RRM from the aquaculture industry and from larger fish processing plants. This development may indicate that fishmeal production of RRM may increase in near future. Silage production is another interesting alternative that could work well with fishmeal production. There is though some opposition amongst the industry to try silage production, which is mostly contributed to some failed attempts in the 80's and 90's. Potential new markets within a growing aquaculture sector in Iceland for silage, FPC and FPH may however result in the industry trying this solution again.

Today production of innovative products for human consumption and high value bio technical ones is to a large extent limited to RRM from cod. An example of that are leather made from fish skins, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics made from bioactive compounds extracted from different parts of the cod (and other fish species), collagen made from fish skin, supplements and protein made from different by-products, mineral supplements made from fish bones, enzyme extracted from viscera, skin and tissue repair patches made from fish skin, extracts from RRM's made into powder or bouillon (i.e. for making soups and sauces), silage made from viscera used for animal feed or as fertiliser, swim bladder and milt. Despite previous utilisation being mostly limited to cod products the landscape is slowly changing towards utilisation of other fish species as the operators have started to realize the hidden value in RRM's. Figure 102 and Figure 103 show some examples of UUC and RRM that previously would have been discarded but are now considered valuable products.

Figure 102: wound healing band aid made from fish skin, fish tongues, dried swim bladder and salted cut-offs

Figure 103: Dried cod head, dried undersized whole fish, dried and salted flatfish and dried belly flap

Figure 104: Dried Icelandic fish products intended for human consumption, fresh cod head served at Icelandic restaurant, chandelier made from cod, cod oil and omega-3 from pelagic species are all examples of product development where previously discarded materials are used.

7.2.3 Countries that are adapting to the European Landing Obligation

Iceland and Norway have managed to tackle discarding in their fleet to a certain point. They have managed to reduce discards significantly and have found ways to utilise UUC and MCRS catches, as well as increasing utilisation of RRM. They have developed their own fishery policies with built-in concessions for landings of UUC and MCRS catches that are in addition allowed for human consumption. That is however something that does not apply to all countries that are operating under discard bans, and in particular the countries that are currently implementing the CFP Landing Obligation. Those countries are facing greater challenges, in respect to regulations regarding human consumption, fish stock- and fleet composition. The following chapters discuss the present and previous circumstances in Denmark France and Spain before the discard ban was

implemented. The selected areas are North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak (Danish part), English Channel (French part) and Bay of Biscay (Spanish part). This coverage highlights landing and discard statistics in selected fisheries and estimates potential landings of UUC of each species that will be landed under the new European Landing Obligation in relevant ports. Discard ratios, species composition and seasonal variations.

Denmark

Reported annual discards of the Danish fleet have varied from 27 to 47 thousand tonnes in recent years, representing 4-11 % discard rate, where Nephrops have accounted for $\frac{1}{2}$ - $\frac{3}{4}$ of the discards. Other species with significant volumes of reported discards are dab, plaice, shrimp, cod and rays. Discards of dab are around three thousand tonnes a year and discards of the other four species are between one and two thousand tonnes a year but discards of other species are much lower.

Table 41 shows discards and landings by Danish vessels in 2014 (STECF, Håkansson, & Ulrich, 2015).

Table 41: Discards of Danish vessels in 2014 according to species

Species	Discarded		Landed	
	Tonnes	% of total discards	Tonnes	Species discard rate
Nephrops	14,316	51.6 %	3,472	80.5 %
Common Dab	3,395	12.2 %	976	77.7 %
European Plaice	1,870	6.7 %	19,838	8.6 %
Common Shrimp	1,578	5.7 %	3,104	33.7 %
Cod	1,428	5.1 %	9,274	13.3 %
Starry ray	1,107	4 %	0	100 %
European Flounder	631	2.3 %	2,142	22.7 %
Long-Rough Dab	472	1.7 %	256	64.9 %
Whiting	420	1.5 %	2,212	16 %
North Deepwater Prawn	392	1.4 %	2,474	13.7 %
Caridea shrimp	380	1.4 %	0	100 %
European hake	312	1.1 %	3,125	9.1 %
Other species	1,459	5.3 %	495,516	0.3 %
Total	27,760	100 %	542,390	4.9 %

The Nephrops discards have been high because of a high MLS in place in Skagerrak and Kattegat. This MLS has been reduced in 2016 with the introduction of the LO, so it is expected that discard quantities will reduce significantly. Additionally, some exemptions for high survivability can be granted for this species, which will also reduce the issue of Nephrops UUC. Making a valuable product out of previously discarded Nephrops will though be challenging, since the main reasons for discarding Nephrops are small size, broken shell, moulting/soft shell and females with eggs.

The below MCRS catches will particularly present a challenge, as such materials it will have to be utilised for non-human consumption. It is likely that solutions for the production of crustaceans for non-human consumption will be different from solutions for roundfish and flatfish species.

There are a handful of harbours that stand out in regard to where the potential discards associated to landings are reported, with the six main harbours representing over 70 % of the potential discards. These harbours are distributed all over Denmark, which will most likely present a challenge when developing solutions for production of products for non-human consumption, as transportation can be difficult. Denmark is on the other hand not a big country and transport within Jutland for example is relatively simple.

The Danish sector has been exploring alternatives for producing silage on board fishing vessels, which are showing promising results (FiskerForum, 2017). The idea is to fit vessels with automated processing units for silage, where all UUC, MCRS and RRM are grounded up and turned into silage, without the fisherman having to do much work. The silage is then simply pumped onto a truck when landing. The problem has however been that the economic margin is very low.

France

Reported discards of the French fleet fishing in the English Channel have fluctuated considerably over the past decade, from being almost non-existent in 2005 to almost 20 thousand tonnes in 2012. There are a few species that stand out with respect to reported discards, with whiting, common dab, Atlantic herring, European Plaice and scallop representing 80 % of the discards 2010-2013 as shown in Figure 105 (STECF, 2014).

Figure 105: Discard ratio of France vessels in the English Channel by species (STECF, 2014)

Boulogne-Sur-Mer stands out when looking at where landings associated with discards are reported, representing around 50 % of the total discard amounts that could potentially be landed there. The rest of the 170 harbours are far behind when looking at potential discard volumes, where the harbour with the second highest potential discard volumes represents 7 % of the discards. There are some seasonal variations in the discards, as the volumes have been highest in the first and last quarter of the year. These variations depend largely on the seasonal nature of what species are being targeted, which subsequently has considerable effects on reported discards in some of the harbours i.e. fleets in some of the French harbours are mainly targeting specific species. The datasets analysed do not give information on whether discards have been obligatory MLS discards or not, which makes it difficult to estimate what parts of the UUC that will be landed once the Landing Obligation is implemented will need to be used for production of products intended for non-human consumption. It is however evident that investment in large scale facilities for processing catches below MCRS for non-human consumption will be concentrated on relatively few harbours, simply because most harbours lack critical mass. Catches below MCRS will most likely have to be transported between harbours and it might even be economically practical to concentrate all of the efforts on the vicinity of Boulogne-Sur-Mer, given that potential discard volumes there exceed the second largest discard harbour sevenfold. The company Copalis is located in Boulogne-Sur-Mer and is currently producing a variety of products from UCC and RRM. They will most certainly be a key player in utilising the UUC that prior to the Landing Obligation have been discarded.

Spain – Basque country

Reported annual landings of the Spanish fleet landing in the Basque country have been around 80 thousand tonnes for the past decade. Significant parts of these catches are coming from the Bay of Biscay. The landing and discard volumes are extremely variable between years, seasons and fleet types, which makes it difficult to predict future landings of UUC when the Landing Obligation comes into effect. The species that represent majority of discards are Horse mackerel, mackerel, blue whiting, hake and whiting. The available data does not give any indications of what the incentives for discarding are, but MLS is the most logical explanation. Harbours with significant landing volumes in the Basque county are few and fairly close to one another. Common facilities for utilising below MCRS catches could therefore be an applicable solution. Table 42 shows discard rates of the Spanish trawl fleet 2011-2013 (SDSP, 2015).

Table 42: Discard ratios of the Spanish pair bottom trawl fleet (PTB) and bottom otter trawlers (OTB) targeting demersal species fleet (OTD) in the Bay of Biscay 2011-2013

Species - (PTB)	2011	2012	2013	Species - (OTB)	2011	2012	2013
Anglerfish	0 %	0 %	0 %	Anglerfish	3 %	0 %	2 %
Black-bellied angler	1 %	0 %	0 %	Black-bellied angler	5 %	2 %	3 %
Blue whiting	8 %	88 %	39 %	Blue whiting	98 %	95 %	99 %
Hake	1 %	5 %	6 %	Hake	65 %	27 %	39 %
Horse mackerel	53 %	82 %	85 %	Horse mackerel	94 %	84 %	87 %
Mackerel	55 %	51 %	15 %	Mackerel	99 %	80 %	99 %
Whiting	0 %	0 %	0 %	Megrim	4 %	1 %	3 %

It is likely that catches of MCRS pelagics will account for the mainstay of UUC under the Landing Obligation and the available infrastructure for processing such materials are primarily for fishmeal and fish oil. The company Barna AS is for example well equipped to deal with these materials coming from the Spanish fleet fishing in the Bay of Biscay.

7.2.4 Interviews with stakeholders

The attitude of stakeholders to discard bans may depend to a large extent on the countries they live in and the sector they are operating within. Fishermen in countries such as Iceland and Norway have had approximately 40 years to get used to the concept and at this point they may be more accepting of a discard ban than fishermen in the EU who are trying to work out what impact the Landing Obligation will have on their operations (Fitzpatrick & Nielsen, 2016). Fishermen in Iceland and Norway have learned that there is a value in the by-catches and that by discarding they are basically throwing away part of their wages (Viðarsson, Guðjónsson, & Sigurðardóttir, 2015). EU vessels on the other hand are mainly not yet equipped to deal with these material streams nor is the market ready to pay high prices for these materials.

It needs also to be taken into consideration that the EU fleet is largely made up by small vessels, as 85% of the fleet is below 12 meters and 97% below 24 meters (EU, 2016). This severely reduces the alternatives available to fishermen for collecting and storing UUC on board.

The comparison between the North and the South is also another factor that makes comparison difficult. Fishermen in the Mediterranean, Bay of Biscay and Celtic Seas may be catching up to 60-80 different species in a single fishing trip, whilst Icelandic and Norwegian fishermen usually only have to deal with 10-20 different species. This species diversity can create additional difficulties in collecting and storing UUC.

Processors in all of the countries discussed in this report are positive when asked about opportunities they see in UUC and RRM. The opportunities for new products are seemingly endless and some processors have even boldly claimed that in the near future the value of by-products will exceed the value of the fillets (Pálsson, 2013). The problem processors are however faced with at present is that they do not know how much volume will be available to justify investing in new processing facilities and technology. Initial indications are that where

implementation of the Landing Obligation has already begun the landings volumes of UUC are extremely small (EC, 2017); (EC, 2018). Based on reported discards prior to the implementation of the LO, it would have been expected that landings of MCRS catches around the Baltic, in Denmark, France and UK would be thousands of tonnes by now; but that is not the case. For this reason, it is difficult for processors to invest in expensive technology to process materials that have not yet been landed in significant quantities.

7.2.5 On board handling of UUC

The simplest way of dealing with UUC on board and under the Landing Obligation is to use the current setup. Species not subjected to catch limits can continue to be discarded and species for which the vessel does not have quota will have to be handled as target catch. The only catches needing to be handled differently under the Landing Obligation is therefore catches under MCRS. Since MCRS catches cannot be utilised for human consumption there will be a need to separate between the two categories. It is relatively simple and inexpensive to separate between human and non-human consumption catches on the processing deck and in the hold, as long as the necessary space is available. A by-catch collection can be used to store the UUC while the target catches are being processed; and the UUC then be handled afterwards. A part of the hold can be boxed off for storing catches intended for non-human consumption and having differently coloured tubs/boxes for those catches will also be beneficial. The MCRS catches should ideally be sorted by species into the tubs/boxes, but it could also be an option to do the sorting during landing. Storing the UUC in the hold will of course have effect on how much target catch can be fit in the hold and potentially result in shortening of fishing trips, as the hold will fill up quicker. This should however not be a major problem as the vessels rarely come to port fully loaded prior to the implementation of the LO. In some instances, the space occupied by MCRS catches in the hold will result in shortening of fishing trips, which may lead to increased oil consumption, as extra fishing trips will be needed to fill the quota. This alternative is therefore simple, inexpensive to implement and applicable in most respect. But does require significant efforts from the crew and gives little economic incentive.

On large vessels and trawlers, there is an option to install an automated size grader and in some instances, it is even theoretically possible to have an automated species grader; but such a solution is not commercially available yet where there are a large number of species being caught and current legislation may not permit their use (EC regulation 850/98). There is though already marketed computer vision technology being used for species identification, but that can at present only separate between limited number of species (3X/Skaginn). Using computer vision and automatic size grading are however solutions that are not permitted on board EU vessels, as they can enable automated high-grading. Automated size graders are on the other hand being used on board Norwegian, Icelandic and Faroese fishing vessels; and the experience they have is that the graders have not been used to assist with high-grading (at least as far as the authors are aware). These are therefore solutions that should be considered as alternatives.

In cases where all catches being sent through the processing line are of the same species, which is quite common when fishing in the NE-Atlantic, it is possible to have an automated grading system

on board the vessel. These grading systems are for example being used on some Icelandic wetfish trawlers and amongst the equipment providers are Marel and 3X-Technology. Each batch is then ready to be sent down to the hold when the pre-decided batch size has been reached. Each tub will then contain the right amount of fish, which will all be of similar size. It is even possible to let the data follow the tub, given that the tubs are fitted with a microchip (RFID) and the crew down in the hold have handheld scanners to connect the chip to the data collected by the grader. During on-land processing the production managers will then have detailed information on the raw material they have and can scan each tub to see what is in it, as well as where and when it was caught etc. This is a system that has for example been partly in operation at FISK Seafoods and Gunnvör in Iceland; and HB Grandi is adopting this system on the new wetfish trawlers they recently got. This kind of size grading system would be very helpful in separating between MCRS catches and catches intended for human consumption; in addition to allowing for better production management after landing.

The economic benefits of investing in size- or species graders are not that clear, as the manual grading does not really cost anything for the vessel owners. It is a task that is simply a part of what the crew does on board the vessel. Improved grading, more uniformed batches and increased data availability are however factors that could potentially be of economic benefit for the vessel owners. The French EODE project found that significant investment could be required to conduct shore-based grading of unwanted catches (Balazuc, Coffier, Soulet, Rochet, & Leleu, 2016).

7.2.6 Safety and quality criteria for UUC

Different regulations may apply in regard to food safety, traceability or quality criteria depending on the intended use of UUC, for example whether it is to be used for human consumption, feed production, extraction of biomolecules or for other uses. Following is a brief discussion on regulations, safety and quality criteria's that need to be considered in regard to UUC.

Human consumption

Food safety is one of the issues that need to be a top priority when considering utilisation of UUC and RRM. The safety of these materials is closely related to the quality and need to meet traceability standards. In 2002, the European Parliament and the Council adopted Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law (General Food Law Regulation) establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety' and the 'Hygiene Package', a term that refers to a group of Regulations that came into force on 1st of January 2006: Regulation (EC). 852/04, 853/04, 854/04 and 882/04.

Regulations that are also important in this respect are 'Regulation (EC) 2073/05 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs', Regulation (EC) 2074/05 and 2076/05, with implementing measures and Transitional arrangements of Hygiene Package respectively.

The on board handling, the landing and later operations must meet the same standards for UUC as for other catches and products intended for human consumption. Table 43 gives an overview of the main regulations for safety, traceability and quality of food.

Table 43: Main regulations for safety, traceability and quality of food

Regulation	Subject
Regulation (EC) 178/2002	General principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety
Regulation (EC) 852/2004	This Regulation lays down general rules for food business operators on the hygiene of foodstuffs
Regulation (EC) 853/2004	Specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin in order to guarantee a high level of food safety and public health
Regulation (EC) 854/2004	Specific rules for the organisation of official controls on products of animal origin intended for human consumption
Regulation (EC) 882/2004	Official controls performed to ensure the verification of compliance with feed and food law, animal health and animal welfare rules
Regulation (EC) 2073/2005	Regulation on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs
Regulation (EC) 1333/2008	Food additives
Regulation (EU) 1169/2011	Provision of food information to consumers
Regulation (EC) 258/1997	Novel Foods and novel food ingredients
Directive 2004/41/EC	Repealing certain Directives concerning food hygiene and health conditions for the production and placing on the market of certain products of animal origin intended for human consumption
Directive 2009/32/EC	Extraction solvents used in the production of foodstuffs and food ingredients
Directive 2002/99/EC	Laying down the animal health rules governing the production, processing, distribution and introduction of products of animal origin for human consumption,

Animal feed

Livestock production plays a very important part in the agricultural sector of the EU. Satisfactory results of this activity depend to a large extent on the use of safe and good quality feed. The Regulation (EC) No. 183/2005 lays down general rules governing feed hygiene, conditions and arrangements ensuring traceability of feed as well as conditions and arrangements for registration and approval of establishments. As regarding the scope, the regulation shall apply to: (a) the activities of feed business operators at all stages, from and including primary production of feed, up to and including, the placing of feed on the market; (b) the feeding of food producing animals; (c) imports and exports of feed from and to third countries.

In particular it introduces the following main elements:

- The compulsory registration of all feed business operators by the competent authority.
- Approval of feed business establishments carrying out operations involving the more sensitive substances, such as certain feed additives, pre-mixtures and compound feeding stuffs.
- The approval system for feed businesses for the cases dealing with more sensitive substances will be maintained but provisions are made to extend the current scope for the approval requirement when necessary.
- To ensure that all feed businesses operate in accordance with harmonised hygiene requirements.
- To implement the application of good hygiene practice at all levels of agriculture production and use of feed.
- To introduce the Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) principles for the feed business operators other than at the level of primary production.
- Community and national guides to good practice in feed production.
- To introduce compulsory requirements for feed production at farm level.
- To provide for a European Union framework for guides to good practice in feed production.

Table 44 gives an overview of the main regulations relevant for safety, traceability and quality of feed within the EU.

Table 44: Main regulations for safety, traceability and quality of feed

Regulation	Subject
Regulation (EC) 1831/2003.	Additives for use in animal nutrition
Regulation (EC) 882/2004	Official controls performed to ensure the verification of compliance with feed and food law, animal health and animal welfare rules
Regulation (EC) 183/2005	Requirements for feed hygiene
Regulation (EC) 767/2009	The placing on the market and use of feed
Regulation (EC) 1069/2009	Health rules for animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption
Regulation (EC) 142/2011	implementing Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009
Regulation (EU) 68/2013	Catalogue of feed materials

These requirements for animal feeding are laid down in various Community regulations, but the most important is Regulation 1069/2009 laying down health rules for animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption. In this regulation, animal by-products are

categorised into three specific categories which reflect the level of risk to public and animal health: Category 1, Category 2 and Category 3, demonstrated in Figure 106 (Viðarsson, Iñarra, Pérez-Villarreal, & Larsen, 2016).

Figure 106: Schema of relation between by-product categories and uses

The Regulation also addresses matters such as:

- Restrictions on use.
- Disposal and use of the different categories of by-products.
- Implementing measures.
- Collection, transport and traceability.
- Registration and approval of establishments or plants.
- General hygiene requirements for establish or plants.
- Handling of animal by-products within food businesses.
- Hazard analysis and critical control points.
- Placing on the market.
- Import, transit and export
- Official controls

Other uses

The MCRS catches can be used for different uses than feed and food, as long as it is not used for production of products intended for direct human consumption. These can for example include extraction of biomolecules (for cosmetic or pharmaceutical uses for example) or the generation of bio-energy (bio-gas or bio-fuels as example). For these uses, quality criteria may be more important than safety or traceability.

For the obtaining of high value biomolecules, the on-board handling, landing, transport and other steps in the value chain; from capture to transformation should focus on maintaining the quality and quantity of the specific biomolecule. In most cases the handling and traceability requires similar limitations as for materials intended for direct human consumption.

Bio-energy production has few limitations, as it may use any kind of UUC and condition is generally not a major factor. The value generation potentials can however be affected by biomass degradation and documentation is generally required to validate what raw materials are used for the production.

Summary of safety and quality criteria's relevant for UUC

Summing-up the most important regulations relevant for safety and quality of UUC and potential products produced from such materials in the EU, the general rule is that all landings intended for human consumption are subjected to the same requirements. It does not make any difference whether the raw materials are from target catches or UUC.

UUC that are not intended for direct human consumption require different treatment and are to be kept separate from catches intended for human consumption. This basically means that treatment, processing and storage needs to be separated early on in the supply chain, possibly immediately after capture and at least before processing. It is important to prevent any chances of cross-contamination, which depends on certain characteristics of the UUC and treatment. In most cases it is necessary no later than in landing ports to define into what production flow the catch is going.

Taking into account that catches will degrade if the storage conditions are not appropriate, they must be stored in accordance with requirements of the final product in mind. Each production alternative requires specific structures for each stage of the supply chain i.e. for stage, crushing; drying or packing etc. Regulation EC 142/2011 is particularly important in this respect, laying down that unprocessed Category 3 materials destined for the production of feed or pet food must be stored and transported chilled, frozen or ensiled, unless it is processed within 24 hours after collection or after the end of storage in chilled or frozen form.

Safety criteria's relevant for UUC utilisation are fairly straight forward and need to apply to established rules and regulations. There is a fundamental difference in requirements for UUC intended for direct human consumption and catches that are used for other purposes, but traceability and documentation verifying that the products are safe are always required. When it comes to quality criteria's requirements can be more subjective, as long as the products are safe.

7.3 Section 2: Identifying best uses for unwanted catches in an Irish context

This section of the report focuses on identifying best uses UUC in an Irish context, based on the analysis in section 1 of the report. This is based on factors such as: likely volumes, existing/available infrastructure and route to market. Potential barriers (e.g. economic, legislative, volume, handling, infrastructural deficiencies, cost of logistics) that can inhibit uses of UUC in Ireland are also identified and analysed.

The first part of this section is an analysis of landings and discard data for species subject to the Landing Obligation and the projection of likely unwanted catch figures from these datasets. Due to the uncertainty associated with such a projection co-operation with relevant Marine Institute and BIM staff was essential at this stage.

The second part of this section reports on meetings and interviews with sales agents, industry reps and relevant processing companies in order to get their views on likely volumes, constraining factors, infrastructural requirements, market and other economic issues. This stage also involved the collection of cost and revenue data which informed the cost effectiveness assessments which is presented in Section 3.

7.3.1 Breakdown of Irish landings and discards of demersal TAC species

The tables and data below are based on extraction and further analysis of data from the EU Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) database of European fisheries landings and discards (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dd/effort/graphs-annex>). Data was also sourced from official Irish landings figures data and port-based breakdown of landings as reported under the Data Collection Framework (DCF).

Table 45 gives an overall breakdown of landings and reported discards (averaged between 2014 to 2016) of the main demersal species by Irish vessels using all gears in Irish waters. From this table it is evident that significant overall discard quantities should be expected to be landed by the Irish fleet under the Landing Obligation and that discard rates⁵ for certain species are also significant.

⁵ The discard rate is calculated as follows: Discard Rate = Discards/(Discards + Landings(tonnes))

Table 45: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VI and VII by Irish vessels (all gears, all vessel lengths, demersal TAC species)

Irish vessels, All Gears, Areas VI & VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	3,686	7,189	34
Haddock	2,898	3,539	45
Nephrops	1,573	9,164	15
Hake	1,016	2,943	26
Monk	820	4,096	17
Plaice	612	448	58
Megrim	587	3,092	16
Cod	336	1,241	21
Ling	153	622	20
Saithe	33	939	3
Black Sole	26	194	12
Pollock	15	1,096	1
Total	11,756	34,564	25

From the table above, it is apparent that only nine TAC species have over 100 tons of reported annual discards associated with them. As this project is essentially focussed on species that are likely to generate significant volumes of discards the analysis will focus on these nine species. Given that the table above covers all Irish waters and all landing ports it is unlikely that Pollock, Sole and Saithe would generate volumes of discards significant enough at a specific time and specific port to justify a specific usage analysis.

In order to further explore where the majority of these discards are occurring Table 46 and Table 47 show a similar breakdown for ICES Area VII and Area VI separately and only including the nine species with significant discard quantities overall.

Table 46: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII (excluding VIIId) by Irish vessels (all gears, all vessel lengths)

Irish vessels, All Gears, ICES Area VII (excl VIIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	3,530	7,094	33
Haddock	2,649	2,501	51
Nephrops	1,570	9,085	15
Hake	957	2,715	26
Monk	775	3,457	18
Plaice	576	422	58
Megrim	539	2,518	18
Cod	310	1,214	20
Ling	109	514	17
Total	11,015	29,521	27
% of VI & VII total	94	91	

Table 47: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VI by Irish vessels (all gears, all vessel lengths)

Irish vessels, All Gears, Area VI			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Haddock	248	1,038	19
Whiting	156	95	62
Hake	59	228	21
Megrim	48	574	8
Ling	45	108	29
Monk	45	639	7
Plaice	37	26	58
Cod	26	27	49
Nephrops	3	78	3
Total	667	2,813	19
% of VI & VII total	6	9	

As ICES Area VI accounts for less than 6% of the total demersal discarding of the nine key species, the focus of this analysis will be on the discarding activity among different gear types and fleets in Area VII.

Table 48 and Table 49 illustrate that only two gear types, bottom trawls in particular and beam trawls to a lesser extent, account for 98% of Area VII discards of the nine key species.

Table 48: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish otter trawl vessels (all vessel lengths)

Otter trawls, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	3,418	6,557	34
Haddock	2,277	2,122	52
Nephrops	1,570	8,913	15
Hake	784	1,770	31
Megrim	463	1,823	20
Monk	359	2,761	12
Plaice	286	276	51
Cod	222	928	19
Ling	57	343	14
Total	9,437	25,493	27
% of Area VII total	86	86	

Table 49: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish beam trawl vessels (all vessel lengths)

Beam trawls, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards	Landings	Discard Rate
Haddock	369	213	63
Monk	307	584	34
Plaice	234	138	63
Hake	105	91	53
Whiting	85	33	72
Cod	70	150	32
Megrim	70	665	9
Ling	48	75	39
Nephrops	0	15	0
Total	1,288	1,964	40
% of Area VII total	12	7	

A comparison the tables above shows that the majority of discards for the nine species in Area VII are generated by the otter trawl fleet. Discard rates however for beam trawlers are higher on average, at 40% across the nine species, than those for otter trawlers at 27%. Despite the fact that there are some very high discard rates listed in these tables (e.g. 72% for Whiting caught by beamers in Area VII) the emphasis of this report is not on reducing discard rates, but on analysing

where the greatest volumes of discards originate from, where they are likely to be landed and the utilisation options for those volumes.

The STECF database allows for further analysis of the bottom trawl fleet by looking at mesh size and vessel length subdivisions and the following tables indicate the proportion of landings and discards accounted for by under and over 15m vessels using trawls and seines with either 70-99mm (TR2) mesh size or 100mm (TR1) mesh size and over.

Table 50: Average tonnes (2014-2016) catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish 10-15 metre TR1 vessels (using bottom trawl or seine equal to or greater than 100 mm mesh size)

TR1 10-15m, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	57	90	39
Haddock	45	38	54
Monk	16	42	28
Nephrops	14	79	15
Hake	10	14	41
Megrim	10	47	17
Plaice	5	5	49
Cod	5	12	28
Ling	1	5	16
Total	163	333	33
% of Area VII total	2	1	

Table 51: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish TR1 vessels (bottom trawl or seine equal to or greater than 100 mm mesh size) over 15 metres.

TR1 Over 15m, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	1,829	4,176	30
Haddock	1,238	1,521	45
Hake	369	1,473	20
Nephrops	288	2,288	11
Megrim	187	1,245	13
Monk	169	1,687	9
Cod	146	659	18
Plaice	96	214	31
Ling	25	245	9
Total	4,348	13,507	24
% of Area VII total	42	46	

Table 52: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish 10-15m TR2 vessels (bottom trawl or seine 70-100 mm mesh size)

TR2 10-15m, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Whiting	200	110	64
Haddock	170	80	68
Nephrops	133	575	19
Hake	44	13	77
Monk	39	152	20
Megrim	39	106	27
Plaice	22	22	51
Cod	12	17	42
Ling	4	4	50
Total	663	1,078	38
% of Area VII total	6	4	

Table 53: Average tonnes (2014-2016) demersal catches and discards in ICES Areas VII by Irish over 15m TR2 vessels (bottom trawl or seine 70-100 mm mesh size)

TR2 Over 15m, Area VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (t)	Landings (t)	Discard Rate (%)
Nephrops	1,106	5,968	16
Whiting	1,036	2,180	32
Haddock	771	482	62
Hake	339	269	56
Megrim	239	425	36
Monk	139	873	14
Plaice	65	34	65
Cod	55	240	19
Ling	26	89	23
Total	3,776	10,561	26
% of Area VII total	36	36	

It is probably safe to assume that any previously discarded catch which is above the Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) will be disposed of on the human consumption market. The main interest in this study is therefore in utilisation of those previously discarded fish, which are smaller than the MCRS. Article 15 of the 2013 Common Fisheries Policy states that “the use of catches of species below the minimum conservation reference size shall be restricted to purposes other than direct human consumption, including fishmeal, fish oil, pet food, food additives, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics” (EC, 2013). Estimates of the proportion of discards below MCRS

in Table 54 have been sourced from Hedley and Catchpole, 2015. For Nephrops the figure for the proportion of discards below MCRS was calculated by using the figure of 7% of total Nephrops catch below MCRS from a report by BIM on catch composition in Celtic Sea Nephrops trawls (BIM, 2015) and applying it to the total Irish Nephrops catch. It must be stressed however that due to the numerous uncertainties which could affect implementation of the Landing Obligation as well as uncertainties within the estimation process, the figures below should be treated only as indicators of potential volumes of below MCRS fish which may be landed.

Table 54: Estimated potential volume (tonnes) of unwanted catch (below MCRS) for eight key demersal species (Monkfish is not included here as there is no MCRS specified for monkfish)

Irish vessels, All Gears, Areas VI & VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (tonnes)	% discards <MCRS	Discards <MCRS (tonnes)
Whiting	3,686	39	1,438
Haddock	2,898	49	1,420
Nephrops	1,573	48	752
Hake	1,016	46	467
Plaice	612	44	269
Cod	336	67	225
Ling	153	46	71
Megrim	587	6	35
Total	11,756	40	4,678

The total figure for below MCRS discards of these eight species in Area VII by all Irish vessels is projected to be 4,678 tonnes based on the method outlined above. This is a highly significant amount and as a comparison the figure is larger than the annual landings total for all except for the top six Irish ports. Only six species are likely to have below MCRS quantities of over 200 tons per year and we will therefore further focus our analysis on these. Of the top six species four are gadoids, one is a flatfish and one is a shellfish species.

Table 55 shows that projected below MCRS quantities equate to 19% of the total annual average landings for these species between 2014 and 2016. Furthermore, the ratio of below MCRS fish to annual landings for certain species could be much higher and up to 60% for Plaice.

Table 55: Ratio of <MCRS unwanted catch to average annual landings

Irish vessels, All Gears, Areas VI & VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards <MCRS (tonnes)	Landings (tonnes)	<MCRS as % of landings
Whiting	1,438	7,189	20
Haddock	1,420	3,539	40
Nephrops	752	9,164	8
Hake	467	2,943	16
Plaice	269	448	60
Cod	225	1,241	18
Total	4,572	24,524	19

It is clear from the projections in Table 54 and Table 55 that if comparable quantities of small fish are going to be landed in the future this would create a significant utilisation challenge. This is dealt with in greater detail in Section 3.

In order to assess where these below MCRS fish are most likely to be landed we have used the landings figures for the main ports broken down by each of the six species we are focussing on. Table 56 shows the overall landings volume and value in the main ports in 2015 and 2016 (BIM, 2016). Table 57 and Table 58 show the estimated volume of below MCRS discards which would be landed based on the assumption that the distribution of below MCRS discards by port is the same as that for commercial landings for each of the six species.

Table 56: Volumes and values of landings at the top 10 Irish ports in 2015 and 2016

Port	Volume (tons)			Value € million			Notes
	2016	2015	Average	2016	2015	Average	
Killybegs	155,500	148,746	152,123	85	81	83	78% pelagic, 20% demersal, 20% foreign
Castletownbere	39,700	45,763	42,732	111	113	112	70% foreign
Dingle	10,500	12,611	11,556	23	29	26	76% foreign
Dunmore East	10,400	10,978	10,689	19	16	18	46% Demersal
Howth	6,000	4,411	5,206	16	12	14	15% demersal, 79% shellfish
Kilmore Quay	5,500	4,437	4,969	13	16	15	51% demersal, 48% shellfish
Ros a Mhil	3,300	3,637	3,469	14	12	13	12% demersal, 78% shellfish
Greencastle	3,600	2,826	3,213	9	7	8	81% demersal, 10% foreign
Union Hall	2,400	2,286	2,343	9	7	8	43% demersal, 56% shellfish
Clogherhead	1,900	1,555	1,728	9	6	8	91% shellfish

Source: BIM Business of Seafood reports 2015 and 2016. (Note: includes landings by foreign vessels).

Table 57: Estimated potential volumes (tonnes) of unwanted catches (below MCRS) of 6 key species in the main Irish ports

Port	Whiting	Haddock	Hake	Cod	Plaice	Nephrops	Total	Total Gadoids
Dunmore East	661	295	34	56	20	135	1,201	1,046
Castletownbere	332	361	208	46	19	114	1,080	947
Greencastle	174	343	49	16	14	6	602	582
Kilmore Quay	110	118	51	40	17	28	364	319
Union Hall	34	93	33	30	8	70	268	190
Killybegs	36	94	14	4	6	5	159	148
Howth	30	46	2	21	94	173	366	99
Dingle	15	16	60	3	0	23	117	94
Clogherhead	34	32	5	8	88	72	239	79
Ros A Mhil	14	22	10	2	3	126	177	48
Total	1,440	1420	466	226	269	752	4,573	3,552

Source: Official Irish landings figures data and port-based breakdown of landings as reported under the Data Collection Framework (DCF).

Table 58: Estimated total unwanted catch volumes (tonnes) for 6 key species in the main Irish ports, landings by Irish vessels in those ports, unwanted catches as a percentage of total key species landings

Port	<MCRS key species (tonnes)	Total Irish landings	Irish landings key species	<MCRS as % of key sp. landings
Dunmore East	1,201	10,189	5,066	24
Castletownbere	1,080	14,008	4,583	24
Greencastle	602	3,298	1,819	33
Kilmore Quay	364	5,466	1,409	26
Union Hall	268	2,305	1,378	19
Killybegs	159	152,123	490	32
Howth	366	5,703	2,303	16
Dingle	117	11,556	668	18
Clogherhead	239	1,834	1,164	21
Ros A Mhil	177	3,074	1,525	12
Total	4,573	209,556	20,405	22

The tables above show that projected below MCRS quantities will be significant and furthermore that they represent a significant proportion of landings of the six key species when examined on a port basis. The significance and likely consequences of this are discussed in greater detail later in Section 3 of the report.

7.3.2 Breakdown of Irish landings and discards of Pelagic TAC species

Discard rates in pelagic fisheries are generally much lower than in demersal fisheries, but the quantities can however be substantial. Discards in both the Irish mackerel and blue whiting fisheries were above 3,000 tonnes in 2016, as shown in the following tables (Data for this section was taken from an exercise examining pelagic and demersal discards conducted by the Pelagic

Advisory Council using a Choke Mitigation Tool which was based on the STECF landings and discards database (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dd/effort/graphs-annex>).

Table 59: Mackerel landings and discards 2016 (tonnes) by Irish vessels in all areas

Reported landings 2016 (t)	77,520
Reported discards 2016 (t)	3,247
Discard rates 2016 (%)	4%
Demersal landings 2016 (t)	9
Demersal Discards 2016 (t)	115
Total demersal catch 2016 (t)	124
% of Total catch	0.2%
Total catch 2016 (tonnes)	80,767

Table 60: Herring landings and discards (tonnes) 2016 by Irish vessels in all areas

	Celtic Sea	VlaS	VlaN	N Sea
Reported landings 2016 (t)	12,856	1,172	569	127
Reported discards 2016 (t)	88	32	2	0
Discard rates 2016 (%)	1%	3%	0%	0%
Demersal landings 2016	57	0.03	0.00	0
Demersal Discards 2016	86	32.00	0.00	0
Total demersal catch 2016	143	32.03	0.00	0
% of Total catch	1.1%	2.7%	0.0%	0.0%
Total catch 2016 (t)	12,944	1,204	571	127

Table 61: Blue Whiting landings and discards (tonnes) 2016 by Irish vessels in all areas

Reported landings 2016 (t)	27,662
Reported discards 2016 (t)	3,010
Discard rates 2016 (%)	10%
Demersal landings 2016	0
Demersal Discards 2016	275
Total demersal catch 2016	275
% of Total catch	0.9%
Total catch 2016 (t)	30,672

Table 62: Horse Mackerel landings and discards (tonnes) 2016 by Irish vessels in all areas

Reported landings 2016 (t)	29,066
Reported discards 2016 (t)	223
Discard rates 2016 (%)	1%
Demersal landings 2016	1
Demersal Discards 2016	222
Total demersal catch 2016	223
% of Total catch	1%
Total catch 2016 (t)	29,289

Table 63: Boarfish landings and discards (tonnes) 2016 by Irish vessels in all areas

Reported landings 2016 (t)	16,325
Reported discards 2016 (t)	7
Discard rates 2016 (%)	0%
Demersal landings 2016	0
Demersal Discards 2016	7
Total demersal catch 2016	7
% of Total catch	0.0%
Total catch 2016 (t)	16,332

7.3.3 Interviews/Port visits

The authors of this report had a number of meetings and interviews with sales agents, industry reps and relevant processing companies in order to get their views on likely volumes, constraining factors, infrastructural requirements, market and other economic issues. Cost and revenue data, which will inform the cost effectiveness assessments presented in the third section of this report, was also collected.

Sectors covered

- Co-op managers
- PO managers
- Pet food/Bait Company Manager
- Whitefish processors & fresh fish buyers
- Pelagic Processors
- Fishmeal and Fish Protein Plant Managers
- Enterprise Ireland Development Adviser

Ports directly covered via interviews/meetings:

- Castletownbere
- Dunmore East
- Greencastle
- Ros a Mhil
- Union Hall
- Killybegs

Interview responses:

Overall implications of the Landing Obligation

- Most found it difficult to envisage implementation of the Landing Obligation due to multiple impacts on the catching sector removing any incentive to comply. In particular the impact of landing below MCRS fish on restrictive quotas such as Haddock is seen as a major implementation barrier.
- Strong support for an incremental approach based on gradual mesh size increases, discard reduction targets and spatial discard management.

General economic issues

- There is a huge discrepancy between the value of fish for the human market and even the best-case scenario for the non-human market. Currently this is probably the bait market at a maximum price of around €400 per tonne.
- All currently available utilisation options entail significant additional costs including storage, transport and additional boxes.
- Many processors are currently not receiving any return for fish processing waste and are happy to get it off their hands. Generally, they are using a mix of pet food and mink farms in such cases.
- There is the possibility of the fresh fish market price collapsing if all previously discarded fish was landed – the example given where this scenario would most likely occur was Haddock.
- Some interviewees identified the biggest problem as one of scale or volume. They felt that currently too much white fish is exported whole and until more processing happens here it may be difficult to establish alternatives to fishmeal or pet food producers as utilisation options.

Infrastructural issues

- Cold storage capacity is already limited at all co-ops. One manager said they have 1200 boxes capacity and some days they would need 3000 just for fresh fish storage. They currently get around this by using refrigerated shipping containers as a temporary measure.
- A number of fish sales organisations, such as Kingfisher Fresh, Castletownbere, Foyle and Galway and Aran Fishermen's Co-ops, have benefitted from securing funding from BIM, under the EMFF, to increase cold storage capacity which would at least partially offset projected increases in volumes of unwanted catch. However, the issue of sending partial loads of unwanted catch to the fishmeal plant in Killybegs could still be an issue as fresh fish can only be kept in cold storage for a finite period before significant degradation occurs.
- If the Landing Obligation were implemented now there would be a public health issue with boxes of discards being stored on piers. This would inevitably create an issue with hygiene, attract pests and provoke a negative response from the public. There is some uncertainty about whether ABP rules would allow discards to be stored with fresh fish in cold stores.
- Landing of discards would also create an infrastructural issue for skippers as they have a finite cold storage capacity on vessels which could result in trips being cut short. This is one of the findings of the French EODE project (Balazuc, Coffier, Soulet, Rochet, & Leleu, 2016).

Fishmeal

- See box below for estimation of additional costs for fishmeal provided by Co-Op managers.
- There is a possibility to mitigate some costs of new boxes through BIM funding and this has been successfully achieved in some cases through the securing of EMFF funding by fishermen's co-ops.
- Despite the low return for fishmeal to fishermen or co-ops after transport and other costs have been factored in there is some scepticism that any other solution will offer a better return.

- A number of interviewees expressed dissatisfaction with the fact that the only fishmeal plant had a monopoly with a negative impact on price. There is some interest in a feasibility assessment for another fishmeal plant situated somewhere in the centre or south of the country as previous viability assessments for same had included volumes of pelagic and processing waste but did not include volumes of discards. Such an inclusion may change the viability of another fishmeal plant based in the south.
- Some interviewees mentioned a proposed fish protein and oil plant based in Mitchelstown which may be taking waste and discards. Plans for this plant have now been shelved but the insight gained by the prospective operator has been very useful in compiling this report.
- There seems to be a difference in perception of the value of returns from fishmeal between pelagic processors who have traditionally used this outlet as a way to dispose of processing waste and some whole fish discarded during processing. Their view of the prices returned are more positive than demersal representatives who are looking at fishmeal revenues in comparison with the price for fresh fish and accordingly have a much more negative perception.

7.3.4 Example costs for utilisation of demersal fish discards as fishmeal

Co-op managers provided detailed information on costs and returns associated with converting demersal discards to fishmeal. Transport costs €40-60 per tonne depending on proximity to Ireland's only fishmeal plant in Killybegs. The example given in Table 64 below gives a breakdown of costs based on one co-op manager's figures.

An issue mentioned regarding the transport of discards to the fishmeal plant was boxes which would be temporarily missing. One co-op manager estimated that the number of boxes would need to double from the current figure of 15,000 boxes. At a cost of €11 per box that is an outlay of €165,000.

There are also costs associated with additional handling, storage and washing of boxes estimated at €40 per tonne.

These costs are not perceived as viable at a current price of approximately €120 per tonne for demersal fish at the fishmeal plant.

Further examination of this option and others is given in Section 3.

Table 64: Estimated summarised costs and revenue from demersal fishmeal utilisation option based on one fisherman's co-op manager's figures

Price per tonne Demersal fishmeal	€120
Additional handling costs	€20
Additional storage costs	€25
Transport costs	€50
Return to fisherman/Co-op per tonne	€25

The return for pelagic fish is higher as due to their higher oil content they receive a price of approximately €180-200 per tonne and also handling costs are slightly less due to the use of bins rather than smaller capacity fish boxes.

Pet food

- Pet food is perceived by some managers and processors as an occasionally higher return option than fishmeal at up to €150 per tonne. However, the capacity to take significant volumes of fish is limited and suppliers felt that the pet food price would collapse in the context of landings of significant quantities of below MCRS fish.
- One pet food company manager said they received approximately 100 tonnes of discards in 2015 from vessels participating in trials but the volumes initially anticipated never materialised. There is a significant correlation between the price they can pay and the degree of mixing of species and the lowest price product they supply is a mixed fish product. DNA testing is done by his customers to ensure the species integrity of his products.
- The pet food company manager felt that there could be some added value in using discards through a Mechanically Recovered Meat process as filleting small fish, in particular where species are mixed, creates technical difficulties.
- The issue of investing in the processing of discards is complicated by the potential for the supply to shrink due to non-compliance or selectivity improvements.
- A number of co-ops and processors are disposing of their waste and discards to mink farms but they receive no economic return for this.

Bait market

- This is a “best of a bad lot” solution for some co-op managers but there may be issues with the size of the market and some supply constraints as detailed below.
- The bait market is seen by many co-op managers as an area that would have to be expanded in the context of Landing Obligation implementation and landing of below MCRS unwanted catch.
- Prices for bait depend on species and pot fishery targeted.
- Prices vary from €200 per tonne for shrimp bait to a maximum of €400 per tonne which was paid by whelk fishermen for whiting discards caught in the Herring fishery in 2016.
- Whiting, Haddock and Plaice are the most common and preferred bait for many pot fishermen.
- A major constraining factor is the capacity to freeze whole fish for the bait market before the season. The bait season for most pot fisheries lasts from March to September/October.
- Setting up a bait distribution network to widely dispersed pot fishermen is also a constraint to bait supply companies.
- The size of the bait market is uncertain – one supplier stated that it could take all discards but that the price would drop if significant quantities of below MCRS discards were landed.

New utilisation options mentioned but not currently used

- A lot of interest was expressed in small silage units and many of those contacted would like to receive further information on the costs and viability of same. The possibility of stabilising material (i.e. stopping degradation) and allowing a full transport load to be accumulated would in itself be a step forward from the current situation whereby partial loads have to be sent to the fishmeal plant in Killybegs which further reduces the potential return to fishermen.
- The manager of the pet food company said that a significant barrier to the use of silage units in ports would be the uncertainty regarding which species have been placed in the unit. If security or certainty around this issue was guaranteed it could be a viable option.

- The biggest challenge to the use of discards in producing fish protein products (Soluble Fish Protein Hydrolysate (FPH), Partly Hydrolysed Fish Protein (PHP) and Fish Bone Powder) is the mix of species which may be the only way to generate the scale needed. Whether a mix of species can produce the consistency of end product required is still uncertain.
- Usage of prawn heads for shellfish stock. One of the Co-ops has identified an interested customer and supplied some initial quantities, but quantities would likely be small.
- A very consistent message is that the higher the degree of mixing of species the lower the market price that can be achieved regardless of the utilisation method.

Other comments from interviewees

Co-op manager involved in pelagic and demersal fisheries “It’s difficult to see anything getting a better return than fishmeal.”

Co-op manager involved purely in demersal fisheries “Fishmeal, possibly protein extraction or pet food may be options for us down the line. But they are still a fraction of the value of fresh fish”.

Fresh fish buyer and bait supplier “The bait market would take the entire Irish quota if it could and pot fishermen are screaming for bait this year”.

“If whitefish discards were all landed we would have a far better picture of the state of the stocks”.

Whitefish and Salmon processor who has also taken some discards “I haven’t looked into fishmeal or other disposal options, I’m just happy that I can dispose of them free of charge for pet food and mink feed”.

Pet food and bait company manager “It’s difficult to justify investing in equipment when the supply is likely to shrink every year. Already volumes that were supposed to be landed have not materialised”.

7.4 Section 3: Cost effectiveness analysis of potential uses for UUC

It is clear from the projections in section 2 of this report that if these quantities of small fish are going to be landed in the future a significant utilisation challenge will arise. An exploration of which utilisation options and the feasibility of these is therefore required. In this section we examine currently available and potential future utilisation options. We look at costs of infrastructure and equipment and potential revenues back to fishermen for each of these options.

The cost effectiveness analysis is based on the economic return to fishermen. Although other points further along the value chain (e.g. return to processors) are also relevant, the removal of the incentive to continue discarding is the primary goal of the Landing Obligation rather than the development of further revenue streams from the processing of discards.

The cost effectiveness analysis used estimates of costs and economic returns based on some or all of the following variables: routine costs of on board handling, cost of on board infrastructure required, price returned to fisherman, transport costs, processors/sales organisations handling costs, infrastructure or equipment costs for processors/sales organisations, R&D costs for processors/sales organisations and sales price returned to processors/sales organisations.

Scenarios accounting for a number of future uncertainties and cost effectiveness analyses of these scenarios are also described. Additionally, the effect of factors which create uncertainty in these projections, such as future volumes of discards, are examined.

Economic data sources: The data used in this section and in the tables are based wherever possible on real data supplied by co-op managers, processors and buyers. Where additional equipment will be required we received indicative quotes from a number of suppliers. In some cases, we were provided with costs for similar recently installed equipment e.g. a silage unit recently installed in the Shetlands at a cost of £140,000 Stg. Out of necessity in some cases we have averaged cost data supplied. For example, an average cost of €45 per tonne for transport to either fishmeal, pet food or protein plants in the North West of Ireland was used whereas in some cases the costs are as high as €60 per tonne even for a full load. The figures outlined in the tables in this section are averages based on data provided by a number of respondents and the figure for return to fishermen may vary for particular sales agents depending on their costs and overheads.

For the more speculative options, e.g. advanced silage processing or FPH production, firm investment cost and price information can be difficult to obtain as equipment suppliers were very keen to stress that both capital costs and operating costs are highly dependent on the specific installation context and whether synergies with existing processes could be utilised. Likewise pinning down price information for the products of some of the utilisation options is difficult due to the fact that in certain countries well developed markets and distribution networks are available which may mean that the price available, for silage in Norway for instance, will not necessarily be achievable in Ireland. These cost and price issues are discussed in further detail below.

Although the data used in these economic projections are based as far as possible on real figures there will be situations where there will be higher costs or greater revenues than those presented in the tables. These tables are indicative only and some significant averaging to simplify presentation has been done.

Utilisation options analysed: From the inclusive list of utilisation options outlined in section 1 of this report we have identified a subset which are either currently available or which we consider having some potential in the medium term. The chapter below (Currently available options) provides an analysis of options either currently available or which could be available with relatively small levels of investment. The section following that (Options requiring more significant investment or longer time scales) provides a further analysis of options and scenarios which may require significant investment, but which could have potentials as usage options in the Irish context.

For various reasons some utilisation options have not been analysed in this report. In some cases, this is due to the fact that certain options may not be economically viable in Ireland. An example of this is the drying of whole fish that is only feasible in Iceland and Norway due to both environmental conditions and the availability of cheap geothermal energy. Other potential uses, such as anaerobic digestion to biogas or composting have been shown in other reports (Catchpole, Elliott, Peach, & Mangi, 2014) to provide no economic return to fishermen or to incur a disposal cost. As we are ideally looking for options which provide some incentive to comply with the Landing Obligation rather than merely to solve a disposal problem we have not explored these options further. Another category of unwanted catch utilisation are those that will require significant investment in both infrastructure and R&D before they can be considered as economically viable options. Such options may in the future be feasible, as can be seen from the Icelandic and Norwegian experiences, where high value niche products have been developed, but our focus here is on solutions in the short or medium term.

7.4.1 Currently available options

The authors of this report have concluded that the most applicable solutions at this time for utilising catches below MCRS in Ireland are for fishmeal, bait, pet food and silage. Table 65 shows the main costs and revenues associated with options currently available or in the case of silage an option which could be available with relatively small levels of investment.

The first four options in the table are already used to a significant extent as utilisation options for processing waste, pelagic fish disposal and to some extent whitefish disposal. Fishmeal is the option currently most utilised by co-ops and processors when dealing with significant volumes of fish and one reason is that the only additional costs are in transporting the fish to Killybegs. However, those transport costs are significant with a cost of €60 per tonne quoted for operators from Wexford, Cork and Kerry. Another aspect of the fishmeal option is that it delivers a relatively fixed price. Fishmeal is a global commodity and the prices are fixed according to global trends. On the positive side this means that suppliers to the fishmeal factory can be relatively certain of the price they will get but the downside is that there is a fixed ceiling to the price so the return to the

fisherman for this material can only be increased by reducing costs, of which the main one is transport.

The option to sell fish as fresh bait presents the greatest return to the fisherman and one that is unlikely to be bettered in the medium term. The price per tonne for bait is based on an average of different prices reported to me by co-ops, processors and bait supply companies. In certain fisheries and at certain times higher prices may be paid for bait, for example €400 per tonne paid for Whiting discards caught in the Herring fishery in 2016. At certain times of the year significant volumes of below MCRS fish could be disposed of in this way and in some areas, there may be very low transport costs incurred also depending on whether the bait is distributed by the supplier or picked up by the buyer. However, the average return for disposal to the bait market is probably somewhere between the fresh and frozen bait columns here as for significant parts of the year when pot fishing is not occurring freezing and storage will be a necessity.

Table 65: Costs and revenues per tonne of utilisation options for below MCRS fish in Ireland (Costs are based on 1 tonne units (25 X 40kg boxes) of below MCRS whitefish)

Economic variable	Fishmeal	Bait fresh	Bait frozen	Pet food	Silage basic
Transport	45	30	30	45	45
Labour	10	20	25	10	20
Boxing	10	10	10	10	5
Cold Storage	0	10	120	10	0
Plant installation cost ¹	0	0	0	0	80,000
Plant Capital/ton ²	0	0	0	0	32
Plant operational materials ³	0	0	0	0	2
Energy requirement	Low	Low	Medium	Low	Low
Subtotal costs	65	70	185	75	104
Price per tonne from buyer	120	250	250	130	140
Net € return per tonne to fisherman	55	180	65	55	36
Currently available to Irish whitefish industry	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

¹ Installation cost based on prices from Icelandic and Norwegian companies and a silage plant recently fitted in Shetlands by UFI.

² Based on average of 50 tons throughput per month for 10 months per annum.

³ Operating costs Acid (3.5g per 100kg @ €700 per tonne), Antioxidant (ethoxyquin) (@200ppm and €5 per kg).

Transport costs are averages based on quotes from co-op managers and processors throughout Ireland.

Cold storage costs for frozen bait are based on 2 months frozen storage @ €10 per week for 650kg pallet.

Silage price is based on indications from potential buyers for a stabilised product under controlled conditions.

We have not included additional boxing, icing and labour costs aboard the vessel as for all options, with the exception of on board silage units, these are essentially the same.

For the pet food option, pet food companies dealing with fish products in Ireland at present currently get significant supplies of processing waste which they do not pay for but cover the cost

of transport. In order for the price listed in Table 65, €130 per tonne, to be a realistic option the quality of the product would have to be good, species would have to be unmixed and supply quantities would have to be significant and stable.

The option to produce silage from unwanted catches is listed alongside the currently available options as it is a possibility that does not require significant investment. Additionally, it is being discussed throughout Europe as a potential option for the disposal of below MCRS catches, so it is appropriate to examine its feasibility here. The silage price listed here, €140 per tonne, is based on indications from potential buyers for a stabilised product produced in a controlled way. Without strict controls prices for a silage product would be the same as the fishmeal price above at €120. Reported prices in Norway are higher at approximately €200 per tonne for silage, but it is uncertain whether such prices would be achievable here given the volume of the fish silage market in Norway, synergies with the salmon industry and the well-developed transport logistics including the use of silage vessels which can transport large quantities of silage to the buyer.

The €80,000 equipment and installation cost is an average figure based on quotes from Norwegian companies and actual costs of similar units recently installed in the UK. Figure 107 below shows the layout of such a unit from a Norwegian company, Steinsvik. The cost for the system shown is approximately €65,000 but additional tanks for storing the silage would also be required.

Figure 107: Primary silage unit from Steinsvik in Norway. Secondary tanks for storing the prepared silage would also be required

The projected return to fishermen for basic silage in Table 65 is the lowest of the five options, but there are some potential savings on transport and installation costs which are analysed further in the following chapter. The main advantage of the silage system is not necessarily that it attracts a

better price but that when correctly operated the product is stabilised and protein degradation can be halted. The resulting silage could also be sold more locally as a protein supplement in animal feed and thus the transport cost could potentially be reduced.

Table 66 below shows a comparison between the potential returns per tonne of below MCRS fish with a tonne of round Whiting, round Haddock or small Plaice. The higher transport cost for small Plaice reflects the fact that it is often necessary to transport small flatfish such as Plaice to continental markets such as Zeebrugge, where there is a greater demand for them.

Table 66: Costs and revenues per tonne of utilisation options for below MCRS fish in comparison to small Haddock, Whiting and Plaice

Economic variable	Fishmeal	Bait fresh	Bait frozen	Pet food	Silage basic	Round Whg/Had	Small Plaice
Transport	45	30	30	45	45	45	120
Labour	10	20	25	10	20	10	10
Boxing	10	10	10	10	5	10	20
Cold Storage	0	10	120	10	0	0	0
Plant Costs/tonne	0	0	0	0	34	0	0
Subtotal costs	65	70	185	75	104	65	150
Price per tonne from buyer	120	250	250	130	140	1,100	900
Net € return per tonne to fisherman	55	180	65	55	36	1,035	750
Loss Vs round fish per tonne	-980	-855	-970	-980	-999		

Costs are based on 1 tonne units (25 X 40kg boxes) of below MCRS whitefish.

7.4.2 Options requiring more significant investment or longer time scales

A number of utilisation options exist which require more significant investment including more advanced processing of silage to produce concentrated silage (Fish Protein Concentrate, FPC) or hydrolysed fish protein (FPH).

FPC is a concentrated silage product that requires a combination of centrifuging, evaporation and pressing operations. Depending on the degree of processing applied the end-product can vary from a wet cake type product (essentially where liquid in the raw silage has been partially evaporated) to a virtually odourless and tasteless powder with a maximum total fat content of 0.75 per cent. The cost of processing increases with the degree of drying and fat separation required. The less processed products, which still have bone material mixed through are generally used in aquaculture and animal feed. The additional equipment required to move beyond raw silage production means that a minimum price for a first stage concentrated silage process which would include some evaporation is approximately €1,500,000. A Norwegian company, PG Flow systems, is selling an on board advanced FPC silage production process for large freezer trawlers, which utilises recycled heat from the vessels main engine for heating and evaporation and which

produces an advanced silage product without bone material. The system could be readily adapted for onshore operation also. The cost of the system is estimated at €5 to €7 million but the company claim that the silage product would have a value of €1200 to €1500 per tonne compared to a raw silage value of €200 per tonne. Whether the high prices which FPC might achieve in Norway is possible in other countries is open to question. The FPC silage system in Table 67 illustrates the economic breakdown for such a system.

FPH is a stable product with good functional properties and high nutritional value, prepared from the protein fraction of whole fish or fish by-products by chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis. It is used mainly in animal feed but can also be used in the food industry. A pilot fish protein plant has been established recently in Ireland which is focussed on the production of FPH, Partly Hydrolysed Protein (PHP), fish bone powder and fish oil from Blue Whiting and Boarfish caught by large pelagic vessels. Although gadoids and other white fish, with their low oil content, are excellent candidates for the production of FPH one of the restrictions of using the fish protein plant is that it can only operate with raw fish frozen in blocks. The additional cost of freezing is reflected in the costs in Table 67. Whether the processing of below MCRS gadoid fish is a potentially viable option at this protein plant is uncertain but may be an avenue worth exploring further.

Another option would be for a group of co-ops or processors to set up and operate a small FPH plant. The costs indicated in Table 67 for such an operation are again for a small system capable of handling 10 tons per day which if run over 200 days would process 2,000 tons per year or approximately 55% of the total projected below MCRS gadoid landings. However as can be seen from Table 67 such a small system would be difficult to operate at a profit unless all of the revenue streams from the different products (FPH, Bone powder and oil) were maximised. The general problem that smaller systems are more difficult to make profitable applies in this case also. In interviews with a prospective small FPH system operator the difficulty of making a marginal business such as this profitable was discussed. In order to make a profit it is essential that valuable markets for all products of the FPH process; the FPH powder, fish oil and bone powder, would have to be found. Additionally, the plant should ideally be located in a landing port as protein degradation sets in very early. The interviewee was also unsure whether or not below MCRS fish would provide a sufficiently stable and high-quality source of raw material in order to sell the products into high value markets.

The option to produce FPH powder of sufficient quality and under sufficiently hygienic conditions to produce food and cosmetic grade products would open up much higher potential markets, of approximately €20 per kg, but would also increase the plant investment requirements significantly.

A number of those who were interviewed mentioned that in more advanced processing such as FPC and FPH the equipment was not necessarily the greatest cost but that on an ongoing basis energy and labour costs were more significant.

The regional silage network option in Table 67 is based on a proposal made during one of the interviews that the fishmeal plant in Killybegs could organise a silage pickup and transport

operation if some funding to install a number of silage units was available and if there was some certainty that a significant supply of below MCRS fish was available.

Additionally, the option of a small fishmeal plant based in the south of the country, which could be operated by a consortium of co-ops or processors, is included in order to examine the effect of reducing transport costs. The price included here is based on a quote from an Icelandic company for a small fishmeal plant with a capacity of 40 tons per day.

Discussions with operators and prospective operators of protein plants and equipment suppliers stressed that in common with the fishmeal industry the fish protein industry is a marginal business dependent on both a reasonable level of scale and also successful marketing of multiple products arising from the process. As a result, it is likely that any success in the FPH or FPC areas will depend on strong financial backing and time to develop the multiple markets necessary to maximise revenues. This may mean that Irish companies wishing to get involved in this area would require partners from countries where these industries are already developed in order to succeed.

The economic breakdown given in Table 67 does not claim to be the definitive statement on whether or not any of these options are viable or not. For example, the breakdown for the southern-based fishmeal plant would look very different if fish processing waste and pelagic fish were also included however that is beyond the scope of this study. Even smaller fishmeal units (under 10 tons per 24 hours) are available from some Icelandic and Norwegian companies but we have not analysed these as the advice from those companies is that it is not possible to make the smallest systems profitable on a stand-alone basis.

Table 67: Costs and revenues per tonne of below MCRS fish utilisation options requiring more advanced processing (Costs are based on 1 tonne units (25 X 40kg boxes) of below MCRS whitefish)

Economic variable	Existing Protein Plant	FPC silage system	Silage FPH	Regional Silage Network	Small Fishmeal Plant
Transport	45	20	20	20	25
Labour	25	40	40	20	10
Boxing	5	5	5	5	0
Cold Storage	65	0	0	0	0
Plant installation cost	0	5,000,000 ¹	3,000,000 ²	0	3,000,000 ³
Plant Costs/ton ⁴	0	500	300	0	300
Energy requirement	Medium	High	High	Low	High
Subtotal costs	140	565	365	45	335
Price per tonne from buyer	200	400	400	140	360
€ return per tonne to fisherman	60	-165	35	95	25
Currently available to Irish whitefish industry	Possible	No	No	No	No

¹The installation costs here are based on prices from a Norwegian company, PG Flow Solutions, for a system designed for use on board a fishing vessel but which can be adapted for onshore use. <https://pg-flowsolutions.com/portfolio/pg-silage-for-high-value-fpc/>

²Installation costs based on prices from prospective FPH plant operator.

³Installation costs based on quotes for small fishmeal plant (capacity 20 tons per day) from Norwegian and Icelandic companies.

⁴The costs per tonne above are based on an annual throughput in each case of 2,000 tons per year. This is a very small figure in comparison to the throughput values for most fishmeal plants but we use that figure to illustrate what the figures look like based purely on below MCRS fish landed due to the LO.

7.4.3 Scenarios

Scenarios could account for variables such as improvements in selectivity, quota-catch mismatch, compliance or changes in economic cost-base among others. An important factor also is likely to be time, as experiences from Norway and Iceland have shown that over time significant economic activity by companies specialising in high-value, niche products from viscera or other parts of fish can develop. Although such companies may not appear overnight their potential development in the context of long-term landings of unwanted catches will be considered in our analysis.

Figure 108: Scenarios likely to affect discard volumes and associated costs

Equipment costs shown in Table 67 for new protein or fishmeal plants are for relatively small units. An even smaller €1 million plant with a daily capacity of less than 10 tons is available from the Icelandic company Hedinn (<https://hedinn.com/fishmeal-processing/>). However, even according to the manufacturing company it is impossible to make a unit like this profitable on a stand-alone basis. It would only work as part of a larger processing operation, with associated cost efficiencies and

synergies particularly regarding labour and energy. For that reason, we have used slightly larger units with a somewhat higher installation cost but even at that size some of the difficulties in making a stand-alone unit profitable exist.

Consequences of reduction in volume of discards

A decrease in discard volumes, either due to non-compliance or improved selectivity, would not have an overly negative impact on existing options such as the use of the fishmeal plant in Killybegs. However, it would have a significant effect on any business plans which require even low levels of investment. Options that are marginal in a high-volume scenario will become unfeasible without significant moves towards higher value products and markets. This highlights a structural problem with the Landing Obligation when it comes to the disposal of small fish as their quantities should theoretically decrease over time therefore compromising the incentive for investment in market-based solutions.

However, where a decrease in discard volumes occurs due to selectivity improvements, the negative impact of reduced volumes on processing options ashore would be offset by more profitable and selective fishing activities and an associated improvement in efficiency of quota use. This can be clearly seen when comparing the value of round fish above MCRS with the best available values for below MCRS fish. Table 68 demonstrates that a fisherman would have to land at best 6 tons of below MCRS fish to receive the same economic return as 1 tonne of round fish above MCRS and at worst 29 tons.

Table 68: Equivalent number of tons required for various utilisation options to equal value of Round Whiting/Haddock and small Plaice

Economic variable	Fishmeal	Bait fresh	Bait frozen	Pet food	Silage basic	Round Whg/Had	Small Plaice
Subtotal costs	65	70	185	75	104	65	150
Price per ton from buyer	120	250	250	130	140	1,100	900
Net € return per ton to fisherman	55	180	65	55	36	1,035	750
Tons required to equal value of 1 ton roundfish	19	6	16	19	29		
Tons required to equal value of 1 ton small plaice	14	4	12	14	21		

Cost reduction

The main costs associated with unwanted catch utilisation are initially infrastructure costs and on an ongoing basis transport, labour and energy costs. The issue of reducing initial infrastructure costs by looking at the economics of small processing units is complicated by the fact that small units are more difficult to make profits from in a marginal industry. The Regional Silage Network

option in Table 67 is based on reduced transport costs arising from a partnership with the buyer and reduced infrastructure costs if funding to install silage units can be sourced. This scenario could be the only potential way in the medium term that an improvement in returns to fishermen could be achieved over and above the currently available options of bait, fishmeal or pet food. Whether the circumstances required for such a scenario, in particular the necessity for a stable and significant raw material supply, are realistic is not certain at this point however.

Achieving cost reductions through synergies with other processing operations is possible. There are one or two caveats to how this can be achieved however. Buyers from multiple sectors continually stressed the fact that the more mixing of species and species types that occurred the lower the price of the product would be.

7.5 Conclusions

In this section we summarise the best options for the utilisation of unwanted catch in Ireland in the short and medium term and the most relevant issues which may positively or negatively impact on those options. The most important challenge we address is which uses could provide an economic return to Irish fishermen landing unwanted catches and thus incentivise compliance with the LO. We conclude with some points about which criteria are most likely to create the right conditions for an economically feasible utilisation option.

The first point is that there are no “magic bullet” solutions which can produce high economic returns to fishermen for size classes of fish which previously had no economic value. Returns will be in most cases a fraction of the value that smaller grades of above minimum size fish can achieve.

One of the implications of this finding is that concern that the LO, by requiring fishermen to land small fish, would result in the targeting of undersize and juvenile fish is unfounded. At least in the case of Ireland there is no possibility of this occurring under current conditions. Unfortunately, this also implies that there are not significant economic incentives to comply with the Landing Obligation in the sense that compliance means the landing of small fish. Quota Uplift, the raising of quotas to account for fish that was previously discarded should address at least some of these economic losses issue.

The second implication and the flipside of the first, is that there is a huge incentive to fish more selectively and, as far as possible to utilise the quota available in the most economically rational manner. The landing of below MCRS fish will lead to the loss of a large part of the future economic value in those fish. The values we have calculated for currently available options show that 1 tonne of above MCRS fish is worth between 6 and 19 times the value of 1 tonne of below MCRS fish.

Selectivity improvements alone cannot resolve all Landing Obligation issues however and some residual unwanted catches will always be an issue in most demersal fisheries. In such cases the best current utilisation option appears to be the pot fishery bait market. When averaging between fresh and frozen supplies to this market a value of €100 to €120 per tonne could be returned to the fisherman for below MCRS fish landed. While significant investment in advanced equipment is not required for this option the main infrastructural constraint here is access to refrigerated

and frozen storage. This issue has been successfully addressed by a number of co-ops and sales agents who have received EMFF funding from BIM to improve storage infrastructure. Even in upgraded facilities at certain times when large volumes of commercial landings are present there would still be competition for space in refrigerated storage.

The next best currently available utilisation options are fishmeal, which can essentially take an unlimited supply, and pet food which can take more limited quantities. Both options would deliver a price per tonne to fishermen of approximately €50 per tonne. This highlights the fact that the price differential in demersal fish between small size grades of fish sold on the fresh market and fishmeal is far higher than it is for pelagic fish which is why the fishmeal option is only used occasionally for demersal fish. The prices achievable in the fishmeal option are essentially fixed as fishmeal is a global commodity and significant improvements on that price are highly unlikely.

In the pet food option there may be opportunities to improve prices to a level above that outlined in our initial analysis. Conversations with pet food company operators and Enterprise Ireland experts in the area have highlighted that there is a growing market for high quality niche pet food products from whole fish or fish-based ingredients. In common with any other potentially promising options the requirement would be for a reasonably stable and significant supply of good quality fish with as little mixing of species as possible. The high value pet food market is an option that is worth exploring further.

A potential option, which is being discussed throughout Europe, is the use of small silage units to stabilise unwanted catches either at sea or ashore before distributing the product to fishmeal plants or other buyers. The difficulty with this option is that it does not add significant value to the product without further concentration and concentration requires more significant investment in equipment. The main advantage of the basic silage process is that it prevents further degradation of the product and allows for the accumulation of silage until a full transport load is ready and thereby reduces transport costs. A network of regional silage units, partly funded by EMFF or other funding, with a partnership arrangement for transport with a fishmeal plant or other buyer and fed by a significant supply of raw material would have some potential to reduce costs and deliver a reasonable return to fishermen.

In the medium term there are a number of options that would require more significant investment but could potentially deliver higher value products. A common problem across almost all of these options is that there is a conflict between the investments required, their high supply volume nature, and the policy goal of the LO, which is to reduce the supply of undersized fish. The fact that to date only very small volumes of below MCRS catches have been landed throughout Europe adds to the unattractive nature of these options for investors, at least currently. One exception to this is the possibility that a supply of gadoid fish could potentially be block frozen and processed through the new fish protein plant in the North West of the country. The technical details and economic viability of this would have to be worked out but it is an option worth exploring as potentially there could be a high value market available for the products of this process.

In the long term what should be aimed at, in line with the desired goal of the Landing Obligation to reduce unwanted catches, is high value uses of smaller volumes of below MCRS fish which cannot be avoided. This calls into question any business plans and large infrastructural

investments based solely on discards. Viable options would have to be established in conjunction with existing processing operations and existing supply lines of processing waste or low value commercial grades of fish.

To summarise in order to successfully add value to unwanted catches in the longer term it appears that most if not all of the following criteria should be met:

- Prospective operators would have to be confident that a reasonable supply of smaller fish will be available in the first place.
- Prospective plants should ideally be in, or at least in close proximity to, a fishing port where significant landings will occur as protein degradation in fish occurs quickly.
- Synergies with other fish processing activities are essential in particular regarding energy recycling and labour.
- A long-term approach will have to be taken by any prospective operator. Experiences from Norway and Iceland have shown that over time significant economic activity by companies specialising in high-value, niche products from viscera or other parts of fish will not appear overnight but develop over time.
- The financial clout and long-term commitment required means that either a large co-operative or consortium would be necessary in order to sustain the enterprise.
- It will be necessary to fully exploit high value niche markets for all product streams in order to get the most value from the raw material. For example, a fish protein (FPH) operation could target pharmaceutical products or human functional foods at the higher level, performance proteins for high-end animal feed at the middle level and high-quality fertiliser at the lower level. A successful example of this approach is the case of Celtic Sea Minerals, based in Castletownbere, which has gradually, through investment in R&D, increased the niche value of its products over time.
- Achieving this will require significant technical and marketing expertise and a commitment to R&D.
- Companies in other countries with a history of bycatch and by-product utilisation have built up significant expertise in both the technical aspects of these processes and in the marketing of the final products so a partnership approach with such companies would be advisable.

8 Discussions

The title of this report is “Report on validation in pilot case studies” and it is the fifth and final deliverable of work package five in the H2020 DiscardLess project. The work package is titled “from deck to first sale” and it is intended to explore, suggest, develop and validate alternatives for on board handling of UUC that will have to be landed as results of the CFP Landing Obligation. The authors have selected six pilot case studies for this purpose, which have been selected to provide a relevant cross-section of the EU fleet and the countries affected by the Landing Obligation.

The report has focuses on four different fishing fleet sectors and two national examples, varying in size and operation. The report is structured in such a way that each case is independent, which has allowed the reader to choose what case studies to read. This does however mean that there has been some repetition for those that have read the report as a whole; particularly on technical specification.

The six case studies presented in the report are small-scale coastal vessels, intermediate size bottom trawlers / Danish seiners, large-scale fresh fish bottom trawlers, and large factory bottom trawler; as well as national examples/analysis of how the Greek and the Irish fishing sectors can attempt meet the requirements of the Landing Obligation.

The first four cases are presented with detailed 3D drawings of the vessels along with renders of images and videos on the DiscardLess webpage <http://www.discardless.eu> which enables stakeholders to see the results in a visual manner. Furthermore, a cost-benefit tool has been developed and it can also be found on the website. The cost-benefit tool allows stakeholders to get raw estimates on the investment needed, operating costs, revenues and return of investment based on the fleet type, the gear chosen and assumptions on catch and catch composition. The most relevant outcome of the work reported on in this report is therefore not the report itself, but the drawings, videos and cost-benefit tool that is now publicly available on the DiscardLess webpage.

All the solutions presented in the report are currently available on-board fishing vessels and are being used by several fleet segments and therefore the focus has been on making them as realistic as possible for the reader; with the intention of providing stakeholders with the necessary facts that they can judge for themselves if the identified solutions are applicable for their own case.

The solutions focus largely on separating between the target catches and the unwanted catches and to provide alternatives for processing and storing under MCRS catches, as well as other UUC. These categories cannot be utilized for direct human consumption according to the Landing Obligation of the EU Common Fisheries Policy.

Given the current status of the EU seafood sector and how it is presently adapting to the Landing Obligation, it is the opinion of the authors of this report that there is a need for implementing short-term simple solutions to meet the requirements of the Landing Obligation; but that strategies for long-term solutions need also to be drafted. The main emphasis of this report has been on short-term solutions, primarily in the form of silage, fishmeal and fish oil production that can be implemented

immediately. The report has though also identified and discussed more complicated long-term solutions that require significant investment and forward thinking of everyone in the value chain.

It is the hope of the authors that this report, along with the blueprints, videos and cost-benefit tools available on the DiscardLess webpage will contribute to meaningful discussions on the Landing Obligation and possibly pave a way for a successful implementation.

The work reported on in this report contributed to a chapter on “vessel modifications” in a book published by Springer on “*The European Landing Obligation: Reducing Discards in complex, Multi, species and Multi-Jurisdictional Fisheries*” <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8>

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